

**OUT OF THE SILO: A QUALITATIVE
STUDY OF PARAMEDIC TRANSITION TO A
SPECIALIST ROLE IN COMMUNITY
PARAMEDICINE**

David N Long

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For my boys
Ayden, Callum and Kynan

"Fail and all your dreams may just come true"

Keywords

Ambulance; Community Paramedic; community paramedicine; CP; ECP; EMS;
Extended Care Paramedic; low-acuity; pre-hospital; Paramedic;
paramedicine; qualitative; specialisation; specialist; work role transition.

Abstract

Community paramedicine is an evolving specialist stream of paramedic practice comprising two dominant service delivery models; those aligned with an Extended Care Paramedic (ECP)-type model and those aligned with a Community Paramedic (CP)-type model. The underlying philosophy of community paramedicine is to provide patients in the community with options to navigate more efficiently the healthcare system and avoid unnecessary presentations to a hospital emergency department. Community paramedicine contrasts with “traditional” paramedic practice by targeting non-urgent patients who may benefit from an expanded scope of practice in both scheduled and unscheduled out-of-hospital care. However, little is known about the process of transition of paramedics from a work role in traditional paramedicine to a specialist work role in community paramedicine. To date, specialist work role transitions in paramedicine have been largely neglected in the literature. This study aims to illuminate how qualified paramedics can transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine.

The study recruited ECPs (n=25) from two Australian jurisdictions and CPs (n=11) from a Canadian provincial health service, in a qualitative study exploring their experiences of transition. The data from the three study sites were pooled and interpreted using constructivist grounded theory methodology, as informed by Charmaz (2014). The analysis revealed transition to a work role in community paramedicine involved four phases. The first phase represented a junctional point in a paramedic’s clinical career trajectory in which the decision to enter a community paramedicine pathway was made. Three “active” phases of transition followed in which participants engaged formally in the transition process. Additionally, four core categories of transition were interwoven through each active phase of transition; *Engaging in a Community of Practice*, *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change*, *Developing Critical Thinking* and, *Mastering Skills*. The evolution of each of the four core categories contributed “ancillary markers” of transition, that

coalesced to define the end-point of transition: *Adequate proficiency in the work role.*

The significance of this PhD research is demonstrated by positioning the study beyond the practical transferability of extant work role transition theories. Certainly elements of leading work role transition theories in paramedicine (Devenish, Clark, & Fleming, 2016; McFarlane, 2010), nursing (Barnes, 2014; Benner, 1984; Boychuk Duchscher, 2009) and generic organisational literature (Nicholson, 1984), resonates with the current study. For instance, experiencing negative emotions early in the transition experience was a common finding across the literature. However, no existing theory of work role transition can illuminate adequately the complex interplay between the elements, core categories and phases that comprise the community paramedicine transition experience.

This PhD study makes a significant contribution to the understanding of how paramedics transition to a specialist work role in community paramedicine. The unique knowledge generated by this study allows for additional targeted intervention points for paramedics to navigate more efficiently the transition experience. Ultimately, the precision gained in understanding the relationships between the various elements of transition within a conceptual and temporal framework, may decrease the time frame to deploy high-quality, ready-to-work paramedics in the community.

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List of Abbreviations

AHS EMS	Alberta Health Services Emergency Medical Services
CGT	Constructivist Grounded Theory
CP	Community Paramedic
ECP	Extended Care Paramedic
EMT-P	Emergency Medical Technologist – Paramedic
ICP	Intensive Care Paramedic
NSWA	New South Wales Ambulance
OHCP	Other Healthcare Professional
QP	Qualified Paramedic
SAAS	South Australia Ambulance Service

Definition of Key Terms

Community Paramedic	An experienced paramedic operating within a “preventative” model of community paramedicine by working collaboratively with other primary care services under local medical control (doctor supervision).
Community Paramedicine	A specialist clinical stream of paramedicine in which paramedics collaborate with other healthcare professionals to deliver “non-traditional”, community-based care utilising an expanded scope of practice.
ECP/CP	Collective term for paramedics that work under the auspice of community paramedicine.
Extended Care Paramedic	An experienced paramedic operating within a “reactive” model of community paramedicine by responding to calls for unscheduled care. ECPs have a dual role in the delivery of traditional (high-acuity/urgent) care as operational needs arise.
Paramedic Service	An agency that delivers emergency and non-emergent care by paramedics in the out-of-hospital setting. <i>Synonyms: Ambulance Service, Emergency Medical Service.</i>
Paramedicine	“The unique domain of education, practice and self-determination of paramedics, which includes traditional emergency response, and evolving non-emergent roles such as community paramedicine” (Batt, Ward, & Acker, 2017).
Primary Care	“The first (primary) layer of services encountered in health care and requires teams of health

professionals working together to provide comprehensive, continuous and person-centred care” (Australian Government, 2017).

Qualified Paramedic

A paramedic who has completed the minimum mandatory training for paramedic practice, mandated in their respective jurisdiction.

Specialist

A Qualified Paramedic who has undergone additional training to develop a unique skill-set and specific expertise in an area of paramedic practice.

Traditional Care in a Paramedic Service

The delivery of emergency and non-emergent care by paramedics in the out-of-hospital setting, resulting most often in the transport of the patient to a health facility.

Work role transition

“Any change in employment status and any change in job content” (Nicholson, 1984).

Publications and Presentations stemming from this PhD Study

Long, D. (2015). *From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role*. Poster presented at Paramedics Australasia International Conference, Adelaide, South Australia.

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Long, D., Clark, M., Lim, D., Devenish, S. (2016). What's in a name? The confusion in nomenclature of low-acuity specialist roles in paramedicine. [Commentary]. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, 13(3), 1-2.

Long, D. (2017). *Defining the end-point of transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine: Is feeling "comfortable" enough?* Oral presentation at Paramedics Australasia Conference, Melbourne, Victoria.

Statement of Original Authorship

The work contained in this thesis has not been previously submitted to meet requirements for an award at this or any other higher education institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published or written by another person except where due reference is made.

Signature: [QUT Verified Signature](#)

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The sky's the limit!

Chapter 1: Introduction

Paramedics are increasingly seen as an integral component of the healthcare continuum (Cooper & Grant, 2009). Although the core functions of paramedic services to treat and transport the sick and injured to hospital have remained largely unchanged, a significant paradigm shift in the care of non-urgent patients has been gathering momentum over the last two decades (Catterall, 2012). The impetus for change is multi-factorial, and yet an overarching sense of “missed opportunities” to improve the health care journey of paramedic service patients has been growing in prominence (Joyce, Wainer, Piterman, Wyatt, & Archer, 2009). Paramedic services across North America, the United Kingdom and Australasia have embraced progressively new paradigms of care in the primary care setting. Although the nomenclature used to describe the work roles by specialist paramedics engaged in community paramedicine varies between jurisdictions, the principal function remains the same - to more efficiently navigate the patient through the healthcare system and provide pathways other than defaulting to the emergency department.

Despite a growth of specialist clinical roles within paramedicine, little is known about how paramedics make the transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine. The aim of the study was to develop a theoretical understanding of the process and influencing factors of transition from Qualified Paramedic to specialist work role in community paramedicine. The influencing factors provide further insight into the aspects of transition which either accelerated or decelerated the process of transition. Constructivist grounded theory has been selected as the most appropriate methodology to examine systematically the transition from Qualified Paramedic (QP) to Extended Care Paramedic (ECP) or Community Paramedic (CP), with an emphasis on theory construction rather than simply process description (Charmaz, 2014). Moreover, the subjectivist epistemology of constructivism has been utilised as a suitable “lens” through which to view this study.

Paramedicine has become more professionalised, as evidenced by the move to university training (O'Meara, 2009). As with many professional health disciplines such as medicine, allied health and nursing, increased professionalisation in paramedicine has led to increased specialisation in work roles. The creation of a specialised role under the auspices of community paramedicine mirror other specialised roles in paramedicine such as those of Intensive Care Paramedics (ICP) and Retrieval Paramedics (RP) (Paramedics Australasia, 2009).

Little is known about why paramedics seek to specialise in community paramedicine. Unlike the disciplines of medicine and nursing, no studies were identified in the literature review (Chapter 2) which specifically examine the process of transition from QP to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Thus, the constructivist grounded theory approach is appropriate to the study of role transition, as the logic of grounded theory resides in the analysis of processes and actions rather than themes and structures (Charmaz, 2014). Furthermore, a constructivist approach emphasises the engagement of the researcher as an active participant in the research process and makes explicit the preconceptions, values and experiences that may influence the analysis (Charmaz, 2014).

An understanding of the process of transition may translate to enhancements of paramedic educational programs and facilitate the recruitment, selection and retention of paramedics in a community paramedicine role. Additionally, a holistic understanding of transition may contribute significantly to the more efficient operationalisation of new community paramedicine services and decrease the time frame to deploy high-quality and ready-to-work paramedics in the field. Ultimately, the research seeks to generate new knowledge that may inform policy and models of care to deliver a measurable impact on both effectiveness (clinical outcomes) and efficiency (service delivery).

1.1 COMMUNITY PARAMEDICINE: A BRIEF INTRODUCTION

The paramedicine discipline continues to undergo transformative changes. The evidence lies in the development of key areas such as paramedic education (Joyce, et al., 2009; O'Brien, Moore, Dawson, & Hartley, 2014), discipline-specific research (O'Meara, 2012; Patterson & Skillman, 2013) and work role specialisation (Colbeck, 2014; Seel & Turner, 2016). Indeed, the advent of community paramedicine as a specialist clinical stream of paramedic practice is testament to the ongoing professionalisation of paramedicine. However, there is no uniform agreement in the definition of "community paramedicine" in the literature, and to add to the confusion, some terms are used interchangeably (Long, 2016). For clarity, this PhD has defined community paramedicine as:

A specialist clinical stream of paramedicine in which paramedics collaborate with other healthcare professionals to deliver 'non-traditional', community-based care utilising an expanded scope of practice.

In brief, two dominant service delivery models comprise community paramedicine: those aligned with an Extended Care Paramedic (ECP) type-model and those aligned with a Community Paramedic (CP) type-model¹. ECPs most often operate in a "reactive" model of service delivery, that is, ECPs will respond to calls for unscheduled care, for predominantly low-acuity or non-urgent conditions. It should be noted however, that the term low-acuity may not define the severity or complexity of the patient's presenting problem. CPs on the other hand, work in a "preventative" model of care by working collaboratively with other primary care and social services in areas such as

¹ Some commentators argue a distinct third model, Mobile Integrated Healthcare (MIH) in the United States, falls under the auspice of community paramedicine (O'Meara, Stirling, Ruest, & Martin, 2016). However, this PhD study argues MIH is conceptually aligned with the CP-type model. Moreover, the position of this PhD study is consistent with the views of other recent publications from the US that use the terms "Mobile Integrated Healthcare" and "Community Paramedic" interchangeably (Choi, Blumberg, & Williams, 2016; Coffman, Wides, Niedzwiecki, & Geyn, 2017).

chronic disease management, health promotion and education and early intervention.

Broadly, the aims of community paramedicine can be defined through an amalgam of the conceptual underpinnings of ECP and CP programs (Bigham, Kennedy, Drennan, & Morrison, 2013; Kizer, Shore, & Moulin, 2013; O'Meara, et al., 2016). The aims are to:

- More efficiently navigate a patient through the healthcare system and provide options other than presentation to an emergency department.
- Increase access to primary care services for medically underserved populations, particularly in rural/regional areas.
- Enhance opportunities for the development of paramedic clinical practice.

Paramedic training in community paramedicine varies according to local community needs and availability of existing resources in the community (Choi, et al., 2016). In the United States for example, the Community Healthcare and Emergency Cooperative has developed a standardised community paramedicine curriculum. Colleges across the United States that utilise the curriculum can adapt the curriculum to suit local needs (Kizer, et al., 2013). Graduate level community paramedicine programs are well established in the United Kingdom (Catterall, 2012) and have recently been developed as a Master's program in Australia (Edith Cowan University, 2016; Monash University Extended Care Paramedic, 2017). For many paramedic services however, initial community paramedicine training is provided "in-house" and is tailored to fit the individual service's objectives (Gresens, 2017; White & Wingrove, 2012).

Following completion of initial training, ECPs/CPs operate with an expanded scope of practice. Examples of the skill sets and competencies for ECPs/CPs include:

- local anaesthetic techniques
- suturing techniques
- wound care
- principles of dressings and splinting
- joint examinations
- neurologic, cardiovascular, respiratory system examination
- medication dispensing including analgesia, antibiotics, tetanus toxoid
- intravenous therapy and rehydration
- mobility and social needs assessments
- requests for radiography
- referral processes, including emergency department, general practitioner, district nurse and community social services (Bigham, et al., 2013; Mason et al., 2007; Nolan, Hillier, & D'Angelo, 2012).

However, due to the heterogenous landscape of community paramedicine programs worldwide, it is inappropriate to narrowly define community paramedicine in terms of training curricula or scope of practice. Community paramedicine is best viewed conceptually as an approach to meeting the healthcare needs of a medically underserved community. In this regard, paramedics service a niche in the healthcare system that other healthcare professionals are unable or unwilling to provide. The literature review in Chapter 2 provides a more detailed analysis of the background, trends and arguments in community paramedicine through two foci: evolution and drivers of change in paramedicine and service delivery models in community paramedicine.

1.2 RELEVANCE OF THE RESEARCH TOPIC

Community paramedicine is gaining momentum worldwide with various pilot programs trialled in Canada, the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand (O'Meara, 2014). Evaluations of community

paramedicine programs have generally demonstrated positive outcomes in areas such as patient safety, cost effectiveness, integration with community health services and ambulance transport to emergency departments (Coffman, et al., 2017; Mason et al., 2009; Thompson et al., 2014). Yet despite the growing popularity of community paramedicine programs, little is known about *how* Qualified Paramedics transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine.

To date, an understanding of work role transition in paramedicine has been informed from a singular perspective; vocational or university-trained students transitioning to the paramedic service workplace (Devenish, et al., 2016; Kennedy, Kenny, & O'Meara, 2015; Lazarsfeld-Jensen, Bridges, & Carver, 2014; Lazarsfeld-Jensen, Bridges, & Loftus, 2011). However, elements of the new-to-practice transition process clearly do not resonate with the transition of seasoned practitioners to a specialist role. Similar arguments render the transferability of work role transition theories from the nursing discipline (Barnes, 2014; Benner, 1984; Boychuk Duchscher, 2009) and generic literature (Nicholson, 1984) problematic.

Few theoretical studies have been published in the community paramedicine space. O'Meara (2014, p. 11) quite rightly argues that "without a theoretical basis, empirical studies of community paramedicine models will tend to remain descriptive and ambiguous in nature." Consequently, this PhD research is well placed to make a significant contribution to the theoretical basis upon which community paramedicine models are built. In particular, areas including job design, recruitment and retention strategies, support mechanisms and capability development may benefit from the outputs of this study.

1.3 RESEARCH AIMS AND QUESTIONS

The aim of the study is to develop a theoretical understanding of paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine and determine the factors that either accelerate or decelerate the transition process. Therefore, the primary research question is, "*How do paramedics*

transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine?" The second research question is, *"What are the influencing factors that accelerate or decelerate the transition process?"*

1.4 OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH APPROACH

Constructivist grounded theory (CGT), based on the work of Charmaz (2014), informs the methodological approach of this PhD study. A defining feature of CGT is the focus on explicating a process or action (Charmaz, 2014). Given that existing theories of work role transition in cognate health fields indicate transition is a process (Boychuk Duchscher, 2008; Spoelstra & Robbins, 2010; Westerman et al., 2010), CGT is considered a suitable approach for the community paramedicine setting. Additionally, grounded theory methods are flexible, iterative and complementary to theory development (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). A focus on theory development is significant as it moves the findings away from simple description, towards an abstracted understanding of the transition experience. Chapter Four provides further rationale for the design of this PhD research and the methods used in the collection and analysis of the data.

1.5 REFLEXIVITY

Constructivist grounded theory positions the researcher as an active participant of the research. Consequently, the research product is informed by the researcher's own experiences, perspectives, history and positions (Creswell, 2012; Liamputtong, 2009). Reflexivity engages the researcher in critical self-reflection to make explicit the researcher's contribution to shaping the data and analysis (Johnson & Waterfield, 2004). In this regard, reflexivity enhances the rigour of a grounded theory by critically examining the researcher's effect on data construction (Urquhart, 2012). By making the subjective viewpoints of the researcher known, the reader is better placed to make interpretative judgements on the relevance and value of the research findings (Malterud, 2001a). Although some authors have counselled against using reflective techniques, citing they are poor quality assurance measures (Birks & Mills, 2011; Cutcliffe & McKenna, 2004), Charmaz (2017a) emphasises

the importance of deep reflectivity or “methodological self-consciousness” in understanding how the researcher’s worldviews, language and meanings enter the research process.

The following two accounts bring reflexivity into the foreground, making explicit the potential influences on the research journey. The first account is a scrutiny of the researcher’s involvement in the research process. The second is a personal biography of the researcher to further illuminate the researcher’s background and connection with the research topic. These are discussed in turn.

1.5.1 Scrutiny of researcher’s involvement

Reflexivity was built into each phase of the research process. The principal tool to engage reflexivity was memoing², supported by reflective discussions with the researcher’s supervisory team. An early example of engaging reflexivity occurred during the development of the interview guide. Existing work role transition theories from cognate disciplines including nursing were assumed to harbour tentative clues³ to the process of paramedic transition to community paramedicine, and therefore guided the design of the initial interview questions. However, I was also strongly motivated to undertake a PhD study to create new discipline-specific knowledge, thereby gradually weaning paramedicine off its reliance on other disciplines. By engaging reflectivity, I was questioning whether the interview guide served any other purpose than the achievement the study’s aims. For instance, I considered whether the questions aligned paramedicine too closely with nursing and indeed, if the questions were subtly admonishing the nursing discipline.

In addition, every interview with a participant provided an opportunity to engage reflexivity. For instance, I had worn my operational uniform (as a

² In brief, memoing is a written record of analysis; a means of having a dialogue with one’s self to garner clarity from the complexity of the data (Corbin & Strauss, 2015).

³ “Tentative clues” are also known as sensitising concepts (Charmaz, 2014) and is referred to in greater detail in Chapter 4: Methodology.

matter of convenience after completing a shift) to an interview with a participant who was employed by the same paramedic service. The uniform clearly designates clinical capacity through patches and epaulettes. Almost immediately, the participant, who was not certified as an Intensive Care Paramedic, greeted me by saying, "Oh, I didn't know you were IC!"⁴ From the participant's response, it was reasonable to assume the uniform may carry tacit implications of power and authority, augmenting the known power imbalance between researcher and participant (Råheim et al., 2016). Although it was not my intention, the very perception of a subtle power imbalance may have compromised trust and rapport. Trust and rapport are vital in qualitative interviews to allow the richness and depth in the data to emerge (McConnell-Henry, James, Chapman, & Francis, 2009).

Later during the data analysis phase, reflectivity was again employed when examining the influence of management practices on paramedic transition. Late in my paramedic career, I had become disillusioned with the management and operation of ECPs in the paramedic service which employed me. Through memoing and engaging with supervisory colleagues, questions arose about the analysis became more overt. The questions included:

- Had I overstated the influence on paramedic transition of a community paramedicine program manager based on my prior perceptions of managers?
- Had I misinterpreted the intent of participants as a whole, by focusing on individual participants?
- Because I felt dissatisfied in my previous employment, had that affected my analysis? Was I over-representing participants who demonstrated congruence with my own views?
- Was there a relationship between power, identity and publication of a research product favourable to a particular point of view?

⁴ IC – Intensive Care Paramedic

The importance of a strong thread of reflexivity throughout the research process should not be underestimated. Equally important is the recognition of the researcher as an active participant in shaping the analysis. The following section provides a personal biography to provide the reader with further insight into my own background and experiences that may have generated possible biases.

1.5.2 Personal biography

My interest in first aid was originally piqued during high school where I was introduced to basic first aid courses during my time in the Australian Army Cadets. Following school, I completed an undergraduate degree in disability services. Although strongly motivated to improve the lives of people with a disability, the remunerations in the disability sector were poor. Moreover, I found myself longing for more “excitement” in a vocation. Searching for the nexus between personal and professional needs, my attention was drawn towards paramedicine. On my second application to an Australian paramedic service, I was accepted into the vocational training program in 1998 and upon graduation, was posted to a large metropolitan region. I completed a paramedic diploma in 2001 and obtained my Advanced Diploma in Intensive Care Paramedicine in 2004. After a few years of work as an Intensive Care Paramedic, and having completed an undergraduate degree in Pre-Hospital Care, I began to feel the need to extend myself further. Somewhat fortuitously, the paramedic service I was employed by began recruiting for a new model of healthcare delivery – Extended Care Paramedic (ECP). Initially, my colleagues and I knew little about the concept. However, I was aware that ECPs would practice with an expanded scope to improving patient clinical outcomes. I found this prospect appealing and enthusiastically applied for a position. I was successful in becoming one of 12 paramedics to undertake the inaugural ECP course in 2007.

I did not appreciate at the time that the journey of work role transition from an emergency paramedic to community paramedicine had begun. The ECP course consisted of an initial 10-week didactic component at a university

campus. The course was a revelation; the curriculum stimulated clinical reasoning which was a marked departure from the protocol-driven format of earlier "in-house" paramedic courses. Lecturers were also highly credentialed, and I was excited to learn new clinical procedures to complement my existing ICP practice. At the time, I felt that participating in the ECP program contributed to the continuing professionalisation of paramedicine.

The initial deployment into the community was daunting and replete with negative emotions due to the many challenges of engaging in a new work role. However, I relished the challenges of not only working with an expanded scope of practice, but also as a single responder. As the months went by, my confidence in the work role continued to grow. Every time a new procedure was completed or patient follow-up revealed a satisfactory outcome, I advanced in the transition process. I revelled in the camaraderie of the ECP cohort as we all worked towards the common goal of proving the community paramedicine concept a success.

Unfortunately, the unique milieu of the ECP program was not to last. After a year and a half or so in the program, many of the original cohort, including myself, became disillusioned and frustrated with the management and operation of the ECP program. Moreover, some of our traditional care paramedic colleagues seemed to view community paramedicine as a simplification, or worse still, a de-evolution of the paramedic role. The sense of being undervalued was pervasive and deeply affected my morale. After a short stint interstate, I returned to the same paramedic service later the same year, to be re-employed as an ICP. Unfortunately, no policies existed at the time for the re-credentialing of ECPs.

1.6 OVERVIEW OF STUDY SITES

The previous section established reflexivity as an interpretative tool for the reader to gauge the relevance and value of the research findings. On a similar vein, an overview of the paramedic services and the respective community paramedicine programs that participated in this PhD study, speaks to the resonance or transferability of this research to other settings (Lincoln &

Guba, 1985; Tracy, 2010). Transferability is the extent to which the reader can justifiably relate the findings of the current study to another setting (Shenton, 2004). In this regard, providing a rich and thick description of the context in which paramedic transition occurs, moves this PhD study away from a purely scholastic discussion to that of having practical, “real-world” applications.

1.6.1 South Australia Ambulance Service (SAAS)

South Australia (SA) is the fourth largest state or territory in Australia with a total area of 983,482 square kilometres (Figure 1.1). Around three quarters of the total population of 1.7 million people are located in the capital Adelaide and surrounding metropolitan areas (South Australia Government, 2017). SAAS attended over 280,000 cases in 2015-16 and transported approximately 231,000 patients (SA Ambulance Service, 2016). SAAS operate an Extended Care Paramedic program that was established in 2008. The operational footprint of the program includes metropolitan Adelaide and fringe areas as required. Approximately 35 ECPs are currently engaged in the program and attended 4,706 cases in 2011-12 (SA Ambulance Service, 2013). SAAS ECPs are recruited exclusively from the ICP ranks and therefore have previous experience of work role transition to a specialist clinical role within a paramedic service.

Figure 1.1 Location of South Australia in Australia (inset). Map data copyright 2017 by Google.

SAAS ECP training initially involves a four-week didactic component. Classroom learning is followed by a two-week clinical placement in Adelaide and 240 hours of supervised practice. Additionally, as ECPs routinely undertake rotations in the Emergency Operations Centre (EOC) to assist with case allocation and management, two weeks' further training is included for EOC operations (SA Ambulance Service, 2014b). Assessment for both the didactic and placement elements include: written exam, viva voce, simulation assessment, skills-based log book and case reviews. Examples of the SAAS ECP scope of practice include:

- pathology sampling
- suturing/stapling/gluing
- skin tear repair
- pathology sampling
- PEG replacement⁵
- IDC replacement⁶ (male and female)
- warfarin overdose reversal
- pathology interpretation
- antibiotic therapy
- breakthrough pain control
- palliation
- alternative definitive care (SA Ambulance Service, 2013).

1.6.2 New South Wales Ambulance

New South Wales (NSW) is smaller in size geographically to South Australia at 809,000 square kilometres (Figure 1.2). It is however the most populous state/territory in Australia with 7.79 million people. Almost 62% of

⁵ A percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) tube is a tube that is passed through the abdominal wall most often to assist with feeding and hydration.

⁶ An indwelling catheter (IDC) is a tube that allows urine to flow from the bladder.

NSW's population reside in the Greater Sydney region (NSW Government, 2017). NSW Ambulance⁷ (NSWA) employs over 3,700 paramedics and provided over 963,000 ambulance responses in the 2015-16 financial year (NSW Health, 2016).

Figure 1.2 Location of New South Wales in Australia (inset). Map data copyright 2017 by Google.

Like their colleagues across the border, NSW operates an ECP program. The program became operational in December 2007 and was one of the earliest instalments of a community paramedicine service model in Australasia at the time⁸. Currently, there are over 100 ECPs working from dedicated ECP modules across Sydney, the Illawarra, Central Coast and Hunter/Newcastle regions. ECPs also work as part of a double-crewed ambulance in various other locations across the state. However, ECPs operate mostly in a metropolitan or

⁷ Ambulance Service of NSW was renamed in 2015 to become NSW Ambulance.

⁸ Coincidentally, 18 Queensland Ambulance Service paramedics graduated as Isolated Practice Area Paramedics in the same month as the initial cohort of 12 NSW ECPs became operational (Reeve, Pashen, Mumme, De La Rue, & Cheffins, 2008).

semi-rural setting and attend approximately 18,000 cases per year (NSW Ambulance, 2016).

Contrasting with the other two study sites, the minimum qualification for ECP recruitment in NSW is Qualified Paramedic. ECP training commences with a 10-week program of approximately 340 contact hours at the University of Sydney Clinical School (Nepean). The program is inclusive of a two-week clinical placement phase at Nepean Hospital in Sydney's west. On-going professional development activities such as case presentations and reviews are likely over the following 12 months. Although the paramedic is credentialed as an ECP at the successful conclusion of the clinical placement phase, the paramedic cannot apply for other specialist roles until a two-year consolidation period of the role has been completed. Examples of the NSW ECP scope of practice includes:

- aged care
- aged care screening
- falls risk assessment
- wound assessment and management
- minor injury presentations e.g. musculoskeletal sporting injuries
- minor illness presentations e.g. urinary tract infections
- antibiotic therapy
- pain management (NSW Ambulance, n.d.-a).

1.6.3 Alberta Health Services Emergency Medical Service: Calgary Zone

Alberta is a province in western Canada, covering an approximate area of 662,000 square kilometres (Figure 1.3). Out of a total population of around 4.2 million, roughly 1.5 million people reside in Calgary (Canadian Government, 2005).

Figure 1.3 Location of Calgary, Alberta in North America (inset). Map data copyright 2017 by Google.

The Alberta Health Services Emergency Medical Services (AHS EMS) attended to over half a million calls for assistance in 2015-16 (Alberta Health Services, 2016), with the Calgary Zone responding to over 160,000 calls annually (Alberta Health Services, 2017b). AHS EMS operate a metropolitan-based CP model and like SAAS, only recruit paramedics who are credentialed at the highest clinical level. Calgary operations commenced in January 2013, and currently with 22 full-time and casual staff, attended to 5239 patients in 2015 (Alberta Health Services, 2015). CPs undergo a 10-day training program divided into two blocks, to allow for course consolidation between blocks. Trainees are paired with an experienced preceptor for approximately one week (variable depending on competency) before being credentialed as an independently practicing clinician.

Examples of AHS EMS CP scope of practice include (Alberta Health Services, 2017a):

- specimen collection (blood, urine, swabs)
- central venous catheter (CVC) and intravenous (IV) rehydration
- blood transfusions
- urinary catheterisation

- wound closure and care (tissue adhesives, sutures, dressings)
- coordination of community services
- facilitate transport for diagnostic imaging
- 53 stocked medications.

1.7 THESIS STRUCTURE

The thesis is organised into 10 chapters, followed by references and appendices. The first chapter begins with the introduction of the research topic. This is followed by a brief introduction to community paramedicine, given the relative obscurity of community paramedicine in “mainstream” healthcare delivery. The PhD study is then further contextualised with an overview of the three study sites. The research aims and questions are then postulated and the researcher’s approach delineated.

An exposition of existing knowledge relevant to work role transition to community paramedicine is presented in Chapters 2 and 3. Chapter 2 reviews the advent of community paramedicine through the evolution and drivers of change in paramedicine, followed by a contemporary review of service delivery models in community paramedicine. Chapter 3 presents a theoretical background to the current study via a critical appraisal of authoritative work role transition theories in the generic literature, paramedicine and nursing disciplines. Cumulatively, the review of the literature and analysis of extant work role transition theories, reveals the gap in knowledge of how paramedics transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine.

Chapter 4 outlines the methodological approach to this PhD study including justification of research design. The chapter includes a concept map explaining the research process along with information pertaining to recruitment, ethics and operational approvals and data collection strategies. Additionally, the data analysis method is explicated and evidence of quality and rigour presented.

Chapter 5 introduces the first phase of the transition experience. The Pre-transition Phase defines those events or circumstances participants

identified as necessary to be present, prior to the active engagement of the transition process. In effect, the Pre-transition Phase allowed the participants an opportunity to rationalise the reasons for pursuing a career in community paramedicine.

Chapter 6 through to Chapter 8 present the results and discussion of each of the three “active” phases of transition. Whereas Pre-transition is considered a “passive” phase, the Early Phase (Chapter 6), Middle Phase (Chapter 7) and Late Phase (Chapter 8) represent the active constituents of the transition experience. The formatting of each chapter has been scaffolded around four core categories that permeate the transition experience. Consequently, each chapter is presented in the following format:

- Introduction
- Unique Aspects of [Early/Middle/Late] Phase
- Analysis of the Results
 - Engaging in a Community of Practice
 - Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change
 - Developing Critical Thinking
 - Mastering Skills
- Summary of Results
- Discussion of the [Early/Middle/Late] Phase
 - Engaging in a Community of Practice
 - Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change
 - Developing Critical Thinking
 - Mastering Skills
- Conclusion.

Chapter 10 begins with a summative interpretation of paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine, complemented by the presentation of the theoretical model. The significance of the study is outlined, drawing emphasis on the degree of transferability of work role

transition theories from cognate disciplines to the community paramedicine setting. Next, implications and recommendations are offered and the limitations addressed. Finally, recommendations for future works and concluding comments are presented.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Despite an increase in paramedicine research over the last decade, research in the speciality area of community paramedicine has been lacking (Bigham, et al., 2013). This view is echoed by a Delphi consultation⁹ in the United Kingdom of key stakeholders in emergency care which has prioritised research into the development of alternate management strategies to reduce patient transports to the Emergency Department (ED), as one of the three highest priority areas in paramedic practice (Snooks et al., 2009). Moreover, the consultation underscored that ambulance response times are no longer synonymous with quality, but that the delivery of appropriate patient-focused services is a more accurate measure of improved performance. Given the dearth of knowledge relevant to community paramedicine, the aim of this literature review is to provide a critical analysis of the published literature and establish the framework in which to position the relevance and significance of this PhD study.

The literature review examines the background, trends and controversies in community paramedicine through two foci: evolution and drivers of change in paramedicine and service delivery models in community paramedicine. Through a synthesis of the peer-reviewed and grey literature, a unifying definition of community paramedicine has been identified. The definition of community paramedicine is based on the conceptual underpinnings of the two dominant service delivery models in community paramedicine and is, arguably, a unique contribution to the field.

The literature review is further expanded in Chapter 3 through a critical appraisal of prominent work role transition theories in the generic

⁹ A Delphi consultation attempts to achieve consensus on an important issue, often via brain storming or survey (Hasson, Keeney, & McKenna, 2000; Keeney, Hasson, & McKenna, 2011).

organisational literature, paramedicine and nursing disciplines. Cumulatively, the review of the literature and analysis of extant work role transition theories reveals a gap in knowledge about how paramedics transition to a specialist work role in community paramedicine. However, the literature review may possibly remain a controversial topic within grounded theory methodology (Birks & Mills, 2011; Charmaz, 2014; Mohamed, Kennedy, & Oliver, 2017). Therefore prior to continuing, the premise and application of the literature review in this PhD study is reviewed briefly.

2.2 THE PREMISE AND APPLICATION OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW

Grounded Theory purists may argue current theories and existing literature should not be reviewed until after data analysis has occurred in order not to force their data into pre-existing categories (Ramalho, Adams, Huggard, & Hoare, 2015). Indeed, seminal authors Glaser and Strauss argued the literature review should only be written after the analysis was completed so as not to contaminate the research findings (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Contrary to Glaser and Strauss' view, Charmaz (2014), another seminal author, recognises that utilising the literature in a more traditional logico-deductive model could potentially lock the research into previously established concepts.

Despite the arguments above, this PhD study posits the literature review as an integral part of the research process for several reasons. First, it should be noted that the literature review was a requirement of the research proposal submitted to human research ethics committees and paramedic services for approvals prior to commencing data collection. Importantly, the literature review also provided context and added to the researcher's knowledge and understanding of the relevant issues in community paramedicine. Contextualisation was of particular importance for the current study given the confusing nomenclature and models of care within community paramedicine (Long, 2016). Moreover, the literature review identified the gaps in knowledge regarding paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine. By understanding the gaps in the literature, this PhD study can lay claim to

adding a unique body of knowledge to the science of paramedic work role transition.

The literature review provided sensitising concepts, that is, initial but tentative ideas that were used as a point of departure to guide the initial interview and analysis (Morse, 1993). It should be emphasised that sensitising concepts did not continue to guide the analysis. Herein lies the significance of the key characteristics of grounded theory methodology; the iterative approach to theory development in grounded theory studies employs techniques such as constant comparison, reflectivity and memoing (see Chapter 4), to ensure a degree of detachment from the existing literature. Other commentators have described the approach as giving the data “due consideration, due respect, before imposing other theories” (Urquhart, 2012, p. 17).

The constant comparative method is a salient example of the value of the literature review (Charmaz, 2014). The literature review provides an important source of comparison and analysis to define how this PhD study’s depiction of paramedic transition to community paramedicine challenges and supersedes the explanatory power of existing work role transition theories, particularly from cognate disciplines. In utilising the literature, the constant comparative method (see Chapter 4) also facilitates the application of abductive reasoning¹⁰. The extant literature works as a lens for “seeing” all conceivable theoretical explanations prior to empirical testing (Charmaz, 2014, p. 203).

In summary, this PhD study argues the literature review is integral to any research adopting a grounded theory approach. The literature review was utilised in the current study to not only classify and evaluate the current evidence on paramedic work role transition to community paramedicine, but

¹⁰ Abductive reasoning makes an inferential leap to consider all theoretical possibilities to explain the observed data and moves a grounded theory study away from qualitative descriptive accounts to that of an abstract conceptual framework (Charmaz, 2014).

was woven throughout the research process to advance the theoretical arguments during the analysis.

2.3 SEARCH STRATEGY

The design of the search strategy reflects a two-phased approach. The first phase aimed to provide a holistic contextualisation of community paramedicine within the auspice of paramedic service delivery. The second phase involved determining the extent of the literature specifically relating to the transition of qualified paramedics to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Through the examination of the cognate literature from the nursing and allied health fields, along with the more generic literature describing work role transitions from disciplines such as industrial/organisational psychology and business, a comprehensive evaluation of the literature has emerged.

A range of databases and sources (Table 2.1) were accessed to provide a rigorous appraisal of the literature that included both peer reviewed and non-peer reviewed databases. Where applicable, citations suggested by the search engines were also explored. Additionally, both forward snowballing (a process of identifying articles that cite the articles found in the original search) and backward snowballing (retrieving articles from the reference list) (Jalali & Wohlin, 2012), were proven to be productive strategies throughout each phase of the literature review. Other researchers have also affirmed the efficacy of snowballing and advocate snowballing as a primary method of finding relevant articles in writing systematic literature studies (Webster & Watson, 2002).

In order to examine comprehensively the paramedicine literature, a prehospital filter developed by Smith, Archer, and Burgess (2012) was applied to both CINAHL and PubMed databases. Although the intended application was for the Cochrane Library in 2010, the MeSH and text terms used in the filter provided a suitable template for high sensitivity (albeit low specificity) returns from the paramedic literature. Further search terms were added post filter to achieve the final search results and included: "low-acuity", "novice to expert", "expert to novice", "organisational socialisation", "qualitative" (filtered as

publication type), "work role", "specialist", and "transition". The terms were entered as text word (.tw) searches to seek out the word in the title or abstract of the paper.

Table 2.1

Information Sources accessed for the Literature Review

Peer Reviewed	Non-Peer Reviewed
CINAHL	Google Scholar
Medline/PubMed	Government reports
Scopus	QUT Library catalogue
Embase	Government / Agency websites
PsycINFO	
ABI/Inform	
Trove: Australian Thesis	
Journal of Paramedic Practice	
Australasian Journal of Paramedicine	

Furthermore, truncations, wildcards and the syntax "adj5" or "adj25" were used in addition to the search terms where appropriate. For example, the text word search for "specialist" was entered as "speciali*.tw" to capture various truncations of the root-word (i.e. specialist, specialisation) and differences in spelling between the US, UK and Australian English. The design of the pre-hospital filter developed by Smith, et al. (2012) was not appropriate for application in the remaining databases. Consequently, text terms were added to those used above and included: "ambulance", "emergency medical services", "paramedic", "ECP", "Extended Care Paramedic", "CP", "Community Paramedic", and "community paramedicine".

The objective of the second phase search strategy enabled the examination of work role transitions within the scope of the nursing and allied health fields. Of particular interest was the exposure of existing theories that may illuminate the process of role transition in other disciplines. The search strategy was simplified using two to four search terms due to the volume of relevant returns generated. Titles and abstracts were examined and articles

that had a focus on work role transitions and which also appeared comparable to the research topic were retained. Additional data sources including websites from predominately health organisations such as state health ministries and paramedic representative bodies were also accessed.

2.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The previous chapter presented a general overview of the key constituents of community paramedicine along with an introduction to the confusing nomenclature of role definitions. The following sections provide a more detailed background to the field of community paramedicine, and further articulate the context in which paramedic transition to community paramedicine occurs. The background to community paramedicine is discussed in terms of the evolution and drivers of change in paramedicine and the service delivery models that have subsequently emerged.

2.4.1 The evolution and drivers of change in paramedicine

Paramedicine is still a relatively young discipline, having coalesced from the rudimentary “stretcher bearers” of the 19th century (Williams, Brown, & Onsmann, 2012). The evolution of the Anglo-American paramedic service model has grown primarily to deliver timely treatment of the acutely sick and injured with subsequent transport to hospital (Al-Shaqsi, 2010). In contrast to the Franco-German model of “stay and stabilise” (often utilising doctors supported by paramedics), the Anglo-American model is based on the philosophy of comparatively shorter scene times and transport to an appropriate medical facility (Dick, 2003). However, towards the end of the last century, it had become apparent the impetus for change had migrated away from the traditional transport paradigm towards the provision of more holistic quality care (Veronesi, 1999).

Consequently, paramedicine itself is in a state of transition (Cooper & Grant, 2009; Kennedy, 2011; O'Meara & Grbich, 2009; Wright, 2008), most notably in the areas of organisational, logistical and clinical practices (Chilton, 2012). The reasons for the transitional change in paramedicine are multi-factorial. An often-cited contributing factor is the significant increase in

demand for paramedic services over recent times (Joyce, et al., 2009; O'Meara, Tourle, Stirling, Walker, & Pedler, 2012). By way of example, the total number of ambulance transports across all Australian paramedic services increased by 28% over a 10-year period ending 2012-13 (Productivity Commission, 2014). Jurisdictional examples include South Australia Ambulance Service (SAAS) experiencing a 4.7% increase in ambulance call-outs in 2013-14 on the previous year (SA Ambulance Service, 2014a) and New South Wales Ambulance (NSWA) reporting a 3.3% increase across the same period (Ambulance Service of NSW, 2015). Compounding the issue, most forecasts project a substantial increase in healthcare services as the population ages (Raven, Tippett, Ferguson, & Smith, 2006) and an over reliance on hospital services for older adults (Abrashkin et al., 2016). The significant challenge for paramedic services therefore, is the more judicious use of finite resources in the delivery of quality care to the community.

Not only are demands on ambulance call-outs increasing, there is also a demand for a more wide ranging utilisation of paramedics in the delivery of primary care services (Eaton, 2017; Kennedy, 2011). The need to reform service delivery models is exemplified by current initiatives from NSW. The patient profiles of people who contact NSW reflects an aging population requiring less trauma intervention and more attention to falls and age-related chronic illnesses (NSW Ambulance, 2015). Consequently, a new concept of operations has been developed to deliver more targeted care to specific patient groups. Whilst time-critical emergency care is still a core foundation of operations, other initiatives have taken form including:

- referrals to GPs for low-acuity patients with a minor injury or illness
- appointment of mental health assessment teams
- employment of dedicated Extended Care Paramedic dispatchers
- frequent caller's management program.

Hospital emergency departments (EDs), along with paramedic services, have also seen a marked increase in patient presentations (O'Meara, Tourle,

Stirling, et al., 2012). The result is over-crowding in the emergency department and possibly the delaying of time-critical care, such as thrombolysis for acute myocardial infarction (Collis, 2010; Tohira, Williams, Jacobs, Bremner, & Finn, 2013). Across Australian public hospitals between 2009-10 and 2013-14 for instance, emergency department presentations increased by 4.8% on average each year, equating to 7.2 million emergency department presentations in 2013-14 (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2014). Similarly in the United Kingdom, the demands for emergency and unscheduled care are correspondingly pervasive and in turn, have advanced the emergence of ECPs as an alternative to hospital conveyance (Mason, et al., 2009).

A key goal in directing patients in the community towards an ECP/CP model is to decrease the number of subsequent emergency department presentations (Nolan, et al., 2012; Thompson, et al., 2014). These assumptions have merit. Bigham, et al. (2013) in a systematic review, cites articles from the UK, Canada and the US that suggest 30% to 50% of all transports to the ED are inappropriate. In point of fact, NSW Ambulance recently reported 40% of patients who call for an ambulance present with a low-acuity (non-urgent) condition (NSW Ambulance, 2015). The findings suggest a considerable proportion of patients in NSW who call for an ambulance could potentially benefit from an ECP/CP contact and avoid an ED presentation.

Additional drivers of change within paramedicine include a decrease in home visits by general practitioners (GP) (O'Meara, Tourle, Stirling, et al., 2012). Home visits by GPs in Australia decreased 51% in the decade leading up to 2007, down from 15.8 per 100 persons, to 7.7 per 100 persons (Joyce & Piterman, 2008). Furthermore, McRae and Pham (2016) cite an Australian Medical Association survey that reported the reason for a decrease in GP home visits in relation to aged-care patients included perceived poor remuneration for the service, the expansion of corporate general practice which usually does not provide home visits, and the time demands of patients in clinics. Additionally, the experience in the United States suggests that people who are

homebound and unable to access outpatient care, forgo necessary treatment for extended periods of time, resulting in an exacerbation of a chronic illness requiring treatment in an emergency department (Abrashkin, et al., 2016; Kelley et al., 2011). It is this fundamental shift away from care in the community setting by traditional primary care providers such as GPs which has placed greater pressure on paramedic services to provide enhanced primary health care services to fill the gaps.

A section of the literature focuses specifically on regional communities where the provision of healthcare services falls behind those in metropolitan areas (Raven, et al., 2006). Indeed, the seeds of community paramedicine have often been sown in regional areas. The genesis of community paramedicine programs in the United States (Choi, et al., 2016) and Canada (O'Meara, Ruest, & Martin, 2015), have generally been attributed to addressing regional healthcare needs. Similarly in Australia, the applicability of paramedics with an extended scope of practice to service regional communities was recognised over 10 years ago (Raven, et al., 2006). The challenges facing regional communities are more pronounced than their metropolitan counterparts due to:

- the rising costs of healthcare
- prevalence of chronic diseases
- lack of access to appropriate healthcare services
- health workforce shortages (Eaton, 2017; O'Meara, Tourle, Stirling, et al., 2012; Wingrove, 2012).

The growing awareness and acceptance of community paramedicine is helped by the on-going professionalisation¹¹ of the paramedic workforce (O'Meara, et al., 2016). One such driver of the professionalisation of paramedicine is the shift in paramedic education, led by Australia and the United Kingdom, from an in-house vocational apprenticeship model to a pre-

¹¹ Professionalisation is the process of an occupation attempting to obtain the status and recognition of a profession (Freidson, 1988; Williams, et al., 2012).

employment university-based training model for paramedics (Devenish, et al., 2016). Ambulance Victoria, for example, has progressed from a less than 10% intake of university graduates in 2001-02, to exclusively university graduates by 2006-07 (Ambulance Victoria, 2015). The reason for the transition to university degree qualifications lies partly in the changing nature of paramedic work that has evolved beyond the simple application of first aid and transport to a more integrated role within the primary healthcare system, necessitating greater responsibility in clinical decision making and treatment (Joyce, et al., 2009). Moreover, the transition of paramedic education to universities and the higher educator sector further legitimises, matures and “mainstreams” paramedicine as a profession (O'Brien, et al., 2014, p. 1). As a consequence, university based training for paramedics in Australia is being consolidated in an escalating framework of paramedic specialisation (Colbeck, 2014).

Further evidence of paramedicine becoming more professionalised is revealed by paramedics specialising¹² in roles beyond the traditional emergency response model including community paramedicine (O'Meara, et al., 2016). Within other health professions, specialisation is not a new concept. The advancement of medical science and technology has seen a marked increase in the specialisation of doctors throughout the 19th century (Caffrey et al., 2014). Within the field of paramedicine, mobile intensive care units (MICUs) began appearing in the 1950s and 1960s in Northern Ireland, Germany and several other countries in Eastern Europe (Caroline, 1995). Staffed by specialist doctors, the concept was relatively simple - bring the doctor to the patient (Dick, 2003).

However, it was not until 1970 that paramedic-staffed MICUs (under radio command by a doctor) made their debut in the United States (Caroline, 1995). A year later in 1971, Ambulance Victoria oversaw the introduction of the first MICUs in Australia, known locally as Mobile Intensive Care Ambulance (MICA) (Ambulance Victoria, 2015). Like other paramedic clinicians who

¹² Specialisation is the extent to which a job involves performing a specialised task or possessing specialised knowledge or skill (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006).

specialise in high-acuity (urgent) cases such as Intensive Care/Critical Care Paramedics (Paramedics Australasia, 2009), MICA paramedics possess a scope of practice that employs advanced clinical skills and procedures within a framework of autonomous clinical decision making. Although variations exist between paramedic jurisdictions, the scope of practice may include advanced practices such as endotracheal intubation, needle thoracostomy and the administration of antiarrhythmics (Bigham, et al., 2013). Examples of less well known areas of specialisation in paramedic practice include tactical environments (Caffrey, et al., 2014) and industrial settings (Acker, Johnston, & Lazarsfeld-Jensen, 2014; Seel & Turner, 2016).

In summary, the numerous drivers for change across health systems in North America, the United Kingdom and Australasia also transect at the primary care setting in the community. Foremost among these drivers are an ageing population, an increase in both ambulance call-outs and emergency department presentations, and a decrease in access to community-based primary health care including GP services. As a result, a gap has emerged in the delivery of quality community-based healthcare services for underserved communities, particularly in regional areas.

It should be noted that various other initiatives exist to meet the needs of the community. These initiatives range from redressing access and equity issues across health systems (Bennett, 2009), to initiating more specific services such as nurse-led telephone advice lines (Woollard, 2012). However, the foundation has been laid for paramedic services to transition to service delivery models that are more innovative, equitable, complementary to existing primary health services and able to meet the current and future needs of the community. Although there appears to be a general consensus in the literature for the factors giving rise to community paramedicine programs, there is significantly less agreement on the definition, scope and utility of the community paramedicine model.

2.4.2 The conundrum of Community Paramedicine models

Paramedicine has been likened, appropriately, to being in a stage of adolescence in which the discipline is still working out what it needs to be (Simpson et al., 2017). Community paramedicine contributes to the uncertainty by laying claim to a niche area in paramedicine outside the bounds of the more familiar “traditional” paramedic service delivery model. Moreover, a lack of consensus on the definition of community paramedicine persists in the literature. The conflict in identity has been postulated recently in the following question, “*Does community paramedicine fit within the arena of emergency medical services, emergency services, public health, public safety, home health, or primary care?*” (Gresens, 2017, p. 208).

Conceptually, community paramedicine is poorly defined. The reason, in part, is that community paramedicine is most often defined in terms of one of two similar – although essentially different - service delivery models. Some authors have been careful to differentiate conceptually between models (O'Meara, 2014; O'Meara, et al., 2016), while others are less concerned with the subtler differences between models (Bigham, et al., 2013; Gresens, 2017). Through a synthesis of the extant literature, community paramedicine can be conceptually mapped in terms of two dominant service delivery models.

Community paramedicine occupies a specialist clinical practice arm of paramedicine. In turn, community paramedicine is comprised of two service delivery models: *Community Paramedic type-models* and *Extended Care Paramedics type-models*. Both these models can be found in a number of paramedic jurisdictions around the world including Canada, the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand (O'Meara, 2014; Wang, 2011). Both Extended Care Paramedic and Community Paramedic models are better expressed with the suffix “type models” as there are many variations of vocational titles of paramedics who ostensibly work in one model or the other. The following provides examples of these variations in nomenclature and is by no means exhaustive. The alignment to either ECP or CP paradigms is provided

in parenthesis, however, in an operational context, the delineation between paradigms is often ambiguous:

- Community Health Specialist (CP)
- Emergency Care Paramedic (ECP)
- Extended Skills Paramedic (ECP)
- Mobile Primary Health Care (CP)
- New Paramedic Practitioners (ECP)
- Paramedic Practitioner (ECP)
- Practitioner in Community Care (CP)
- Urgent Care Practitioner (ECP)

The distinction between ECP-type models and CP-type models is best conceptualised by appreciating where on the patient's healthcare continuum an ECP and CP are most likely to intersect (Figure 2.1). Note: ECPs feature predominately during an unscheduled request for care, whereas CPs operate more in a preventative health-role capacity.

Extended Care Paramedics most often operate in a "reactive" model of service delivery. In other words, ECPs will respond to calls for unscheduled care, most likely activated through traditional notification systems (such as calls to "000" in Australia) and are usually dispatched by ambulance control centres. The patient is treated in their own residence for (most often) a low-acuity (non-urgent) presentation and if necessary, referred for follow-up care, most likely to the patient's GP. After reviewing the international literature, Cooper and Grant (2009, p. 93), proposed the following definition of ECPs:

ECPs tend to be experienced nurses or paramedics working in autonomous but collaborative roles in the out of hospital setting; seeing, treating, releasing (or referring) patients with predominantly minor conditions.

Figure 2.1 The intersection of Extended Care Paramedics and Community Paramedics on the patient healthcare continuum by Long, 2015, From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role. Poster presented at Paramedics Australasia International Conference, Adelaide, South Australia.

In contrast, Community Paramedics are employed to reduce the incidence of “000”¹³ calls altogether by working collaboratively with other primary care services in areas such as chronic disease management, health promotion and education, and early intervention (Abrashkin, et al., 2016; Nolan, et al., 2012). The definition of Community Paramedic (CP) as proposed by the International Roundtable on Community Paramedicine appears to be gaining traction around the world (Bigam, et al., 2013; O’Meara, 2014):

Community paramedicine is a model of care whereby paramedics apply their training and skills in ‘non-traditional’ community-based environments, often outside the usual emergency response and transportation model. The community paramedic practices within an ‘expanded scope’, which includes the application of specialised skills and protocols beyond the base paramedic training. The community

¹³ “000” is the Australian emergency call number, similar to “911” in North America.

paramedic engages in an 'expanded role' working in non-traditional roles using existing skills (Nolan, 2011).

Often, community paramedicine programs are borne out of the selective needs of the local community. Consequently, the model of service delivery that local paramedic services select will be stamped with their own individualities but will still be recognisable around a common premise. For example, the adjoining jurisdictions of South Australia and New South Wales both deploy ECPs who respond to calls for unscheduled care. However in South Australia, ECPs are exclusively recruited from the Intensive Care Paramedic ranks and operate in a metropolitan setting. In NSW, Qualified Paramedics (who have not articulated to Intensive Care practice) are eligible to apply and operate in both a metropolitan and regional setting.

Regardless of the semantics, there are sufficient commonalities between the conceptual underpinnings of ECP and CP models to bring both models together under the umbrella term "community paramedicine". Broadly, the aims of community paramedicine can be defined through an amalgam of the conceptual underpinnings of ECP and CP programs (Bigham, et al., 2013; Kizer, et al., 2013; O'Meara, et al., 2016). The aims are to:

- More efficiently navigate a patient through the healthcare system and provide options other than presentation to an emergency department.
- Increase access to primary care services for medically underserved populations, particularly in rural/regional areas.
- Enhance opportunities for the development of paramedic clinical practice.

The aims of community paramedicine programs are supported by the ECP/CP scope of practice. The following section discusses the confusion in nomenclature between "expanded" and "extended" scope of practice and provides examples of ECP/CP scope of practice from community paramedicine programs worldwide.

2.4.3 Scope of practice

The interchangeability of the terms “expanded” and “extended” scope of practice in the literature is another example of the confusing nomenclature in clinical practice. For example, *Extended Care Paramedics* in New Zealand are said to practice (somewhat counter intuitively) within an “*expanded* set of skills and protocols” (researcher’s emphasis) (Hoyle, Swain, Fake, & Larsen, 2012, p. 653). To provide some clarity, Queensland Health investigated the impact that an expanded health practitioner scope of practice may have on the health system and provides some assistance in defining terms:

Expanded scope of practice was defined as the introduction of any role or task that would result in an expansion to the current scope of a profession’s practice within a particular context in Queensland Health. Expanded scope can include a number of elements, including undertaking full scope tasks where historical policies or context has precluded them, advanced practice and, extended scope (Queensland Health, 2014, p. 16).

Extended scope was subsequently defined as:

A discrete knowledge and skill base additional to the recognised scope of practice of a profession and/or regulatory context of a particular jurisdiction. The tasks involved are usually undertaken by other professions, such as doctors, nurses or other allied health professionals. However, over time, what once constituted extended scope of practice may become part of a profession’s full scope of practice (Queensland Health, 2014, p. 17).

Both of the above definitions are centred around the concept of “scope of practice” which the report defines as, “the full spectrum of roles, functions, responsibilities, activities and decision-making capacity that individuals within that profession are educated, competent and authorised to perform” (Queensland Health, 2014, p. 47). Although paramedicine is not specifically mentioned in the Queensland government report, examples of “extended scope roles and tasks” mirror those of ECPs/CPs. Examples relating to physiotherapists include prescribing rights in the emergency department,

performing clinical procedures such as simple suturing, and deciding on provisional diagnoses (Queensland Health, 2014, p. 26).

Issues in community paramedicine which remain unclear, concern both the point in time, and from whose perspective the current scope of professional practice is measured. For example, some elements of ECP practice in NSW are now “mainstream” for use by all Qualified Paramedics, such as selected low-acuity referral pathways (NSW Ambulance, n.d.-b). It is unclear at what point in time the scope of practice of an ECP will no longer be considered “extended” and become simply part of the recognised scope of practice for Qualified Paramedics. Interestingly, the Australian Nursing and Midwifery Federation have rebuked the term “expanded” in favour of “advanced” practice in places where models of care have been introduced to recognise and support nurses at an expert level within the scope of traditional nursing practice (Bryce & Foley, 2014).

Suffice it to say that the intricacies of this debate are beyond the purview of this study. In general, the definition of extended scope of practice as provided by Queensland Health is the best fit for use in community paramedicine. Consequently, the nomenclature of an *extended scope* will be used throughout this PhD study, even though in the wider literature the terms “expanded” and “extended” continue to be used interchangeably.

The scope of practice employed across community paramedicine programs is tailored to the local community’s healthcare needs (White & Wingrove, 2012). Accordingly, due to the scope of practice varying between community paramedicine programs, defining community paramedicine in terms of scope of practice lacks precision. However, given the comparable philosophy underpinning ECP-type and CP-type programs, similarities in scope of practice are still discernible. Examples of common skill sets and competencies for ECPs/CPs include:

- local anaesthetic techniques
- suturing techniques

- wound care
- principles of dressings and splinting
- joint examinations
- neurologic, cardiovascular, respiratory system examination
- medication dispensing including analgesia, antibiotics, tetanus toxoid
- intravenous therapy and rehydration
- mobility and social needs assessments
- requests for radiography
- referral processes, including emergency department, general practitioner, district nurse and community social services (Bigham, et al., 2013; Mason, et al., 2007; Nolan, et al., 2012).

2.4.4 Selection and training in community paramedicine

Most candidates selected for advanced training to specialise in community paramedicine must first attain the minimum certification as a Qualified Paramedic in their jurisdiction. However due to the diversity in global ECP/CP programs, not all ECP/CP candidates enter their respective programs as paramedics. In the UK for example, nurses in some services are also eligible to join ECP programs (Woollard, 2012). And yet, in an operational context, ECPs still attend the whole spectrum of emergency (“999”) calls. Consequently, the nurses are also subsequently cross-trained as paramedics. It should be noted however, that it is beyond the scope of this thesis to examine the transition of nurses to a specialist ECP/CP role within a paramedic service. The entry point for this study is Qualified Paramedic regardless of prior nursing qualifications.

Because of their knowledge and experience, other paramedic services will only allow senior clinicians to be eligible to apply for ECP/CP positions. For example, Wellington Free Ambulance initiated a new model of care in May 2009 whereby initially, only the “highest grade” of paramedics were eligible to apply (Swain, Hoyle, & Long, 2010, p. 12). Similarly, the South Australia

Ambulance Service only accepts currently certified Intensive Care Paramedics into their ECP program (Thompson, et al., 2014).

The educational requirements for paramedics to qualify as an ECP/CP also vary from place to place. For example, the East of England Ambulance Service Trust formerly East Anglican Ambulance Service, requires 18 weeks in-house academic learning and supervised practice for paramedics to earn the title of "Extended Care Practitioner." In Wales, the title "Advanced Paramedic Practitioners" requires paramedics to engage in a year's full-time university study as a prerequisite for graduating with a Master of Science in Advanced Clinical Practice (Woollard, 2012).

Education and training are key enabling factors of community paramedicine programs. For instance, the education of ECPs/CPs has been linked to a greater degree of workforce flexibility and use of collaborative practices (Cooper, O'Carroll, Jenkin, & Badger, 2007; Raven, et al., 2006). In addition, education has been argued as being of "crucial importance" in the effective and sustainable implementation of a community paramedicine program (O'Meara, Ruest, & Stirling, 2014, p. 6). Furthermore, in a recent publication, O'Meara, et al. (2016) reaffirms the significance of higher education in community paramedicine by adding higher education to an earlier conceptual framework that described the key characteristics of a community paramedic programs (O'Meara, Tourle, Stirling, et al., 2012).

2.4.5 Community paramedicine program evaluations

A growing body of evidence exists in the literature that reports favourably on the efficacy of community paramedicine programs across a number of criteria including, cost effectiveness (Coffman, et al., 2017; Dixon et al., 2009), user service satisfaction (Martin, O'Meara, & Farmer, 2015; Thompson, et al., 2014) and non-transport rates (Abrashkin, et al., 2016; Tohira, et al., 2013). In one of the largest studies reviewed, a quasi-experimental multi-centre randomised controlled trial was conducted in five matched pairs of sites across England over a period of 15 months from 2006 – 2007 (Mason, et al., 2009). Approximately 6000 patients were enrolled in the trial and were allocated to

either an intervention arm (ECP) or traditional care (non-ECP) arm. Among the findings, the authors noted that paramedics with extended skills could provide a clinically effective alternative to standard ambulance transfer to an emergency department. Moreover, patients in the intervention group were more likely to report being highly satisfied with the service they received. However, it is noted that the study was non-peer reviewed and thus the findings should to be interpreted with caution.

Not all forays into community paramedicine have been successful¹⁴. One of the earliest community paramedicine programs in the United States was located in New Mexico and ceased operations after only eight years (Choi, et al., 2016). The program had all the hallmarks of a successful undertaking; it was developed by a consortium of state officials, local EMS and a university group with experience in rural paramedic training. The \$394,000 in federal funding was considered generous (Hauswald, Raynovich, & Brainard, 2005), and legislation was passed in support of the program (Choi, et al., 2016). Yet after five years, only one of the 16 paramedics who had completed the 980 hours of training remained in practice. The reasons for the failure of the program were attributed to local politics, lack of external quality control and crucially, the lack of integration with the local medical community (Hauswald, et al., 2005). Certainly, the integration of community paramedicine programs with the local medical community has often been recognised as a foundational tenant of a successful community paramedicine program (Eaton, 2017; Martin-Misener, Downe-Wamboldt, Cain, & Girouard, 2009; Martin, et al., 2015; Mason, et al., 2009).

Similar circumstances were noted in a failed community-based intervention for people at high-risk of falling (Comans et al., 2011). As with the New Mexico program (Hauswald, et al., 2005), significant planning and

¹⁴ The reporting of unsuccessful community paramedicine programs are all the more important given that early published articles in paramedicine were noted to consist mainly of advocacy (O'Meara, 2014), suggesting the possibility of selective reporting bias in the community paramedicine literature.

endorsement from the “top down” and “bottom up” underscored the program initiative. The program allowed paramedics in a trial area of metropolitan Brisbane, Australia, to engage a direct referral pathway to a falls prevention service. However, the program evaluation clearly showed paramedics did not use the new referral pathway regularly. The outcomes of the trial highlighted the challenging dynamics of clinical practice change management including the inability to educate participating paramedics in a comprehensive manner, the fluid nature of paramedic deployments and lack of dedicated resources (Comans, et al., 2011). Interestingly, a recent article extends upon these findings in suggesting that paramedic decision-making is heavily influenced by role perception when caring for older-people who have fallen (Simpson, et al., 2017) in that the paramedic’s perception of how “legitimate” a case involving an older person who has fallen influences the quality of subsequent clinical risk decisions.

2.5 CONCLUSION

The emergence of community paramedicine programs can be attributed to several drivers of change common across North America, the United Kingdom and Australasia. An ageing population, an increase in both ambulance call-outs and emergency department presentations and, a decrease in access to community-based primary health care including GP services, have cumulatively driven paramedic services to new and innovative service delivery models. However, there is no unifying work role descriptor for paramedics employed in either a “reactive” ECP-type program or “preventative” CP-type program. This is not unexpected, given the individualistic variances between ECP/CP programs such as location, resources and purpose.

Through a synthesis of the peer-reviewed and grey literature, a clearer understanding of the conceptual boundaries of community paramedicine has emerged. Prominent authors in the field have previously delineated between ECP-type models and CP-type models (O'Meara, 2014; O'Meara, et al., 2016), although they have stopped short of a unifying definition of community paramedicine. This PhD study is the first known attempt to define community

paramedicine in terms of two similar, although conceptually different, service delivery models. In this regard, the literature review makes a unique contribution to the community paramedicine field by offering a single definition of community paramedicine based upon the commonality between ECP-type models and CP-type models, that is, to more efficiently navigate the patient through the healthcare system and provide options other than presentation to an ED. It is further argued that consistency, appropriateness and clarity of nomenclature across community paramedicine is one of practical and professional necessity (Long, 2016).

There is a significant gap in the existing literature examining the process of transition of Qualified Paramedics to a specialist work role in community paramedicine. The studies often reported a slant towards the operationalisation or evaluation of community paramedicine programs with limited use of theoretical frameworks. The next chapter examines the theoretical background of work role transition from the perspective of extant work role transition theories in the generic organisational literature, nursing discipline and paramedicine discipline.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Background

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 3 discusses the theoretical background for this thesis, and examines pertinent theories of work-role transition. The meaning and use of the term “transition” varies according to context and discipline (Kralik, Visentin, & Van Loon, 2006). For the purposes of this PhD study, work role transition is defined as “any change in employment status and any change in job content” (Nicholson, 1984, p. 173). Additionally, an individual may inevitably experience a sequence of work role transitions within a given career (Ashforth & Saks, 1995). While it is beyond the scope of this thesis to provide a comprehensive appraisal of transition theory across a range of disciplines, this chapter critically examines the empirical literature and theoretical constructs of work role transition that are of greater relevance to the field of community paramedicine. Consequently, work role transition theories from the paramedicine discipline, nursing discipline and generic organisational literature are included.

3.2 TRANSITION THEORIES IN PARAMEDICINE

The review of the paramedicine literature has established an absence of previous studies where the central theme has been to qualitatively examine the transition of paramedics to any specialist role, including community paramedicine. However, these results were not unexpected. A decade ago, the Cochrane Library had a relatively small number of studies but these did not cover adequately the broad scope of out-of-hospital care (Smith et al., 2007). In a more recent scoping review of the literature relating to Community Paramedics from 2005 – 2012, O'Meara (2014) found only 23 peer-reviewed papers to include in the review. O'Meara's review still represents a modest increase in research and evaluation of Community Paramedic programs, although the majority (14) were empirical studies that reported on outcome measures such as referral rates, client satisfaction and cost-benefit. It should be noted that none of the articles examined work role transition specifically.

The dearth of refereed evidence pertaining to specialist work role transition in paramedicine extends to the specialist service delivery arm situated parallel to community paramedicine, *i.e.*, high-acuity paramedic practice (performed by Intensive Care Paramedics (ICPs)). The extent of empirical knowledge of work role transition in this area can be attributed to a single study that examined the factors that influence the decision to either enter or exit ICP practice (McFarlane, 2010). Despite the similar heritage of specialist work roles in paramedicine, the utility of McFarlane's study to community paramedicine is limited. While elements of McFarlane's study, such as the motivation to enter specialist practice, may illuminate aspects of work role transition in community paramedicine, the study did not examine comprehensively the work role transition from Qualified Paramedic to ICP. Moreover, the work role of ICP and ECP/CP operate under principally different service delivery models, particularly in respect to patient populations.

While the relative scarcity of literature pertaining to specialist work role transition in paramedicine is quite evident, the subject area of work role transition of new-to-practice paramedics appears to be of growing interest. Kennedy, et al. (2015) for example, conducted a scoping review of student paramedic experiences entering the workforce and thematically grouped 11 relevant studies. The authors identified four core categories defined by the emotional, physical and social impact of transitioning into a new workplace and culture. Rigorous conclusions could not be drawn due to the relatively small number of articles returned. The scoping review was thus limited in its findings. However, the article did provide useful insights regarding trainee paramedics by drawing associations with existing work role transition theories, including Kramer's (1974) 'Reality Shock' model. Arguably, the most comprehensive study to date that examines transition in paramedicine is original research by Devenish, et al. (2016), who qualitatively examined the professional socialisation of university qualified paramedics (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 Theoretical Model depicting Paramedic Professional Socialisation by S. Devenish, M. Clark, M. Fleming, 2016, *Journal of Creative Education*, 7 (06), p. 78615.

Devenish, et al. (2016) found that the first three phases of the socialisation of university educated paramedics conformed largely to existing theories of professional socialisation. However, as the study's participants from Australia and the United Kingdom were required to undergo a further years' consolidation to achieve full qualification, a unique fourth phase, termed the "post-internship phase", was found. The post-internship year explored, among others, the transition to being a clinical lead, the mentoring of junior staff and disillusionment with the reality of practice.

¹⁵ Reproduced with permission of Dr S Devenish.

The transferability or applicability of Devenish and colleagues' research to specialist work role transition in paramedicine is unclear due to the fundamental characteristics of the professional socialisation process. Professional socialisation is concerned with how people learn the skills, behaviours and attitudes necessary to join their chosen profession (Devenish, et al., 2016; Howkins & Ewens, 1999). In this regard, work role transition is argued to be conceptually similar to professional socialisation. However, professional socialisation can be distinguished from work role transition on two grounds. First, professional socialisation has an emphasis on the transition of a worker into a *new* professional group and therefore aptly describes the transition of university qualified paramedics into the workplace. Second, work role transition, defined by Nicholson (1984), has a focus on movement from one established work role to another *within* the chosen profession. The distinction is significant enough to limit the transferability of professional socialisation models to studies of work role transition. That said, theories of professional socialisation and work role transition in paramedicine can still be regarded as complementary.

An understanding of the professional socialisation process of new-to-practice paramedics generated by Devenish, et al. (2016) and the contributing scholarship of others (Huot, 2013; Kennedy, et al., 2015; Lazarsfeld-Jensen, et al., 2014; Lazarsfeld-Jensen, et al., 2011; O'Meara, Tourle, Madigan, & Lighton, 2012), provide valuable insights to paramedic transition from university to the workplace. However, the transition experienced by paramedics to other work roles beyond the post-internship year is poorly understood. Studies of paramedic work role transition complement the knowledge of professional socialisation by illuminating transitions across the range of a paramedic's career. In other words, the development of specialist work role transition theories in paramedicine will *extend* the findings of the research conducted on the professional socialisation of paramedics.

Two non-peer reviewed reports on community paramedicine programs were located that yielded information relevant to work role transition. The first, published by Health Workforce Australia (Thompson, et al., 2014), focused on

the impact and evaluation of an expanded scope of practice model at five sites across three jurisdictions in Australia. Although not reporting explicitly on the process of transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine, the authors did conduct qualitative interviews to better understand the personal characteristics of effective Extended Care Paramedics (ECPs). Amongst their findings, ECPs were noted to be committed individuals with a “can-do” attitude (Thompson, et al., 2014). Moreover, ECPs demonstrated a willingness to provide quality care and improve their clinical practice. The findings, whilst providing potentially useful suppositions on the process of transition, were typically descriptive in nature and focused on factors for the successful operationalisation of an ECP program, rather than examining specifically the process of transition.

In a report of higher methodological quality on the evaluation of ECPs based on a quasi-experimental design across five sites in the UK, job design theory was utilised as a theoretical framework to survey both ECPs and non-ECPs in the study sites (Mason et al., 2009). The survey aims were to evaluate the attitudes and perceptions of ECPs with respect to their working relationships with other health professionals, satisfaction and confidence with the role and future career progression. Ultimately though, the focus of the qualitative research was to complement the other epidemiological studies to understanding how to integrate ECPs into the local health economy better. Arguably more insightful than the Health Workforce Australia publication due to the inclusion of qualitative data framed by theory, this report lacked sufficient depth and rigour to provide a rich interpretation of the work role transition to ECP.

The dearth of discipline-specific literature in paramedicine has resulted in the inclusion of literature from other related health professions. Chapter 3 turns to the examination of the nursing literature, particularly those inclusive of Nurse Practitioners, to draw parallels with paramedic work role transition to community paramedicine.

3.3 TRANSITION THEORY IN THE NURSING DISCIPLINE

In contrast to paramedicine, the nursing literature returned more comprehensive results on transition to specialist roles, possibly due to the nursing discipline being more advanced along the professional continuum. Within the nursing discipline, similarities can be drawn to community paramedicine, particularly in relation to the Nurse Practitioner (NP) role. NPs have operated successfully in many countries for over 30 years (Raven, et al., 2006). Due to the similarity of role descriptors in their respective disciplines, NPs are arguably the nursing counterparts to paramedics who specialise in a community paramedicine role. The Australian and Nursing Midwifery Council offered this definition of NPs:

A nurse practitioner is a registered nurse educated to function autonomously and collaboratively in an advanced and extended clinical role. The role includes assessment and management of clients using nursing knowledge and skills and may include but is not limited to the direct referral of patients to other health care professionals, prescribing medications and ordering diagnostic investigations (Ryan, 2009, p. 4).

Common to the role descriptors of NPs and ECPs/CPs is the high degree of autonomy applied within the framework of collaborative practice in the community or with other health professionals. Both these work roles necessitate an elevated level of clinical reasoning and judgment. Furthermore, the similar characteristics of an ECP/CP model of mobile, community-based health care and community nursing models have been recognised previously (O'Meara, 2014). However, the research to date on NP role transition has been primarily descriptive qualitative studies (Barnes, 2014). The majority of these studies originated from the United States, which is not surprising considering NPs have been well established in the United States for almost 40 years (Raven, et al., 2006). The literature review identified 10 articles that specifically addressed the work role transition to Nurse Practitioner (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1

Articles in the Literature Review that specifically addressed Work Role Transition to Nurse Practitioner

Author/Date	Country of origin	Major construct / investigation (per author(s))	Methods/theoretical framework used (if any)	Outcomes	Reviewer's comments
Barnes (2014)	United States	Concept analysis of NP role transition.	Theoretical study using Walker and Avant (2005) method of concept analysis.	Four defining attributes of NP role description.	Synthesis of the evidence to form a concept analysis.
Barnes (2015)	United States	Relationship between prior RN experience and orientation affecting NP role transition.	Cross-sectional survey of NPs/Meleis's Transition Theory (2000).	Orientation promoted transition. RN experience neutral.	Limited in scope.
Barton (2007a)	United Kingdom	Experiences of student nurse practitioners.	Ethnographic study.	Similarity with existing theory (Van Gennepe's Rites of Passage).	Narrow focus limited to student phase.
Brown and Olshansky (1997)	United States	Creation of NP transition model.	Longitudinal/Grounded Theory.	Four stages of transition.	Athoretical and descriptive.
Cusson and Strange (2008)	United States	Transition among neonatal nurse practitioners.	Qualitative descriptive design.	Transition is a linear process comprising four themes.	Convenience sample of 70 NPs. Themes lacking analytic depth.

Author/Date	Country of origin	Major construct / investigation (per author(s))	Methods/theoretical framework used (if any)	Outcomes	Reviewer's comments
Heitz, Steiner, and Burman (2004)	United States	Transition to Family NP.	Grounded Theory.	Conceptual model.	Descriptive with useful sensitising concepts generated.
Kelly and Mathews (2001)	United States	Transition to NP.	"Qualitative approach".	Thematic analysis resulting in six themes.	Methodology poorly described. Results should be cautiously interpreted.
Poronsky (2013)	United States	Transition to NP.	Literature review.	Exploration of NP transition through transition theory.	Effective discussion on use of transition theory to explore NP transition.
Spinks (2009)	United Kingdom	Transition to neonatal NP.	Personal reflective account.	Reflective practice account.	Anecdotal framed with reflective practice models.
Sullivan-Bentz et al. (2010)	Canada	Examination of role transition and support requirements of NPs in their first year.	Ethnographic study and narrative analysis.	Identification of factors that facilitate or hinder transition.	Good scope in reporting outcomes including policy and politics, interprofessional relationships and education.

Of the 10 NP role transition articles in Table 3.1, most (n=7) are empirical studies, while two are theoretical studies and one is a personal reflective account. No articles originated in Australasia, limiting the context to North America and the United Kingdom. Additionally, the results of the empirical studies were generally weighted towards descriptive accounts of the NP transition experience or were limited in scope. Consequently, the findings should be interpreted cautiously. Despite, the findings being NP specific, they may carry some relevance when examining the work role transition of paramedics to community paramedicine.

Through the analogous relationship between NP work role transition and ECP/CP work role transition, the NP transition experience provides a tentative insight into the elements of ECP/CP work role transition. These insights, termed "sensitising concepts" (Charmaz, 2014), offer provisional ideas relevant to ECP/CP transition. In other words, sensitising concepts provide a point of departure to conduct research in ECP/CP work role transition. Additionally, an understanding of NP work role transition is necessary to demonstrate how the resultant theory of work role transition to community paramedicine challenges the transferability of existing knowledge from cognate health disciplines.

Finally, the body of work of Boychuk Duchscher (2001, 2008, 2009), a frequently cited author in the field of nursing transition, was included in a recent systematic review examining nurses' perceptions and experiences of work role transitions – more so than any other author (Arrowsmith, Lau-Walker, Norman, & Maben, 2016). Boychuk Duchscher's (2009) most recent publication on work role transition produced a theoretical framework of the initial role transition for newly graduated nurses. Building upon the seminal work of Kramer (1974), Boychuk Duchscher's "transition shock" describes the experience of moving from the relatively well protected environment of academia to the less familiar role of professionally practicing nurse (2001, 2008, 2009). Transition shock describes the first three to four months of role transition and is characterised by feelings of loss, confusion, doubt and disorientation.

Of interest, is the apparent similarity of the nurse's experience of transition shock across a range of other work roles and disciplines including paramedicine (Devenish, et al., 2016; Kennedy, et al., 2015), medicine (Berridge, Freeth, Sharpe, & Roberts, 2007; Brennan et al., 2010; Westerman, et al., 2010), and health academia (Anderson, 2009). Although the transferability of Boychuk Duchscher's conceptual framework is again limited by the tasks, roles and context in which the transition occurs, the apparent similarity of experiences between disciplines suggests elements of Boychuk Duchscher's framework may be transferable to work role transition in community paramedicine.

The examination of the theoretical background of work role transition now turns to the generic organisational literature. Nicholson's (1984) definition of work role transition¹⁶ was utilised for this PhD study and although simplistic, was sufficiently comprehensive to cover the topic area under investigation. Moreover, Nicholson's work has been the subject of further scrutiny by others (Ashforth & Saks, 1995; West & Rushton, 1989).

3.4 NICHOLSON'S THEORY OF WORK ROLE TRANSITION

Nicholson (1984) published a widely cited article on work role transition that originated within the business and psychology disciplines and which has also been applied as a theoretical framework in the examination of transition to specialist roles in medicine (Westerman, et al., 2010) and nursing (Barnes, 2014; Glen & Waddington, 1998). For these reasons, Nicholson's model is useful in providing a theoretical background to specialist work role transition in paramedicine. Nicholson's model is dynamic in the sense that the focus is on an individual's process of transition to a new work role. The model analyses the interplay between two factors which are independent of each other in the process of work role transition: personal development and role development. In essence, personal development involves a person adapting themselves to

¹⁶ Work role transition is defined as "any change in employment status and any major change in job content" (Nicholson, 1984, p. 173).

the role whilst role development involves adapting the role to fit the person. The interplay of these two factors creates four “modes of adjustment” (Nicholson, 1984, p. 184). In other words, there are four means by which a work role transition is put into effect. The modes of adjustment are shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Modes of adjustment to transition. From “A Theory of Work Role Transitions” by N. Nicholson, 1984, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 29, 2, p. 176.

In brief, the four modes of adjustment are depicted in each quadrant of the model:

- Replication - the person performs in much the same way as in previous roles and thus only minimal adjustments are required.
- Absorption – the emphasis is borne almost exclusively by the person particularly in the area of role learning.
- Determination – the person actively determines the structure of the new role. In other words, the emphasis is borne by the role.
- Exploration – change occurs simultaneously in both personal qualities and role boundaries.

The theory also proposes in turn that the “modes of adjustment” are influenced by both personal factors and environmental factors. Personal factors include:

- Desire for feedback – from colleagues/other staff on appropriate or required behaviours.
- Desire for control – over change the individual needs to affect upon the role.

Environmental factors include:

- Role requirements:
 - Discretion - the latitude to alter task-related characteristics such as methods and timing.
 - Novelty – degree to which the role allows prior knowledge, skills and habits.
- Induction socialisation processes.
- Prior occupation socialisation.
- Individual personality characteristics.

For example, an individual entering a similar role to their previous one may experience both low personal development and low role development. Such an individual falls within the category of “Replication” and is additionally influenced by a weak desire for control and weak desire for feedback. Alternatively, an individual entering a new highly technical role may, for example, experience high personal development and low role development. This category is labelled “Absorption” and is characterised by a person’s strong desire for feedback and weak desire for control.

The transferability of Nicholson’s model to work role transition in community paramedicine has limitations, principally due to the generic framework the theory employs. That is, the model requires the input of data based on the perceptions of individuals undergoing transition and therefore cannot be applied “off the shelf”. Furthermore, Nicholson’s theory is a

predictive model of work role transition with outcomes provided in terms of “degrees of adjustment”. An explanatory model of work role transition would allow a finer understanding of the interconnections between transition elements, thereby providing more targeted intervention strategies to facilitate the transition experience for inductees to community paramedicine.

Nonetheless, the utility of Nicholson’s model still has some merit to understanding the transition from paramedic to community paramedicine. As a predictive model, Nicholson’s theory may provide some insight into the association between the modes of adjustment. For instance, West and Rushton (1989) found that role innovation was associated with nurses’ length of training. That is, the longer the nurses were in training, the stronger was the desire to change their roles. These results have implications for nursing managers and policy makers in resolving issues with nursing staff who may become frustrated and dissatisfied due to an inability to change their roles.

3.5 CONCLUSION

The theoretical background of work role transition relevant to community paramedicine comprises mostly qualitative studies from the nursing discipline. Moreover, most studies are weighted towards descriptive accounts of the transition experience. Empirical studies of professional socialisation or work role transition in paramedicine are rare. Despite the paucity of rigorous literature, the utility of extant theoretical frameworks in a grounded theory study has some merit. Similar to the premise and application of the literature review in Chapter 2, the value of examining the theoretical background of professional socialisation and work role transition provides a source of sensitising concepts. It engages in comparative analysis and facilitates abductive reasoning. Having examined the extant literature and theoretical background of work role transition, Chapter 4 turns to explore the methods and methodology used for the data collection and analysis of this study.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this research is to explore the work role transition of paramedics to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Having discussed the relevant literature pertaining to role transition and paramedicine, Chapter Four provides a rationale for the selection of constructivist grounded theory as the most appropriate methodology to answer the research question. Additionally, the ontological¹⁷ and epistemological¹⁸ assumptions are presented, and the congruence with constructivist grounded theory established. The methods used in the constructivist grounded theory approach are broken down and presented in the following six elements:

- research design
- research sites and participants
- inclusion and exclusion criteria
- ethics and operational approvals
- data collection
- data analysis

A concept map explaining the research process is presented in Figure 4.1.

¹⁷ Ontology is concerned with what a researcher believes is the nature of social reality (Grix, 2002).

¹⁸ Epistemology is concerned with how knowledge can be created or constructed (Scotland, 2012; Urquhart, 2012).

Figure 4.1 Concept map of the research process

4.2 RESEARCH DESIGN: CONSTRUCTIVIST GROUNDED THEORY

Constructivist grounded theory (CGT) based on the work by Charmaz (2014), informs the methodological¹⁹ approach for this research study. CGT

¹⁹ In a recent publication, Charmaz (2017b) acknowledges grounded theory to be both a "methodology" and a "method". However, this PhD study regards CGT a methodology. A methodology is a set of principles and ideas that inform the design of a research study (Birks & Mills, 2011). Arguably, the *Constructivist* grounded theory approach is strongly influenced by the principles and ideas (philosophical assumptions) adopted by the researcher (Charmaz, 2014; Urquhart, 2012). Therefore, CGT can be regarded as a methodology. Methods, on the other hand, are the techniques and procedures used to generate and analyse data (Corbin & Strauss, 2015).

is a contemporary version in the evolution of the work of seminal grounded theorists, Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss (Bryant & Charmaz, 2010), though arguably CGT is influenced more by the pragmatist heritage of Strauss (Charmaz, 2017a). Along the spectra of grounded theory approaches from positivism through to interpretivism (Birks & Mills, 2011), epistemologically, CGT is weighted towards interpretivism. That is, the research product of CGT methodology is an interpretation (construction) of social reality rather than objective renderings of it (Charmaz, 2014).

CGT was selected as research methodology for two principal reasons. First, CGT represents a “tried-and-true” set of procedures for theory construction (Corbin & Strauss, 2015, p. 11). That is, theory is constructed through inductive analytic and systematic data analysis, rather than simply a description or application of extant theories (Charmaz, 2014). The procedures CGT utilise however, are not applied mechanistically (Suddaby, 2006). Rather, theory construction occurs via an iterative movement between data and analysis. Second, as this study involves an examination of the process of transition from Qualified Paramedic to a specialist role in community paramedicine, CGT is argued to be well suited to the analysis of actions and processes (Charmaz, 2014).

Additionally, constructivism was selected in favour of constructionism as a theoretical perspective to the grounded theory methodology. Despite sharing a similar heritage with symbolic interactionists, the two ideologies diverge epistemologically with constructivism placing a greater emphasis on reflexivity of the researcher and the subjective representation of the participant’s views, meanings and actions in specific situations (Charmaz, 2014).

In the past, generic qualitative studies have claimed grounded theory methodology to legitimise the study, despite lacking a clear articulation of the methods used (Charmaz, 2014; Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). Indeed, Charmaz (2017b, p. 2) refers to grounded theory approaches as a “constellation of methods”. This PhD research lays claim to a bona fide CGT

study through the following actions (Birks & Mills, 2011; Charmaz, 2014; Hallberg, 2006):

- Data collection and analysis occurred simultaneously through an iterative process,
- emphasis on theory construction rather than description,
- use of constant comparative methods, memo writing and theoretical sampling (discussed later in the chapter),
- data was examined for variations and contrasts (negative cases) rather than simply patterns and,
- use of inductive and abductive logic to construct abstract analytic categories

The orientation of the researcher's philosophical assumptions with respect to ontology and epistemology are important determinants to how qualitative research data is collected and interpreted (Grix, 2002; Twining, Heller, Nussbaum, & Tsai, 2017). The purpose is not to argue a "correct" interpretation of the data, rather it aims to make the researcher's biases clear. In other words, the philosophical assumptions the researcher brings to a study act as a "lens" through which the researcher interprets the qualitative data.

Epistemologically, CGT emphasises the interrelationship between the researcher and the participant (Mills, Bonner, & Francis, 2008). In this way, constructivism acknowledges that the resultant theory is an interpretation of multiple perspectives by the researcher (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). Analysis of the data does not provide an objective rendering of reality, to which postpositivists researchers aspire. Moreover, in a departure from the methodological stance of Glaser and Stauss' seminal 1967 text *The Discovery of Grounded Theory*, the "truth" in constructivist grounded theory, is not there to be "discovered" (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). Rather, the co-construction between study participants and the researcher suggests that social reality is a rendering of the researcher's own perception of reality influenced by their own experiences, beliefs and professional backgrounds (Corbin & Strauss, 2015).

An acceptance of multiple realities is consistent with a relativist ontology and is congruent with the interpretivist epistemology of Charmazian constructivist grounded theory.

4.3 RATIONALE FOR SELECTION OF RESEARCH SITES

This PhD research examines the transition of Qualified Paramedics to a specialist role in community paramedicine in three paramedic jurisdictions across two continents. Chapter One provided an overview of the three study sites. In the interests of continuing familiarity with the context in which this research was undertaken, a summary overview of the research sites is presented in Table 4.1.

SA Ambulance Service (SAAS) was selected as a study site since their Extended Care Paramedic model served as a template for implementation at five sites across Australia as part of a prospective evaluation by Health Workforce Australia (Thompson, et al., 2014). It is unclear why Health Workforce Australia selected SAAS for the evaluation – possibly due to only one other paramedic service (NSW Ambulance) operating an ECP program within Australia at the time. Nevertheless, the SAAS program was included in the current study as it is well established and represents a mature program.

The NSW Ambulance ECP program was selected for inclusion in the current study for two reasons. First, the program is relatively large with approximately 105 ECPs working in both metropolitan and regional settings. Access to a larger pool of participants allows for more opportunities to explore sufficiently areas of emerging theoretical interest. Second, the program is well established, signalling a degree of operational stability and efficacy of the program.

Table 4.1

Summary Overview of Research Sites

	SA Ambulance Service	NSW Ambulance	Alberta Health Services EMS
Program type	Extended Care Paramedic	Extended Care Paramedic	Community Paramedic
Inaugurated	2008	2007	2013
Number of paramedics (2016 approximate)	35	105	22
Prerequisites for recruitment	Intensive Care Paramedic	Qualified Paramedic, Intensive Care Paramedic	Emergency Medical Technologist - Paramedic
Training	4-week theory, 2-week clinical placement, 240 hours supervised practice	10-week theory, 2-week clinical placement, 12-month consolidation	2-week theory (2 blocks), 1-week supervised practice (variable)
Caseload (per annum)	4706 (SA Ambulance Service, 2013)	18,000 (approximate) (NSW Ambulance, 2016)	5239 (Alberta Health Services, 2015)

Finally, the Community Paramedic program in Calgary was selected as it represents the other major service delivery arm in community paramedicine, and provides an international perspective²⁰. Additionally, Australia and Canada share several attributes including a Federal parliamentary system of government, being geographically large and both having indigenous populations. Indeed, the similarities between political and healthcare systems has provided the justification for comparative analyses between Australia and Canada in other health studies (Philippon & Braithwaite, 2008; Pong, DesMeules, & Lagacé, 2009). Furthermore, Alberta Health Services Calgary Zone indicated in prior personal communication, an appreciation of the significance of paramedicine research and willingness to participate in the study.

4.4 PARTICIPANT INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Participants in Australia were eligible for inclusion in the study if they were currently or previously qualified (credentialed) Extended Care Paramedics employed by either NSW Ambulance or SA Ambulance Service. Similarly, either currently or previously qualified Community Paramedics employed by AHS EMS Calgary Zone were also eligible for inclusion. The paramedic was deemed to be “qualified” if their employer had granted authority for independent practice in the role of either an ECP or CP. The distinction is necessary as NSW Ambulance ECPs must complete a two-year consolidation period before being fully credentialed. However, independent practice occurs at the successful conclusion of the clinical placement phase and thus NSW Ambulance ECPs were deemed “qualified” from this point in time. Self-nomination was considered confirmation of qualification and supporting documentation was not sought.

²⁰ At the commencement of the study, no Australasian paramedic service operated a CP-type model. However in October 2016, SAAS became the first in Australia to operationalise a CP program in two regional areas (Wright, 2016).

Additionally, participants were required to be English speaking for inclusion into the study. Whilst Canada has two official languages - English and French – demographically, Alberta is predominantly English speaking with over 85% of the population nominating English as the language most often spoken at home. Conversely, less than one percent speak French (Statistics Canada, 2011). Thus, it was considered unlikely to encounter a French monolingual participant. Moreover, due to budgetary limitations of the study, an interpreter for data collection would have been prohibitively expensive.

4.5 ETHICAL AND OPERATIONAL APPROVALS

A mandatory requirement for all researchers at Queensland University of Technology is the completion of Research Ethics, Integrity and Safety (REIS) training program prior to the submission of an ethics application to the University Human Research Ethics Committee. The researcher completed all five modules of the REIS program in February 2015 (Appendix A) and the study was subsequently approved by the Queensland University of Technology Human Research Ethics Committee in September 2015 (Approval Number: 1500000813) (Appendix B). The study was consistent with the Australian Government’s National Health and Medical Research Council definition of “low risk research” as the only foreseeable risk to participants was one of inconvenience or possible mild discomfort (National Health and Medical Research Council, 2014). Two subsequent minor ethics variations that did not impact on the study design were approved in December 2015 and February 2016 (Appendix C).

Ethical and operational²¹ approvals were also required by the participating organisations prior to commencing recruitment. NSW Ambulance granted ethical and operational approval through a single application in March 2016. In contrast, authority to commence recruitment in South Australia and

²¹ Operational approval involved evaluating the capacity of the paramedic service to support the research in areas such as use of service assets, staff availability and on-going governance procedures.

Alberta required an operational approval from each paramedic service, in addition to Human Research Ethics Committee approval from the parent health agency (Appendix D, E, F). Approval was granted in May 2016 for South Australia (Appendix G) and following the signing of a "Research Agreement" between Alberta Health Services and the researcher, endorsement to recruit participants in Calgary was secured in August 2016 (Appendix H, I).

Participants were provided with a Participant Information and Consent Form (PICF) (Appendix K) prior to the interview, detailing the study purpose and other information, such as the support services available. The PICF was individualised for either Australian or Canadian participants, to ensure appropriate naming nomenclature (Extended Care Paramedic or Community Paramedic) and local contact numbers for support services. The participant was required to voluntarily sign the consent form prior to the interview and the form was subsequently filed in a secure location at QUT.

Confidentiality of participants was recognised as a cornerstone of ethical conduct during this research. Accordingly, establishing and maintaining the confidentiality of participants received significant consideration at every stage of the research process. For instance, hard copies of consent forms are stored securely under lock-and-key at the Kelvin Grove campus of QUT. Additionally, electronic data, such as MP3 (audio) files containing participant interviews, are secured under password protection on a QUT server.

Importantly, participants were de-identified through the substitution of names with a randomly generated two-digit number (www.random.org/integers). No further identifiers, such as gender or the paramedic service were included. Both SAAS and AHS EMS programs (and to a lesser extent NSW) are relatively small and operate from centralised locations. Given the assumed familiarity of the participants, the inclusion of demographic information raised the possibility of participant identification through interview transcripts. However, the participant's demographic information could be accessed by the researcher to facilitate analysis, such as making comparisons between paramedic services.

4.6 RECRUITMENT OF PARTICIPANTS

This PhD study utilised purposive sampling as a strategy to access “information rich” participants who could provide the most substantial insights into the research questions (Devers & Frankel, 2000, p. 264). As the research questions centred on the transition experience of ECPs and CPs, sampling was directed towards the recruitment of participants assumed to be well-informed about the process of transition to community paramedicine. Furthermore, reverse snowball sampling, whereby participants already recruited to the study were asked to assist in the recruitment of their ECP/CP colleagues was also employed.

Participant recruitment was initiated with the dissemination of an “approach” email (Appendix J) with an attachment containing participation information and a consent form (Appendix K). The content of the email was approved by the respective paramedic services and initially distributed to ECP and CP program managers. The email was subsequently forwarded to the corporate email accounts of operational ECPs/CPs, thereby ensuring participant confidentiality was not breached. The email introduced the study and requested participants to contact the researcher directly should they wish to become involved in the study. ECP and CP program managers were not made aware of who had volunteered to participate. Following participant contact, a time for the interview was arranged ensuring the participant was off-duty.

Formerly credentialed ECPs/CPs or paramedics who unsuccessfully attempted transition were not included in the corporate email distribution list, despite the requests of the researcher. Subsequent attempts at contact were made through snowball sampling, however, the strategy was unsuccessful. Given the limited time and resources available to complete the study, no further attempts at contact were made. The inclusion of former ECPs/CPs and paramedics that had unsuccessfully attempted transition may have added a unique perspective to the conceptual understanding of the transition experience. The absence of data collected from formerly credentialed

ECPs/CPs or those who unsuccessfully attempted transition is recognised, therefore, as a potential limitation of the study.

The total number of participants recruited for this study was 36. The number of participants from each paramedic jurisdiction and prior designation before commencing ECP/CP training is outlined in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2

Number of Participants Recruited and Prior Designation to ECP/CP Training

Prior designation	Number of participants recruited			Total
	NSWA	SAAS	AHS EMS	
ICP/EMT-P	8	10	11	29
QP/EMT	7	0	0	7
Total	15	10	11	36

Note. ICP = Intensive Care Paramedic; *EMT-P* = Emergency Medical Technologist – Paramedic; QP = Qualified Paramedic; *EMT* = Emergency Medical Technician.

4.7 DATA COLLECTION

The research data were collected from two main sources. The first was voice recorded semi-structured interviews utilising an interview guide (Appendix L) and open-ended questions to allow the participants the freedom to explore new avenues and concepts beyond the interview guide. The interview guide was developed from the extant literature, the researcher’s knowledge and experiences in the field, and supervisor feedback. Sample questions included:

- What led you to decide to become an ECP/CP?
- At what point did you feel you have successfully completed the transition to ECP/CP (if at all)?
- Did you feel supported in the new role at an individual (peer) and organisational (systems) level?

Most participants were interviewed individually, in person or via the internet carriage service Skype™. Three participants were interviewed via telephone due to scheduling difficulties and inability to access the internet. Interviews, both in person and via a carriage service, were conducted in private surroundings to encourage openness and maintain confidentiality. The length of interviews ranged from approximately 35 minutes to 90 minutes. All interviews were audio recorded and stored securely as per Queensland University of Technology's Manual of Policies and Procedures (MOPP) D/2.8 Management of Research Data.

The second data collection source included printed or electronic documents from paramedic services, health departments and government agencies. Examples include web pages, annual reports, policy directives, orientation manuals, local activity reports, performance evaluations, training programs, and referral forms. From the constructivist perspective, the documents that were collected are not assumed to be objective facts. Indeed, documents are created within social, economic, historical, cultural and situational contexts (Charmaz, 2014). The documents constituted another form of data and provided contextualisation to the programs under study. Moreover, the findings from the interviews were correlated against the documents to assess the degree to which the process of transition complements operational and policy expectations.

All interviews were transcribed by uploading the original audio files to a professional transcription service following receipt of a confidentiality agreement (Appendix M). During the transcription process, participant's names were substituted with their allocated two-digit identifier to further protect participant anonymity. For largely budgetary reasons, audio files were transcribed as "clean verbatim" such that interjections such as "ahs" and "ums" were not included. Similarly, pauses and other nuances such as laughter were not included. However the subtleties of verbal communication during an interview are not without value (Charmaz, 2014). Following receipt of the transcripts, the audio recordings were played and relevant cues noted, such as laughter and inflection in the voices of the participants. This process

ensured verification of the accuracy of the transcription and further immersion with the content.

The number of participants required to provide sufficient richness and depth in qualitative studies has often been an area of contention amongst researchers (Liamputtong, 2009). Indeed, Creswell (2012, p. 60) established that the literature “did a poor job of operationalizing the concept of saturation, providing no description of how saturation might be determined and no practical guidelines for estimating sample sizes for purposively sampled interviews.” Whilst accepting predefined limits is problematic, ultimately the number of participants is dependent on whether fresh data reveals new theoretical insights (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). Although the point where no new theoretical insight is established has been referred to as “saturation”, the use of the term appears contentious within the literature. Corbin and Strauss (2015) offer the most salient definition of theoretical saturation, suggesting a point where further data gathering and analysis add little to the conceptualisation of categories. Moreover, the researcher must have sufficient confidence that the categories are well developed and importantly, appreciate that variations can always be discovered should the data collection continue. Pragmatically, Creswell (2012) proposes saturation is likely to be reached at between 20 to 60 participants, while a study by Mason (2010) of 560 PhD studies using qualitative approaches noted that the mean sample size was 31. However, to pre-define sample size is somewhat counterintuitive to the principles of qualitative research. Ultimately, the sample size was theoretically and pragmatically determined.

4.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Consistent with the grounded theory approach, data analysis was initiated with the use of inductive logic via an iterative process to enhance precision in the analysis (Charmaz, 2014). The use of inductive logic is first apparent in the writing of memos following each participant’s interview. In essence, memoing is a written record of analysis: a means of having a dialogue with one’s self to garner clarity from the complexity of the data (Corbin &

Strauss, 2015). However, memoing is more than a mechanistic system for the storage and retrieval of descriptive information. Crucially, memoing represented the first analytic foray into analysis of the raw data from participants²². Through asking questions, proposing relationships and forming tentative concepts, memoing formed a crucial element of the iterative process.

By convention, memos are not subject to academic scrutiny, intended only for personal consumption (Charmaz, 2014; Creswell, 2012). However, memos also provide an audit trail of the analytic progress of the research (Charmaz, 2014). To that end, Figure 4.2 is presented as an exemplar of how memos recorded in a personal diary facilitated the analytic direction of the research. The language and clarity of script reflects the ad-hoc convenience of adding memos at opportunistic moments. In fact, the advantage of a hand-written diary lay in the ability to record spontaneous thoughts along with the ease of portability and convenience. Additionally, memos and annotations were recorded electronically during the coding process.

4.8.1 Initial coding

The next level of analysis began with the coding of the interview transcripts²³. In brief, coding assigns a short word or phrase that renders interpretative meaning to a portion of the participant's transcript (Saldaña, 2015). Coding took the analysis beyond that of the initial memos by "splitting" the data into smaller codable elements (Bernard, Wutich, & Ryan, 2016; Saldaña, 2015). The splitting of the data ranged from a few words and phrases to sentences and paragraphs based on the conceptual underpinnings

²² Memoing had commenced prior to data collection and analysis. Memoing served to challenge preconceptions, engage in reflexivity and record early heuristic thoughts of the research direction.

²³ Coding was facilitated with the use of computer assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS) NVivo Pro™. The value of CAQDAS lies in the ability of the software to efficiently store, organise, manage and reconfigure large amounts of data to facilitate analytic reflection (Saldaña, 2015).

Figure 4.2 Extract of the researcher's methodological diary with commentary on relevance of diary entry

of the element. In essence, the data was split by asking the classic axiom, "What is going on here?" These initial attempts at conceptualisation of the data moved the analysis forward by defining what was happening in the data, how actions occurred and why relationships evolved. Importantly, initial coding also informed where the gaps in the data were located.

Alternate approaches to coding, such as the popular "line-by-line" method advocated by some notable authors, were considered for this study (Charmaz, 2014; Corbin & Strauss, 2015). However, this PhD study utilised the coding technique of splitting the data into small conceptual elements. By splitting the data, sufficient depth to drive the analysis towards an emergent conceptual framework was generated without being overwhelmed by voluminous "fine-grained" codes. Moreover, the coding of the data was subsumed by a combination of coding techniques consistent with the epistemology of constructivist grounded theory, including gerunds, in vivo coding and emotion coding. Examples of initial coding techniques are provided in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3
Initial Coding Techniques and Examples

Coding technique	Code	Raw Data
Gerunds: Coding for action and processes utilising the verb form of a noun.	Seeking reassurance	P55: Yes I think so. Generally, you know what you are thinking and the path you want to go down. Sometimes you just need a little bit of reassurance to make sure that you are not alone in your thought process and the other extended care paramedics would do the same. Once you have got that reassurance you are comfortable to go down that pathway.

Coding technique	Code	Raw Data
In vivo: Codes transcribed directly from the data.	Trying to stay afloat	P17: You are just swimming; you are just trying to stay afloat. I don't know if it was from coming from the country and dealing with a different management system where it is very laid back. [laughs] And never having worked in Sydney before I had to get used to doing lots and lots of jobs, working by myself, learning the management but not knowing who to talk to about things.
Emotion coding: Labelling the feelings participant felt.	Feeling nervous	P68: Quite nervous. Yeah, quite nervous. So my first suture job, you know, very nervous. My first catheter job, very nervous. But you're just basically thrown in the deep end and you just do the best you can. (laughing)

4.8.2 Focused coding and theory building

Focused coding (Charmaz, 2014; Saldaña, 2015) was the second major phase in the coding process and advanced the theoretical direction of the analysis. The initial codes were rearranged to fit under more specific code categories, thereby creating a hierarchy of codes. Focused coding provided the supporting structure to the embryotic analysis by identifying the initial codes which afforded greater theoretical reach and direction. Whereas earlier coding was relatively basic in form and structure, focused coding drove the data into deeper analysis.

During the process of focused coding, the theoretical plausibility of categories began to emerge. For instance, the core category *Engaging in a Community of Practice*, initially formed from the clustering of the focused

codes: *Seeking reassurance*²⁴, *Facilitating partnerships* and *Equalising relationships*. Furthermore, the robustness of the core categories was enhanced through a variety of complementary strategies including theoretical sampling, abductive reasoning and member checking. The following excerpt is an example of confirming the theoretical plausibility of the core category, *Engaging in a Community of Practice*, via member checking:

Interviewer: Thanks again P83 – really appreciated. Can I just ask if I’m right with this equation? Being a knowledgeable, proficient, competent etc. CP, means the physician is more confident/comfortable in working with that particular CP, so the CP receives validation that he/she is doing the right thing, therefore there is an increase in CP confidence, which equals faster transition. Does that sound about right?

P83: Absolutely. That has been the case in my experience and in talking with my colleagues.

Although less obvious, the passage above highlights an abductive “leap” taken to illuminate the salient features of the community of practice in the Late Phase of transition. Reichertz (2007) argues the inclusion of abductive logic moves a grounded theory study away from qualitative descriptive accounts to that of an abstract conceptual framework. Briefly, abductive reasoning makes an inferential leap to consider all theoretical possibilities to explain the observed data. The question to the participant arose as an attempt to plausibly explain the relationship between competence, physician attitude, validation and confidence in the late phase of transition. The resultant data contributed to the development of the Community of Practice feedback cycle in the Late Phase (see Chapter 8) and ultimately, the core category itself.

²⁴ *Seeking reassurance* is an example of an initial code that was elevated to a focused code as it carried conceptual authority.

4.8.3 Temporality

Constructivist grounded theory provides the tools to study temporality (Charmaz, 2017a). Establishing the temporality or timings of the various elements in the transition experience was integral to answering the research questions. Moreover, understanding the sequencing of events informed not only the processes involved in transition, but also assisted in establishing the interrelationships between core categories. Although not used exclusively to establish temporality, engaging in constant comparisons and sensitising concepts were two key strategies utilised in establishing temporality.

The use of constant comparative methods is fundamental to a CGT study (Charmaz, 2014). Constant comparison aims to make comparisons between data thereby establishing if the data is conceptually similar or different (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). By comparing statement with statement and incident with incident across a range of participants, the temporality of the transition process was revealed. Table 4.4 provides an example of how establishing temporality through the context of the transcripts illuminated the evolution of the *Community of Practice* core category over time.

Table 4.4

Example of Establishing Temporality through Constant Comparison

Community of Practice - <i>Early Phase</i>	Community of Practice – <i>Late Phase</i>
Generally, you know what you are thinking and the path you want to go down. Sometimes you just need a little bit of reassurance to make sure that you are not alone in your thought process and the other Extended Care Paramedics would do the same. Once you have got that reassurance you are comfortable to go down that pathway. P55.	That is when I believe you really have done the complete transition. It doesn't matter what happens during the day. You don't have to make a lot of phone calls to ask a lot of questions. For me most the time when I call for advice it is like, I am in a situation and I know what I am supposed to do but I always make that phone call to check and

say, "What do you think about this?"

This is what has happened. P50.

In addition, sensitising concepts derived from the extant literature, helped guide the initial analysis and establish temporality. For instance, transition theories from cognate disciplines (Barnes, 2014; Poronsky, 2012; Spoelstra & Robbins, 2010) suggest work role transition is comprised of discernible phases or stages. With the understanding that sensitising concepts provide a place to start analysis, codes and categories were sifted into three broad phases of transition – Early, Middle, Late. During the later stages of analysis, a fourth “non-active” *Pre-transition Phase* became apparent in the transition experience.

4.9 RIGOUR

The determination of rigour or quality in qualitative research is challenging to which a different set of criteria from quantitative inquiry is required (Corbin & Strauss, 2015; De Witt & Ploeg, 2006; Tracy, 2010). Positivist researchers, for example, have questioned the perceived lack of validity (credibility) in qualitative research and thus view the findings as unreliable (Liamputtong, 2009). Indeed, some qualitative researchers advocate the adoption of quantitative terminology such as “validity” rather than the qualitatively aligned “credibility”, to bring qualitative research more in-line with the “hard” sciences (Rolfe, 2006). However the application of quantitative approaches to rigour in qualitative science is problematic in a number of areas, particularly on ontological and epistemological grounds (Koch & Harrington, 1998).

This research study, for example, contends there are multiple realities constructed by numerous actors – a philosophical departure from the positivist agnosticism of a single measurable reality. More specifically, constructivism as a methodological foundation of this research study views the researcher as the

“instrument” of measurement, and is therefore not open to positivist’s criteria such as repeatability. In other words, the same presentation of data to a different researcher could yield different results due to the subjective and complex interpretation of the data. The argument presented here is not to absolve the researcher of the responsibility to establish rigour; on the contrary, rigour in qualitative research is no less important than in quantitative science.

Establishing rigour in qualitative research is perhaps best conceptualised around the question “What makes a research product believable or plausible?” (Koch & Harrington, 1998, p. 882). The strategies to ensure rigour in this research study were informed by four principles: credibility, dependability, transferability and confirmability (Liamputtong, 2009). In brief, the techniques employed to ensure rigour in the study, based on the work of Tuckett (2005), are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5

Techniques Employed to ensure Rigour

Criteria	Technique	Rationale
Credibility	Triangulation	The study used multiple data sources including participants, paramedic service and health/government agency “grey” literature and, peer-reviewed literature
	Researcher triangulation (peer review)	Analysis was reviewed with the researcher’s supervisory team
	Member checking	Salient concepts and categories were “played back” to participants to gauge accuracy and reaction.
	Audit trail	Fortnightly meetings with supervisors to discuss theoretical,

Criteria	Technique	Rationale
		methodological and analytic choices.
		Memoing and personal diary.
		Conceptualisation of core categories was discussed with an academic staff member of QUT outside of the immediate research team.
Transferability	Purposeful sampling	Interviewing of ECPs and CPs
	Thick descriptions	Detailed contextual information provided
Dependability	Triangulation	As above
	Audit trail	As above
	Thick descriptions	Particularly of methodology
Confirmability	Audit trail	As above
	Reflexivity	Memoing and personal diary.

4.10 CONCLUSION

Chapter Four outlined the rationale for the selection of Charmazian grounded theory along with the theoretical “lens” (ontology and epistemology) used to answer the research question. In making the methodological approach to a research study explicit, the researchers can position themselves on how the results are analysed and interpreted. However, whilst a different methodological approach may produce an alternative interpretation of the results, all qualitative research must ensure the principles of rigour and quality are adhered to.

Having examined the methods behind data collection and analysis, the following chapters examine the results of the analysis. The results revealed a definable four-phase theoretical model of work role transition from traditional pre-hospital care to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Factors which either accelerated or decelerated the transition process were also distilled from the participant's responses. Each phase of transition is presented as a stand-alone chapter and includes a discussion of the results.

Chapter 5: Pre-transition Phase

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 5 presents the results of the current study and a discussion on the first phase of transition: Pre-transition. Due to the Pre-transition Phase occurring prior to the commencement of ECP/CP training, this study has not defined the Pre-transition Phase as an “active” phase of transition. That is, participants have not yet formally engaged in the transition to community paramedicine, although significant deliberation has been undertaken in deciding whether to do so. Moreover, paramedics can elect to exit the process at the Pre-transition Phase in order to pursue other career options.

The Pre-transition Phase was nevertheless a vital component of the entire transition experience. It defined the events or circumstances which participants identified as necessary prior to the active engagement in the transition process. In effect, the Pre-transition Phase allowed the participants an opportunity to rationalise the reasons for pursuing a career in community paramedicine. The data can be sifted into three sub-categories of the Pre-transition Phase: *Seeking new career options*; *Improving patient outcomes*; and *Interpreting the ECP/CP role*.

5.2 SEEKING NEW CAREER OPTIONS

All participants had completed mandatory training to become qualified paramedics (QP) in their respective jurisdictions prior to undertaking the ECP/CP training program. Unlike South Australia and Alberta, paramedics in NSW could apply for entry into the ECP program directly from the QP level. Elsewhere, paramedics had to be credentialed at the highest clinical level as either an Intensive Care Paramedic (South Australia) or Emergency Medical Technologist – Paramedic (Alberta) to enter an ECP/CP program. With most participants credentialed to the highest clinical level (n=29), the desire to be further challenged in their careers was a commonly held view. For example:

I had been an ICP for long enough and I call it the 8-year itch...I find a lot of people begin to go, 'I need to get off-road, do something else for a couple of months, get back on and then see different patients', but the work is not challenging. I didn't find being an ICP challenging any more. I needed something to do or else I was going to have to find another career. (P99)

Another participant also credentialed as an Intensive Care Paramedic, offered comparable sentiments saying, "I was getting a little bit stagnant; a little bit bored." (P37). Continuing further, other participants spoke of core paramedic work (high-acuity patients) as, "very check box. It's basically airway, breathing, circulation and everything forms into that." (P93). For other participants, boredom was not the reason for the lack of satisfaction in their traditional role. Rather, these participants were eager to expand their roles:

I liked the idea of doing more than just 'emerge'²⁵. I really enjoyed the emergency stuff and I still do, but I wanted the extended role, I wanted to be able to get out there and have more of a diagnostic and then care planning role. (P82)

Through these descriptors, participants alluded to the existence of a junctional point in their traditional paramedic careers. The limited field of career choices was a source of frustration for many. For example:

There's nowhere to go, you either go to management or you work on the street, there's no middle. Whereas in nursing there's so much lateral movement, every job there's lateral movement right, even fire, police. But paramedic, there's nothing. (P60)

Yet for other participants, the high-acuity workload of traditional ambulance work had taken its toll:

And after 13 years, I'd had enough of the street, too many dead babies, too many unfortunately. I've got kids and yes, so I was like, 'I'm done.'

²⁵ Slang term for emergency or urgent calls to patients.

I didn't want to lose my mental capacity. So, I was ready for something different. (P08)

Although less common, the decision to change work roles based on personal influences was identified, contrasting with the more "benevolent" motivations of their ECP/CP colleagues. Examples of the personal influences included, *inter alia*, the location of ECP/CP home stations closer to large metropolitan centres, family considerations and, a distain for nightshifts:

...some of the practical things were that you wouldn't have to do nights. So, it reduces my night fatigue. I don't mind admitting that was a motivation. I know they don't like hearing that. But, if that's what employees want, then you probably need to listen. But, that was one thing. (P40)

Participants also felt helpless and had difficulty adjusting to the constraints of delivering pre-hospital care to low-acuity patients whom they were not equipped or trained to handle. As one participant remarked:

...but the frustrations I had, was having a fairly high number of patients that I wasn't really allowed to do anything for because they didn't need symptom management, they needed primary care. And they just needed transport to an urgent care site or an emergency department and we didn't have the time or the tools or really the education to really do anything for those patients. (P83)

Frustrations were also felt or experienced due to having only two disposition options available following patient contact in traditional paramedic practice: transport to an emergency department or non-transport²⁶. Participants found they were unable to utilise more appropriate entry points into the healthcare system based on the individual's healthcare needs:

We take them to hospital for stuff that we should have been able to treat at home. It didn't need to go to hospital, but we had no other

²⁶ "Non-transport" is a generic term used by various paramedic services to describe a disposition option, whereby the patient refused transport by ambulance to a health facility following paramedic contact (Gray & Wardrope, 2007).

option. It was sort of like, 'Well, you need to get that sorted.' But we don't have the training for it and we don't have the skill set. So, it's either go to hospital or the patient refuses transport. (P93)

The feeling conveyed by several participants was that high-acuity work had become formulaic, routine and even mundane. Some were therefore emboldened by the prospect of a new clinical practice challenge. One participant provided this summation:

So, I guess it was the clinical challenge, and I guess that does touch very much on ECP. It was always the clinical challenge of, 'Can I get a diagnosis on this person, and what can I figure out what's wrong with them, and can I help fix them?' (P97)

The passage above embodies the sentiment amongst other participants of a willingness to move beyond their current occupational roles and provide more holistic solutions to the healthcare needs of the community. Participants were enthused by the prospect of further education in pursuit of that end. As one of the participants remarked:

So I really have always wanted more medical education, so that was a big part of it and the lure of being able to work closely with the doctors and the nurse practitioners and learn more that way. (P22)

The desire for participants to seek new career options had been inspired largely by a sense of frustration or limitation working in a traditional paramedic role. Although many participants already operated at the highest clinical levels in a traditional role, they were looking to extend their careers by pursuing new clinical practice challenges. Closely aligned with new clinical challenges was the desire to improve patient outcomes.

5.3 IMPROVING PATIENT OUTCOMES

Participants in the study conveyed a deep sense of frustration with treatment regimens in traditional pre-hospital practice, which many thought were overtly formulaic or lacked the authority to deliver more appropriate healthcare options in the community health setting. As one participant remarked: "Giving patients more options is one of the big drawcards [to

community paramedicine]. One hundred percent.” (P12). Many were also aware of the limitations in traditional care since they were unable to provide appropriate services on many occasions. As one participant said:

It was the point of pride of not caring for your patients or doing the bare minimum for patients, like a car wreck on the side of the road or a gunshot wound or something like that. And I didn't want to become that paramedic. I think I resisted that and I really enjoyed the high-acuity calls but I also - on the other side, I was really frustrated by not being able to bring that same level of commitment and hopefully ability to those other patients that weren't the acute emergencies. (P83).

In sum, the following participant showed an acute awareness of the paucity of healthcare options available to ambulance patients by saying:

It seemed like a lot of the work that I was doing was low-acuity work and I could see that there was a need to take these patients or a need to investigate them in a more thorough way, with not necessarily an automatic option to the emergency department for treatment and care. (P88)

Moreover, participants spoke of the appeal of greater autonomy in clinical practice. Participants were emboldened by the prospect of seeking solutions to patient presentations which were out of the realm of traditional pre-hospital care. One participant conveyed the sentiment of many colleagues by saying:

I felt in some ways the [ECP] program has given me permission to be the paramedic that I have always wanted to be, or perhaps that I used to be over the years, right or wrong. (P31).

Others appeared to show an affinity for lower-acuity work which traditionally has not been the core business of a paramedic service (Kennedy, 2011). The reason for this seems to be because of the opportunity afforded by the ECP/CP role to impact patient outcomes positively. A salient example was presented by one participant spending additional time with an elderly person, to better understand what services the person would require in order to prevent a future transport to the emergency department:

I really love having a little bit of extra time with my patients and it might sound a bit cheesy, but I feel like I get far more out of sitting with a geriatric patient and looking at the services they are getting or giving them care and preventing them an unnecessary hospital transport. (P55)

Other participants cited an expanded skill set as an important factor in their decision to change work roles, "You got a lot of good skills out of it that we didn't get on road [in traditional care]; dislocations, suturing..." (P12). For others, a new skill set drew positive comparisons to their current skill set:

I'm interested in the less exciting, less emergent aspects of medicine because to me it's all a challenge, it's all interesting. Showing up on day one and accessing a central line and giving antibiotics to me was as cool as doing CPR or defibrillating or whatever on a car [traditional ambulance]. (P31).

Notably however, most participants downplayed the relative importance of an expanded skill set in defining the ECP/CP role. For example, one participant contributed the following data:

But it is really not the skills so much as being able to lead the patient and help the patient get over some of the hurdles more so than anything. The monkey skills²⁷ are the smallest part of the support that you provide as part of their overall care and that piece that you play in the overall care plan is probably the bigger thing. (P33)

There appeared to be a broad consensus among the participants that an expanded skill set was not the defining hallmarks of community paramedicine. Rather, matters such as the acquisition of new knowledge, the development of clinical reasoning and gaining a holistic understanding of the healthcare system, carried greater relative importance in improving patient healthcare outcomes. In other words, the ECP/CP role was not defined simplistically in terms of an expanded clinical skill set. Participants preferred to view their role

²⁷ The participant was referring to the relative low complexity of performing clinical skills with respect to the overall care of the patient.

as a conduit in streamlining access to better healthcare. To this end, knowledge was ranked as having greater significance than the possession of tangible skills.

Thus far, this study has established that two core sub-categories exist in the Pre-transition Phase, characterised by the paramedic working in a traditional role seeking a means to satisfy unmet “wants”. In essence, paramedics were searching for new career options and a means to improve patient outcomes. A third sub-category, *Interpreting the ECP/CP role*, was the key that lead the paramedic into the field of community paramedicine.

5.4 INTERPRETING THE ECP/CP ROLE

A third sub-category in the Pre-transition Phase was the perception or prior understanding that the participants have of the ECP/CP role. These perceptions provide the link between the other two sub-categories and the participant’s entry into an ECP/CP program (Figure 5.1). Participants utilised their perceptions of the ECP/CP role in deciding whether their personal and professional needs could be met through a community paramedicine career path. If those needs could not be met, participants had the option to exit the Pre-transition Phase at this point and follow other career options in traditional paramedicine or elsewhere.

Figure 5.1 The Pre-transition Phase

A general understanding of what the ECP/CP role entailed was commonly reported, although most often specific information was lacking. The lack of detail was particularly relevant to participants who entered their respective programs early after the programs were introduced. As one participant reflected:

I had a vague idea that we would be able to achieve more and spend more time with patients. I knew it was going to be somewhat low-acuity. I knew that it would be somewhat akin to a nurse practitioner in some shape or form or description. We didn't know exactly what shape it would take but that was intriguing. (P88)

For others, the community paramedicine model resonated with them as a means of advancing the profession. One participant spoke of "realising that the profession is going somewhere and we get to be a part of it." (P33). Another participant extended the sentiment further to include the future direction of paramedic services:

Ambulance services were evolving into a 'treat and leave at home' type model. I thought we had to go, we couldn't keep doing what we were doing. So, ideologically I was in favour of it anyway. So, I was excited as part of being in the program to expand the ambulance service. (P05)

Finally, having a nursing background provided an area of theoretical interest in several areas of transition. The data suggested paramedics who have had previous experience working within the larger healthcare system were more amenable to working within community paramedicine. The data suggested paramedics who are qualified nurses, possess a more matured, whole-of-health understanding, compared to their non-nursing paramedic colleagues:

Yes, and I think that it helps give you a broader understanding, or an awareness I guess. You can understand it, but until you do more of like your nursing basics and principles of your determinants of health, understanding how the systems work and how people interact with them and the situations are set up, I think nursing does a better job of that than paramedicine does. So, I don't think it's a detriment to do

schooling. I wouldn't say you have to do it to be able to do our [ECP] job for sure, but you do gain from it. (P72)

For some former nurses, the prospect of working in an ECP/CP role provided the ability to continue working in community health without the perceived disadvantages of traditional nursing. Some of those disadvantages included large patient numbers and constraints on autonomous decision making:

So one of the huge things was you were always under staffed. Lots of showers, lots of bum wiping, lots of hands on care. Which is nice. However, not what I was looking for. Also, the lack of autonomy relating to nursing. Everything has to be signed off. Or if something happened or the patient farted you had to see a doctor and get reviewed yadda, yadda, yadda. As opposed to paramedics where you have to draw up a kit and you're free to roam. (P12)

5.5 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The data analysis revealed three sub-categories which collectively described the conditions, circumstances and events required for a traditional care paramedic to transition to a role in community paramedicine. Seeking a new career challenge and improving patient outcomes shared similar origins; a deep sense of frustration due to an inability to provide better healthcare options to patients. The third sub-category (Interpreting the ECP/CP role), provided the link between the two other sub-categories and guided the participant towards a career path in community paramedicine. For some participants, the call to community paramedicine was amplified by their previous nursing experiences. The narrative now turns to discuss the key results related to the primary research question, *"How do paramedics transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine?"*

5.6 DISCUSSION OF THE PRE-TRANSITION PHASE

This study found that the process of transition from traditional care paramedic to a specialist role in community paramedicine encompassed four phases. The first of these phases, Pre-transition, was initiated by participants

identifying two unmet professional “needs”: seeking new career options and improving patient outcomes. Subsequently, the reasons for either pursuing a career in community paramedicine or choosing other career options were rationalised through the participant’s perceptions of the ECP/CP role. In simple terms, the Pre-transition Phase was tantamount to a *decision-making* phase for participants. Consequently, Pre-transition was deemed a “non-active” phase of transition as the participant had not formally engaged in the transition process.

Whilst the literature review established a growing corpus of knowledge related to the transition of student paramedics into the profession (Devenish, et al., 2016; Huot, 2013; Kennedy, et al., 2015), and a wider selection in cognate health professions such as nursing (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016; Boychuk Duchscher, 2008; Phillips, Esterman, Smith, & Kenny, 2013), the relative dearth of information regarding transition to specialist roles in paramedicine is stark. Nevertheless, McFarlane (2010) in a Master’s thesis, briefly examined the factors paramedics considered for entering and exiting Intensive Care Paramedic (ICP) practice. The findings are relevant to this study, as the role of ICP can be considered a parallel, specialist clinical stream within paramedicine (Paramedics Australasia, 2009). Moreover, the study has some local relevance as it was conducted within an Australian paramedic jurisdiction.

Elements of the McFarlane’s (2010) findings are congruent with the Pre-transition sub-category *Improving patient outcomes*. For instance, both groups of participants indicated that an integral reason for articulation to specialist practice, was the desire to improve patient outcomes with a commensurate increase in the scope of practice. Indeed, participants in the current study related improving patient outcomes with altruistic personal qualities. However, gaining a clearer understanding of why experienced clinicians choose to articulate to specialist practice in the wider literature remains elusive. For instance, this study’s literature review established that the closest analogy of transition to community paramedicine in a related health field was that of nurse practitioner. Despite the work of notable authors in the field of nurse practitioner role transition (Barnes, 2015; Brown & Olshansky, 1997; Glen &

Waddington, 1998), most literature on this subject is focused on the phases of nurse practitioner role transition aligned to the “active” phases of transition in the current study (Barton, 2007b; Heitz, et al., 2004; Poronsky, 2013; Spoelstra & Robbins, 2010).

It may be noted that one study of transition from neonatal nurse to advanced neonatal nurse practitioner (Spinks, 2009) drew similarities to the current study in areas such as the desire to improve the knowledge base, the acquisition of new skills, and the provision of a more holistic level of care to the patient. The semblance between results may suggest a level of dissatisfaction within “base-level” practitioner roles whereby clinicians are intrinsically motivated to pursue roles with an expanded scope of practice. The results also suggest advanced practitioners are likely to have a demonstrable career history of clinical professional development.

The findings of the Pre-transition Phase in the current study are therefore noteworthy, as few studies have explicitly examined the rationale for the articulation of an experienced practitioner to an advanced practice role. Perhaps more significantly, no other study to date has been identified that specifically discusses the factors impacting the decision-making processes of experienced clinicians moving from one clinical specialist stream to a *second* clinical specialist stream. Comparable discussions in the transition of experienced clinicians moving to academic roles have been highlighted previously in both the paramedicine (Munro, O'Meara, & Kenny, 2017) and nursing (Anderson, 2009; Manning & Neville, 2009) literature. However, with the current study contributing unique aspects on clinical work role transition. One such unique aspect is the possible existence of a *junctional point* in a traditional paramedic career.

The junctional point is the proposed theoretical crossroads in the clinical career trajectory of paramedics who qualify at the highest clinical level, yet elect to remain in a point-of-care role. The existence of the junctional point is alluded through descriptors in the data of the paramedic's previous work role in traditional paramedicine such as *stagnation, boredom, formulaic, routine*

and *mundane*. The descriptors emphasised the deep sense of frustration felt by paramedics because of their inability to deliver more holistic healthcare options to patients. In spite of the fact that there are other avenues for exploring clinical challenges in paramedicine such as retrieval paramedic²⁸ and consultant paramedic²⁹ (College of Paramedics, 2015), a change of work role would also be required.

The proposed existence of a junctional point in a paramedic's clinical career trajectory has not been widely validated previously in the paramedicine and cognate health literature. For instance, a recent systematic review of 26 papers examining the work role transition of both novice and experienced nurses made no reference to the factors impacting the decision to engage in work role transition. (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016). In essence, therefore, the contribution of this original research is to postulate a preliminary definition of the junctional point in a paramedic's clinical career. The junctional point may be defined as the point at which two Pre-transition categories intersect, to wit: (i) the search for new career options and (ii) desire to improve patient outcomes. In other disciplines such as that of business and psychology, the existence of a career junctional point can also be inferred (Lusty, 2013). However, the work role of a paramedic is different in that it has distinctive qualities which may render the translation of findings from other disciplines problematic (Malterud, 2001b). Further longitudinal studies are therefore required to better explore the transition experience within the paramedic domain in more detail.

Nevertheless, the results of the study yielded an unexpected finding: seven non-ICP participants had reached their career junctional points for reasons similar to those of their more experienced ICP colleagues. The finding was unexpected as the non-ICP participants had not yet reached the pinnacle

²⁸ A Retrieval Paramedic is an advanced clinical practitioner who specialises in the transfer of critically unwell patients to a specialist receiving facility (Paramedics Australasia, 2009).

²⁹ A Consultant Paramedic oversees the clinical advancement and governance of the prehospital system in which they work (Colbeck, 2014).

of their clinical careers, yet shared similar frustrations in their work roles. The reason for this result may reside in the participants sharing a common service delivery ethos or philosophy, as distinct from paramedics practicing within a traditional paramedic role. In other words, participants in the current study exhibited an appreciable understanding of improving patient outcomes via pathways other than the emergency department.

The contrasting philosophies of care between community paramedicine and traditional paramedicine are well known (Choi, et al., 2016; Long, 2016; O'Meara, et al., 2016). In determining the likely suitability of a candidate for an ECP/CP role, the findings of the current study emphasise the importance of the alignment in an ECP/CP candidate's service delivery views with the service delivery philosophy which underscores community paramedicine. Ideally, the more suitable candidate should possess a broader understanding of primary healthcare issues and the emerging role paramedics can play in a patient's trajectory through the healthcare system.

Importantly, participants with a nursing background displayed a broader understanding of primary healthcare issues. This is important since it assists in navigating a patient through a healthcare system recognised as complex (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2015). The results are consistent with the conclusions of Williams (2012) who followed five nurses who changed careers to become paramedics. Williams noted that a broader understanding of the healthcare system helped the paramedics to formulate other patient disposition decisions besides hospital admission. Furthermore, since a broad understanding of the healthcare system is a core foundation on which community paramedicine programs are built (Kizer, et al., 2013), nursing experience would appear to complement the transition to community paramedicine. Although data from the current study suggested a nursing background was not an essential prerequisite for successful transition, it appears, nevertheless, that participants with nursing experience begin the transition to community paramedicine in a more advanced position than their non-nursing colleagues, particularly in the area of mastering skills.

5.7 CONCLUSION

Chapter 5 examined the first phase of paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Pre-transition involved a “decision-making” phase whereby paramedics sought options to satisfy two career “wants”: seeking new career options and improving patient outcomes. The nexus between career options and patient outcomes represented a junctional point in the paramedic’s career. Subsequently, career decisions were rationalised through perceptions of the ECP/CP role.

Although poorly studied in both the paramedicine and nursing literature, the relative significance of the Pre-transition Phase to the overall transition experience should not be undervalued. For instance, the degree of uniformity between the paramedic’s own service delivery philosophies and that of the community paramedicine paradigm, may provide some insights as to the suitability of an ECP/CP candidate. Additionally, other factors including a background in clinical professional development and nursing experience, may also be incorporated as a workforce recruitment tool for community paramedicine programs. Finally, as this study is the first of its kind to qualitatively examine the process of transition from one specialist clinical stream to another, further longitudinal studies are required to better illuminate the decision-making processes in the Pre-transition Phase.

Chapter 6: Early Phase – The Novice Practitioner

6.1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter *Pre-transition Phase*, the events and conditions necessary to engage in the transition process were identified and discussed. Chapter 6 explores the first active phase of transition whereby paramedics formally engage in the process of transition to community paramedicine - *The Early Phase*. The phase began with an in-house specialist training course in community paramedicine (see Chapter 1 for further information) and continues until the participant subjectively reported a sense of “competence” in the new role. This chapter presents the unique aspects of the Early Phase of transition, followed by analysis within the context of the four core categories of transition. A discussion of the analysis will continue, then concluding remarks presented.

6.2 UNIQUE ASPECTS OF THE EARLY PHASE

For most participants, the Early Phase was a challenging time. Reinforced by the prior perceptions of the ECP/CP role, many participants exhibited a heightened awareness of the philosophical shift in service delivery from traditional paramedicine to a more holistic model of care in community paramedicine:

We give kind of medical care and just more transport than anything, when you work on the [traditional care] ambulance. And now I'm doing full patient care and your perspective is very different. So the training was a huge perception, it made a huge perception shift. (P22)

A participant from another paramedic service concurred with the sentiments above, emphasising that the initial training program was integral to the philosophical shift in perception:

I described it when we graduated from the college [initial training], I think I stood up in front of everyone and described it as just a gold-

mine of information...It was a paradigm shift where we were able to rethink and restructure the way we interacted with patients in a completely new way. (P88)

Moreover, the magnitude of the transition to community paramedicine was not lost on others given the early realisation that, "you are going from being an expert clinician in the ambulance world, to being a novice community paramedic." (P31). The view was expressed that being a novice practitioner in community paramedicine was like being a probationer (trainee paramedic) again, "Yes, every job. Every job for the first few months was like being a probationer." (P16). For other participants, it was more fitting to describe their experience of the Early Phase by drawing analogies to the transition from Qualified Paramedic to Intensive Care Paramedic:

So, the first stage for me was nervousness, everything is new, I don't know if I can do this, but I'm going to do it anyway because I've got the training, and I can remember it was exactly like this as an ICP... (P41)

Notably, a myriad of emotions experienced by novice ECPs/CPs were chiefly negative with nervousness, stress, isolation and anxiety being the most commonly reported. Some claimed the nervousness was associated with the level of critical thinking required:

We were all very nervous about going to patients, not the catheters, not that sort of stuff, but I can remember going to my first pneumonia patient and stopping on the way to have a quick look back through my notes, and differentiating viral and bacterial [pneumonia] and thinking about the antibiotics that might be used, and how do I do that assessment and all those sort of things. So it was quite nerve wracking. (P82)

Others were emotionally fraught due to their limited experience in performing certain clinical skills:

Quite nervous. Yeah, quite nervous. So my first suture job, you know, very nervous. My first catheter job, very nervous. But you're just basically thrown in the deep end and you just do the best you can.
(*laughing*) (P68)

Finally, additional stressors were evident in relation to relatively new ECP/CP programs. In the following passage, the anxiety and concern for a new Community Paramedic program failing is highlighted:

Probably some fear that it [the CP program] wasn't going to work because it was so new...We were only on the supportive living sites, so you could go a day and not have a call and then you're like, 'If this doesn't work, that means I've got to back to the street, and that's not what I want to do.' (P08)

The Early Phase was characterised by the first active engagement of paramedics in the transition process to community paramedicine. Four core categories permeated each active phase of the transition experience, with each of the categories culminating in an ancillary marker of transition. That is, the evolution of each core category could be tracked through the Early, Middle and Late Phases of transition, with the end-point of each core category defined by an ancillary marker of transition. The combination of the four ancillary markers of transition condensed to a single end-point of transition, discussed in more detail in Chapter 8 – Late Phase. The following four sections (6.3 – 6.6) present each of the four core categories within the context of the Early Phase of transition.

6.3 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The outcomes of the analysis revealed that support was a significant factor throughout the transition experience. These evolving support networks, described as a *community of practice* (Li et al., 2009), allowed paramedics, nurses, GPs and other healthcare professionals, to interact, share knowledge and collaboratively engage with one another, with the eventual objective of improving patient outcomes. The first iteration of a community of practice came into being during the Early Phase of the transition process, and emerged

primarily amongst the ECP/CP cohort during the initial training course. Moreover, the unique cultural milieu of the ECP/CP programs that allowed a community of practice to flourish was not left to chance. Participants speculated that they were recruited for their vision to see the role succeed:

Yes, well it's because you're a small group, especially at the beginning, none of us knew what we were doing. We'd all come from different areas and it was like, 'To make this work, we've all got to work together and support each other and help each other.' (P08)

For others, the community of practice developed from modest beginnings - trainee ECPs living together for the duration of the course:

So I would bounce it off them and they would bounce off me for some of the background information, but they were really good at just doing the practical assessment so they helped me a lot. So we all helped each other. Being all together really helps I think. (P16)

Support was thus one of the defining features of the early rendition of a community of practice. Of particular interest was the finding that peer support crossed traditional clinical hierarchical boundaries (Reynolds, 2008). For example, a Qualified Paramedic (non-ICP) with nursing experience was speaking about lending support to a more senior ICP:

So it was a great group. We kind of helped each other out. The ICPs we found would ask us how to do stuff or [ask] 'can we practice with you' and so we were all integrating practice with each other and we would test each other out and they would be like, 'Can you watch me do my sterile fields, just set up a catheter?' 'Yes okay.' (P17)

In addition, informal support networks provided a safety net for the novice practitioner. The safety net also conceptually introduced the need for *reassurance and validation* from other members of the ECP/CP cohort, to confirm clinical findings and disposition options:

Generally, you know what you are thinking and the path you want to go down. Sometimes you just need a little bit of reassurance to make sure that you are not alone in your thought process and the other

Extended Care Paramedics would do the same. Once you have got that reassurance, you are comfortable to go down that pathway. (P55)

Seeking reassurance and validation from one's cohort, was utilised as a vehicle to move in the direction of work role "comfort/confidence". Comfort/confidence was distilled from the data as the participant's subjective rendering of the end-point of the transition experience (explained in greater detail in Chapter 8 – The Late Phase of transition). The connection between reassurance and comfort was depicted by one participant in the following passage:

I found with my transition to EMS [operational paramedic] from 'student-land', it was kind of, 'You go, you deal with it, just make it happen, make it work.' Versus the transition to community paramedicine, I found at least within our team, I can't speak for any others, but they've been extremely supportive and I find that's what's really needed to transition appropriately. Being able to phone a friend and say, 'I haven't seen this before, can you give me tips on this' or 'What would you recommend doing?' That's helped a lot. (P72)

Whilst the early framework of a community of practice relied on paramedic-to-paramedic collaboration, the significance of developing relationships with other healthcare professionals (OHCPs) such as community nurses and GPs, was not lost on the ECPs/CPs. On reflection, one participant argued relationships with OHCPs were an integral part of the transition process:

I think one of the big things in becoming a successful ECP or transitioned ECP, if that is what you want to say in terms of confidence and competence, is having a strong support network of allied professionals. If you didn't have them, if you just simply worked with your initial 10-week training and the support of your staff at station, you wouldn't be anywhere near as comfortable in the role. (P49)

As the transition process continued, the focus drifted towards the addition of an *external* community of practice. That is, the inclusion of OHCPs to complement the existing "in-house" framework, although experiences of

collaboration varied markedly across the study sites. Moreover, the maturing community of practice framework was continually influenced by each of the other core categories of transition and thus highlighted the intricate complexities of relationships between core categories. The evolution of the community of practice is discussed in greater detail in the Middle and Late Phases of transition.

6.4 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

Novice ECPs/CPs faced significant challenges along the transition process, including the changing organisational and cultural landscape in their respective services. Participants had often emerged from a workplace culture in the traditional ambulance setting that was monotonic. Examples included, “On an ambulance, it’s a very – I hate to use the word ‘dog eat dog’. You don’t want to show vulnerability.” (P72); “We have a reputation of eating our own young as students” (P31); and:

There’s still a culture, and maybe this applies to all ambulance services, you know, doing the wrong thing, screwing up, fucking up, is not viewed as a growth thing, as much as management would try and paint that picture. We’re a no-blame culture etc., etc., but everyone you would ask would have sufficient examples of where that hasn’t been the case, when one of their colleagues, or themselves have done something wrong. (P41)

In contrast, the culture within ECP/CP programs appeared more supportive, particularly in terms of attitudes towards learning and clinical development. When discussing how the cultural change occurred, one participant suggested it was the original cohorts of ECPs who had laid the cultural foundations for subsequent paramedics entering the program:

And I think they [original cohorts] were the champions in terms of that culture. Because they went through it, and the next group didn’t have to go through that. So, they were supported through this culture of discussing [eg. collaborative learning] because it’s all new to them. It’s a new program. They’ve only been ICPs. They’ve only ever taken people to hospital. So, I think that helped create that culture where we

talk about jobs freely. As compared to 'ICP-land', where you only talk about the sexy jobs that went well. (P41)

Unlike the previous discussion however, another participant proposed that the cultural milieu within ECP/CP programs was set by paramedics with prior nursing or tertiary qualifications:

So, I think the vast majority of ECPs have either got a Bachelor of Paramedicine, and so they're aware of continuing education and reflective practice. Or, they're nurses. And so, they've already got that drive to continue education. They've already got that knowledge of evidence-based nursing, and they want to practice evidence-based nursing. And so, I think those people then create that [culture]. The culture's already there. (P97)

During the Early Phase, paramedics were first exposed to a changed workplace culture via the concept of *investment* in their respective programs. Analysis suggested a participant's willingness to invest in their own program was linked to developing motivation, and later to confidence – a key marker to the end-point of transition:

You're actually hitting something really important. My investment in getting interested in the program, and wanting to develop and do more because, it's very easy to do the course, if you like, to be an ECP. And then, if that motivation is not there, what happens is, because we're dispatching ourselves, for example, you'll find people who'll lose confidence in the complex. And I say 'complex' as compared to maybe doing a catheter change, for example. (P41)

Furthermore, a proposed willingness to invest in ECP/CP programs was positively associated with a supportive ECP/CP program management structure. The following passage suggested the level of support within the ECP/CP program was not common in a traditional role:

...we'll have the monthly team meetings and we'll say, 'Okay, this is a problem', and you'll come up with ideas, 'Well what if we tried this?' And it could be a mixture of three people's ideas that come into one decision, but they actually implement it. And you're like, 'Holy cow!

They've listened to me.' So when you go out to work and you're doing something that you've brought to the table if you like, and you know it's improving patient care or it's making a CP's life easier, you're just like, 'Wow!' (P08)

*The changed perception of clinical governance*³⁰ as distinct from traditional care, was another significant instigation during the Early Phase of transition. With respect to ECPs/CPs, clinical governance had a two-fold purpose. First, to collect data in the official reporting on the quality and safety of practice and second, to enable ECPs/CPs to utilise reflective practice in novel ways:

I think, and this is where the misconception of clinical audit can be sometimes, because it used to be that a clinical audit was about a chance to say, 'How good am I? I did this,' and everyone goes, 'Oh, yes, aren't you fantastic? You did that.' That's not the whole purpose of clinical audit, and reflective practice. (P03)

The following participant provided a model for the novel use of reflective practice. They regarded call-backs³¹ as an educational tool, rather than merely a mandatory reporting task:

I have learned more from call-backs I think in that first couple of years than I had in all my years on the job. Just having that follow through, that continuity of care. It's not just 20 minutes and see you later and I have no idea really. Unless you follow up on your more interesting cases, which you do, but time constraints and all that, you can't follow everybody. But love the call-back thing as an education tool for ECPs, especially new ECPs finding their way and getting a feel what happens in this case, what happened to that knee injury, what happened to that guy with the ankle, what happened to that guy with the sutures and you get that feedback and it becomes your internal library. You can

³⁰ Clinical governance is a systematic approach to monitoring and supporting appropriate, safe and quality clinical practice (Ambulance Service of NSW, 2011).

³¹ Call-back is a clinical governance activity to contact the patient following an ECP/CP encounter, primarily to ascertain the patient's healthcare outcome and if any adverse events were encountered.

put it all together and it all adds up to experience and it guides your practice. (P16)

Crucially, clinical governance directly contributed to the ECP's/CP's pursuit of *confidence through validation* in the Early Phase of transition:

So [through clinical governance] you find out if the patient called triple zero again. If the patient got themselves to an ED or to the GP, was it advised by the ECP to do that? How they felt five, six, seven days afterwards. So that helps - that helps to find out that you did the right job on a patient, that you chose the right pathway. And it gives you confidence. (P68)

Testament to the porous nature of the core categories, *validation* was seen conceptually elsewhere in the transition experience, such as *Engaging in a Community of Practice*. Validation was evident in multiple areas as it was a key driver in achieving work role confidence. For participants, attaining a sense of work role confidence was of utmost importance as it constituted a key indicator for success in transition. (The relevance of work role confidence/comfort to the transition experience will be discussed in greater detail in Chapter 7 – Late Phase).

Finally, ECPs/CPs had to contend with the negative perceptions traditional care paramedics and OHCPs had of their roles. The reason appeared largely rooted in a lack of understanding and preconceived biases regarding community paramedicine. For example, participants reported that they were initially perceived as a “threat” by OHCPs, such as general practitioners, until education about the ECP/CP role filtered through:

I think other health care providers have a lot of respect for us. Some feel threatened by what we do, mainly, you know, we find with GPs that work in the community. Some of them feel threatened by our role, and once they sort of learn that we are here to work with them, not instead of them, they are very supportive of what we do. (P03)

Additionally, within the paramedic service community, the negative perceptions of traditional care paramedics have been manifested in derogatory references to ECP/CP clinical skills:

...but so many of the non-ECP [traditional care] paramedics think of us as just as 'mobile catheter vans', that's all that we do. Some people may slight you because they're a friend, and they know they'll get a rise out of it. Some people truly believe that's all we do. So, paramedics-wise, that's all we do. (P97)

For some, being undervalued by colleagues had a negative effect and caused them to pause and consider whether a change in work roles was appropriate:

If I walk out the front of headquarters today someone has dropped dead and I pull out my monitor and defibrillate them. Everyone says, 'Well you are a good ICP you have done that really well.' But if I go to an old bloke that lives in his home by himself with urinary retention and I change his catheter, that's not, in paramedic's eyes, that is not core ambulance business and that is not a particularly glamorous day at work. Now I like it and that is why I chose this job, but it makes you sort of have that thought of 'Am I doing the right thing as I change my role from emergency ICP to ECP?' (P77)

Consequently, feeling undervalued by others prompted ECPs/CPs to educate OHCPs and traditional care paramedics of the niche ECPs/CPs could fill in the patient's healthcare journey. The effect that organisational and cultural changes on the transition experience as it evolves in time will be examined in the subsequent chapters.

To this point, Chapter 6 has examined two of the four core categories of transition: *Engaging in a Community of Practice* and *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change*. This chapter now turns to examine the remaining two core categories: *Developing Critical Thinking* and *Mastering Skills*, and their relevance to the Early Phase of transition.

6.5 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

Critical thinking infers purposeful and informed reasoning, although the concept is not exclusively applied to the clinical setting (Alfaro-LeFevre, 2009). While clinical reasoning is an integral component of the ECP/CP work role, it is more apt to describe the wider skills required to work in the dynamic community paramedicine environment as critical thinking. In the words of one participant, community paramedicine required a different mindset from traditional paramedicine, along with an ability to “think outside the box”:

Like a urinary tract infection - I can start an IV [put a small needle into a vein], I can give a little fluid but I don't carry antibiotics in the ambulance. It's totally different now, the mindset, I'm not necessarily looking how can I spend as least time as possible on this call and get them to hospital. I am really forced to think outside the box because that is why I'm here and say, 'Okay what can I do to make this patient healthier and happy and not have to go to the ER?' (P31)

Critical thinking therefore involved a change of mindset, i.e., a change in understanding that the patient exists within a broader continuum of care. To achieve this change in mindset, trainee ECPs/CPs were encouraged to adopt contemporary adult learning principles during the initial training course. These principles accessed the motivation, readiness and previous learning experiences of the participants to drive the learning. It is important to note however, that the development of learning skills continued across multiple phases of transition.

The duration of initial training for ECPs/CPs lasted between two weeks and 10 weeks, and consisted of time in both classes and clinical placement. After the initial training period, participants were partnered with an experienced ECP/CP mentor for generally two weeks or less in an operational capacity, before becoming an autonomously practicing Extended Care Paramedic or Community Paramedic. Depending on local policies, paramedics were then expected to demonstrate continued learning through several

modalities, such as continued classroom training, clinical placements and case reviews.

For most participants, the initial training course was viewed favourably as it contrasted markedly with previous in-house paramedic training they had experienced, such as the Intensive Care Paramedic (ICP) course. The ICP course appeared more aligned with the static transmission of information in contrast to the ECP course, where self-directed and problem-based learning were prominent. When asked about the ECP course, one participant emphatically stated, "Beats the [traditional] ambulance course by a hundred-fold." (P15). Other participants expressed similar sentiments when comparing the ECP course with traditional paramedic courses:

ICP, there's an expectation that you didn't want to go in not knowing anything new. So when you got there and sat down for a lecture, you wanted to know everything that was coming out of the guy's mouth. You didn't have time. Same with skills. You want to learn your skills back to front and pharmacology back to front. Whereas ECP was, they gave you some pre-course reading which was nice. But you go in, I wouldn't say with an empty slate, but you go in and come out prepared and ready. (P12)

Another participant confirmed the above remarks while also elucidating on the essence of what many participants perceived as the difference between traditional paramedic and ECP/CP courses, "It's not rote learning...You're not spitting out verbatim protocols. It's completely different." (P12). Whether this view was shared by all participants is questionable. One participant suggested that some of their ICP colleagues were challenged during the ECP course by an absence of specific treatment protocols to follow:

I think the ICPs that were in our course were a bit more old school where everything was so black and white. So they really just couldn't grasp the grey area that is ECPs. They wanted a really definitive answer for a patient that you just can't define with so many co-morbidities and you really have to judge each case upon its merit as opposed to just following a protocol. (P55)

The supposition above was not isolated. Another participant observed that working in community paramedicine with its myriad of treatment options, was a “grey” area not to the liking of all paramedics:

[ECP] is very grey. It is something I think that the ambulance service here sometimes has trouble dealing with is just how grey the ECP world is. We had a couple of people actually came in and they are very experienced ICPs and very clever people, way cleverer than me, and they did not stay. It was not because they could not do the knowledge, it was not because they could not do the skills, it was because it was just too vague and they were not comfortable with the vagueness.
(P82)

However, the application of contemporary adult learning principles in the development of critical thinking skills was welcomed. Examples of novel learning included a student-focused approach to case-based learning, reflective practices and assessments via an OSCE³² format:

And the whole idea of OSCEs - never experienced anything like that before in education. And for me, I held my hand up a lot. For me, that was fantastic. It was perfect for me, the best way of learning. This is what ECP's about. But, a lot of ICP [the Intensive Care Paramedic course], we're just sitting in lectures. (P15)

This was not to say that critical thinking skills have been disregarded in traditional paramedic courses. Rather, the development of critical thinking skills has been emphasised in ECP/CP training to better reflect the service delivery role in community paramedicine. For this reason, the relative importance of learning new clinical skills such as suturing was contrasted with the acquisition of new knowledge, like conducting a thorough patient assessment:

Paramedics learn a systematic approach to patient assessments and treatments that enables them to find a confident flow in a sense. That

³² OSCE – Objective structured clinical examination is a clinical or practical assessment that is focused more on what the student can do, rather than what they know (Harden, 1988).

confidence grows into an ability to be an independent critical thinker. This is magnified in Community Paramedics. Exceptional critical thinking enables and supports patient care, in collaboration/consultation with a physician, and assists us in anticipating what, when and why a care plan should or could be executed. (P33)

A second participant juxtaposes the relative importance of skills and knowledge in community paramedicine:

Yes. It's definitely a knowledge-based application process. Why does every paramedic put a tube in a throat? It's not the skill that's particularly hard, it's telling which person to put it in. It's the same with most of what we do. It's not particularly hard skill-wise. Sewing someone up is not hard. Any monkey can be taught to do it. It's just knowing which ones to do. Who's supposed to stay at home? (P04)

During the Early Phase, some participants also suggested it was advantageous to have a nursing background for the development of critical thinking skills. The principal reason appears to be because of a better understanding of the patient's trajectory through the healthcare system. With this understanding, those with a nursing background reported an improved contextualisation of the patient's condition and were therefore better able to rationalise disposition options for the patient. An ECP with prior nursing experience offered:

Yes, and I think that it [nursing] helps give you a broader understanding, or an awareness I guess. You can understand it, but until you do more of like your nursing basics and principles of your determinants of health, understanding how the systems work and how people interact with them and the situations are set up, I think nursing does a better job of that than paramedicine does. (P72)

Participants were additionally appreciative of the high standard of lecturers and preceptors available to them during the Early Phase. The supporting commentary included: "Highly qualified educators. Most of the sessions were run by either doctors, clinical nursing consultants, or very, very

good quality lectures that we got. Yeah, outstanding.” (P68) Notably, one participant drew an association between expert tuition and confidence - a key indicator of transition: “...even for our own mindsets, I think, and made us a little bit more confident knowing that we were taught by experts...” (P23) Moreover, the attitude of the lecturers and the general culture fostered within the course, appeared to be supportive:

I think [the ECP course was better than a traditional ambulance course] because you had doctors, professors, registrars, and people who are specialists in their field coming in. That was part of it. It’s not a blame culture, it’s a supporting culture. It’s not hammered into you, ‘You must get this’. If you don’t get it, that’s fine. Sit down and work it out. (P15)

Finally, the role of preceptor (mentor), during the on-road supervised training period³³, was highly valued by trainee ECPs/CPs in developing confidence. However, the analysis showed that paramedics perceived the training received to be manifestly brief. The following excerpt argues the need for a longer preceptorship to facilitate a sense of comfort:

...definitely having a mentor for longer, like ICP. [An ECP colleague] had two or three weeks, and she was pretty comfortable. I still don’t think that’s enough. And I think, I know it’s hard to do, but having someone supervise every shift you do before you do it, come and see you do it. For me, the hardest part when you’re saying ‘do I feel comfortable with my job’, the hardest part for me was suturing. Because, no one’s ever seen me do it. I’d never practiced on a real person. Here I am, out in the back of Bourke, on a farm with a needle, going, ‘Shit!’ (P15)

For others, the role of the preceptor played a more prominent role in facilitating the development of critical thinking skills:

³³ Trainees were mentored in the community with a qualified ECP/CP for between two and four weeks following classroom training, with one jurisdiction allowing a longer period at the paramedic’s request.

I think, having good mentors makes a massive difference. When you've got really experienced ECPs who have been there, done that, who've problem solved. There are patients you might go to as a novice and you don't think of an option. Because I guess you're trying to get your head out of ED and into what's best for this patient, and there might be options available that you hadn't even thought of, just because you haven't got that experience yet. (P97)

Preceptorship therefore had a crucial role in the development of ECP/CP work role confidence. The role of preceptor morphed throughout the transition process from principally lending instruction to novice practitioners in the Early Phase, through to affirmation of competence in the Late Phase. Furthermore, preceptors made a significant contribution to the mastery of skills by new trainees.

6.6 MASTERING SKILLS

The work role of an ECP/CP required the acquisition of new skills. Analysis revealed that there were two groups of skill sets to be acquired: clinical skills and operational skills. Importantly, ECPs/CPs ostensibly placed greater significance on the acquisition of clinical skills rather than operational skills. Whilst arguably both skills sets are integral to the role, the greater focus on clinical skills acquisition appeared to be due to role perception. ECPs/CPs viewed their role principally in terms of improving patient clinical outcomes, and thus emphasised clinical skill acquisition over operational skills in the transition process.

Clinical skills were specific to the clinical management of a patient in a community paramedicine setting and formed part of an extended scope of practice (Queensland Health, 2014). Examples of ECP/CP clinical skills included:

- suturing
- reducing dislocations
- catheterisation

- pathology sampling
- systems assessments (cardiovascular, respiratory etc.)
- palliative assessment.

ECP/CP trainees were introduced to clinical skills during the didactic component of their training. However, for most participants, consolidation of learning began during clinical placements and continued throughout the Middle and Late Phases of transition. Clinical placements, lasting up to two weeks in duration, were conducted in various clinical settings including, hospitals (wards and emergency departments), in the community with nurse practitioners/community nurses and palliative care facilities. From a learning perspective, the general consensus amongst the participants was very favourable:

But, the clinical placements themselves, the ideas were great. We got a good range. We went out with community wound care nurses, so we saw how 'the professionals' as it were, the experts at wound care management, went about their job. Hyperbaric therapy, most hyperbaric therapy is about diabetic wound care management. We were there. We had continence clinics with our catheterised patients. Fracture clinics for back slabbing, and plasters, and such. So, the clinical placements that we got were really great, but it just relies on you being lucky on the day to see a whole lot. (P97)

The above passage also enunciated concerns other participants had of the sporadic nature of "suitable" (ECP-specific) work during clinical placements:

I spent a couple of days in general ED, and one of those days, nothing happened. Just luck of the draw. Nothing suitable came through the door. But, the other day I had there was good. Neurology was fantastic. Riding with the wound [care] nurses was fantastic. (P15)

The Early Phase of transition was predominantly a time of absorbing instruction on skills (via classroom and clinical placement) and the early engagement of consolidation (via clinical placement and autonomous

practice). Consolidation through skill repetition featured more prominently in the next phase of transition (Middle Phase). Although for some participants with a nursing background, the process of skill consolidation had already been initiated:

I think coming in to ECP, I was very nervous and scared feeling under-prepared. But as we started to do some of the skills that I had already learnt through the nursing degree and through nursing, I realised that they were my strong points and so that gave me confidence in other things. If I can do this, I can do that. It might be a bit harder, but they are all ECP skills. (P17)

Alongside clinical skills, operational (non-clinical) skills was the second grouping of skills within the core category. Operational skills encompassed the non-clinical skills required to effectively operate as an ECP/CP. Many of the skills related to the use of information technology such as the use of medical databases, shared drives and smartphones. Most participants were adept at mastering competency in operational skills and did not require a significant investment in time nor resources. However, there was one operational skill that proved to be the exception – *working as a single responder*.

A single responder was a paramedic working on his or her own, in a vehicle generally not equipped with a stretcher for patient transport. However, the vehicle was stocked with medical equipment commensurate with the paramedic's scope of practice. All three research sites utilised single responders, though one significant variation existed. The ECP model of care, as operated in SA Ambulance Service and NSW Ambulance, required ECPs to be available also for high-acuity (urgent) medical and traumatic cases. Consequently, ECPs worked from clearly identifiable emergency service vehicles equipped with emergency warning lights and sirens. In contrast, CPs in Alberta did not work in "marked-up" vehicles nor attended high-acuity cases. The delineation between ECP and CP programs was significant in this instance, as the issues pertaining to single responders were applicable either generically across all three study sites or specifically to ECPs attending high-acuity cases.

In general, the skills required to work in the capacity of single responder built upon the participant's previous experiences of working in a traditional two-person ambulance. However, the following participant touched on some of the unique issues working as a single responder:

But you have to get in your head about what you want to do differently, where your intervention points are. Because it is very different to working as a double...when and what you choose to do has to be very much thought out. You have to have it clear in your head about how you are going to do stuff, how you are going to lay it out, what you are prepared to have other people do, are you going to intervene at all in certain settings. (P99)

Another issue unique to single responder work, was the sense of isolation. A participant in the study suggested that the social isolation of single responder work warranted further attention:

Because when you work on the ambulance, you go do your call and then you come back to the hospital and sit and 'shoot the shit' with your buddies at the hospital, you go back to the hall and sit. Where we're very isolated, we sit with our patient and we move on to the next call. We do the paperwork, we do the patient care, we do the driving. Whereas when you work in partners, you've got that off set and then you're always going somewhere where there's another group of people to talk to, but we're isolated from the start of our shift to the end of our shift. We may not see another paramedic, we may not have anyone's opinion, help, hands. So it's a struggle, it's a struggle that we're still trying to figure out and trying to keep people mentally healthy. (P60)

To overcome the sense of isolation, "latching on" (P16) by speaking with other paramedics when the opportunity arose was reported. For example, a participant further explained the "latching on" process by stating, "Lots of us will head to a different ambulance station in our down time, catch up with other crews, or go to the hospital, in the ambulance bays and catch up with other crews." (P03). In learning skills to manage isolation, ECPs/CPs gained a sense of belonging, "so you feel part of a team, you are not just floating

around.” (P17). The sense of belonging to a team promoted a supportive culture within the ECP/CP cohort which in turn facilitated transition, “...but definitely making it clear that you’re not alone. Yes, you make work on your own, but support networks are what makes the program work.” (P41). These supportive networks, promoting *esprit de corps*, are revisited in the core category, *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change* in Chapter 6.

For ECPs however, the transition to single responder work was compounded by the obligation to attend high-acuity cases as well as the ECP-specific cases that they had trained for. (The analysis on high-acuity single responder work was distilled from South Australian and New South Wales participants). For many ECPs, the work role of high-acuity single responder was a novel experience, distinct from their previous work role:

...because then not only have I got this anxiety about doing high-acuity jobs on my own. I am having to totally rethink the way I work even as a normal paramedic coming from a double-crew to now doing big jobs on my own. (P55)

Somewhat counterintuitively, many participants found that qualifying for a role in community paramedicine, resulted operationally in a significant high-acuity workload. For this reason, the performance of a high-acuity single responder could arguably be constituted as a bona fide new work role. One participant surmised, “I reckon it’s half rapid [single] response, half ECP [community paramedicine]” (P15). Thus contained within the Mastering Skills core category, *ECPs experienced a sub-transition to high-acuity single responder within the main transition process*. Moreover, some found the disparity between work role expectations and operational reality stressful:

I come out [to the operational environment] in the middle of winter and I am pretty much being used for 1As, 1Bs [cardiac arrests and other high-acuity cases] and I found that really stressful when I first came out because you are amped up with all I am going to be an ECP. I am going to do sutures and catheters and you memorise all your new pathways and protocols. Honestly for three to four months I did not use any ECP skills at all. I remember the first week going to 1As

[cardiac arrests] on my own and I went to a big prang [road traffic crash] of motorcyclists here. I was on scene for 20 minutes by myself...
(P55)

Comparable to clinical skill development, the data suggested mastery of single responder skills was a function of repetition. Simply put, the more often the paramedic was dispatched as a single responder, the earlier skill mastery was acquired:

At the moment that probably feels like a skill-learning thing. I feel like I am still learning to use the most basic end, to drive safely to lights and signs jobs through the centre of the city, because that is a new thing to me. There were not traffic lights where I used to work, so that is just a skill-learning, repetition-type side of things. (P77)

Similarly, acquiring the skills to work as a single responder was less challenging for some paramedics who had previously been employed as single responders in regional areas, "I worked a lot on my own in the country. I did a lot of single response in the country, so I was actually used to that." (P68) It is unremarkable then, that paramedics with previous experience in single responder work had the advantage of entering the transition process with more confidence:

Working singularly originally you are kind of scared that you are by yourself. If something goes wrong are you going to be able to deal with it. Having been put in that situation and in that situation for several years, you know that you can deal with it. So when it came to ECP working by myself, I knew that I could deal with it. (P37)

For both ECPs and CPs, the analysis suggested participants readily incorporated the transition to single responder work as part of the wider transition experience. In pragmatic terms, participants recognised that working as a single responder was merely another operational skill to be mastered. The complexities of acquiring operational skills were relatively low, meaning skill mastery was reliant largely on repetition and workload volume.

6.7 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The Early Phase of transition signalled the beginning of an active engagement with the four core categories of transition. The Early Phase laid the foundations for the evolution of the core categories over the course of the transition experience. The Early Phase was characterised by an array of negative emotions: stress, anxiety, nervousness and isolation. This was not surprising, particularly given the requirement to essentially perform two new roles under a single ECP/CP job title. Participant's identified the ECP/CP role was actually comprised of two distinguishable roles; that of the "traditional" single responder (with the added complexity of high-acuity cases for ECPs) and, the "non-traditional" community-based role utilising an expanded scope of practice. In response, participants enacted strategies to facilitate the transition process through the rudiments of a community of practice and supportive culture within the ECP/CP cohort. The following section presents a discussion on the Early Phase of transition.

6.8 DISCUSSION OF THE EARLY PHASE

The Early Phase constitutes the first foray into "active" transition whereby participants commenced their journey towards a subjective sense of work role competence. Most of the preliminary emotional descriptors of the transition experience during the Early Phase were negative. The literature is replete with examples of similar findings of Early Phase emotions across the health domains of medicine (Brennan, et al., 2010), nursing (Barnes, 2014) and paramedicine (Devenish, et al., 2016; Kennedy, et al., 2015). Participants of the current study cited several factors which contributed to their having negative emotions. These included an awareness of the magnitude of the transition, the level of critical thinking required, and inexperience with clinical skills. For some participants, these contributing factors were cumulative, drawing similarities to "transition shock", a concept often documented in the nursing literature (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016; Boychuk Duchscher, 2009; Kapborg & Fischbein, 1998).

Transition shock, a term coined by Boychuk Duchscher (2009), builds upon the seminal work of Kramer (1974), in describing professional role adaptation for the nursing graduate. Duchscher argues transition shock is embedded in the first stage of entry into nursing professional practice when the student transitions from the known role of being a student to the relatively unfamiliar role of practicing nurse. In basic terms, transition shock represents the disparity between the expectation of the role, and the true experience of the role. Furthermore, transition shock is encapsulated by imagery such as, "I felt like I just jumped into the deep end of the pool" (Boychuk Duchscher, 2009, p. 1105). Similar sentiments were voiced by participants in this study during the Early Phase of transition citing, "nervousness", "stress", "isolation".

Moreover, the limited studies published on paramedic work role transition seem to support the conclusion that transition shock (Boychuk Duchscher, 2009) is an experience that may be common to the transition of novice paramedic clinicians. For instance, the presence of transition shock was detected by Kennedy, et al. (2015) in a scoping review of student paramedic transition. Likewise, in an examination of university educated paramedics, Devenish, et al. (2016) found that university graduates experienced transition shock during the post-formal stage of socialisation (analogous to the Early Phase in this PhD study).

However, the transferability of the transition shock model and associated conceptual framework proposed by Boychuk Duchscher (2009) is significantly more complex when extrapolated to cognate disciplines such as paramedicine. Nursing and paramedicine share obvious parallels in the delivery of a clinical service, but also have innumerable differences across culture, relationships, and philosophies. Consequently, the congruence between her model and the transition to community paramedicine model should be interpreted with caution. Moreover, transition is contextually influenced in a multitude of ways including, amongst others, relational, situational and environmental conditions (Kralik, et al., 2006). For instance, the most significant point of contention between new-to-practice nurses and ECPs/CPs is likely to be the contextual differences in the current study's cohort of experienced paramedic

practitioners transitioning to a specialist role, as opposed to those of students transitioning to first-position roles.

Nevertheless, sufficient similarities between Duchscher's (2009) transition shock framework and the current study, support a proposition that a *form* of transition shock is experienced by paramedics transitioning to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Indeed, elements of Duchscher's (2009) "transition shock experience" categories resonate with the four core categories of transition distilled from the current study's data. For example, common to both models are: "seeking validation and reassurance", "role uncertainty", and "intra-disciplinary relations". The applicability of Duchscher's model and other theories of transition to the current study are discussed in greater detail in Chapter 10 – Conclusions. In due course however, further longitudinal studies are required to better understand the unique complexities of transition to other specialist roles in paramedicine. The rest of the chapter will now proceed to discuss the salient findings in each of the core categories of transition.

6.9 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The participants' descriptive language of the supportive architecture within the ECP/CP cohort provided the first clues to the existence of a community of practice (Wenger, 2011). Participants spoke of a developing milieu within their respective programs that fostered a sense of collaborative learning and support. Numerous interpretations of a community of practice pervade the literature (Li, et al., 2009). However, an apt definition of the community of practice advanced by the study participants is offered by Hansman (2008, p. 299), citing Lave and Wenger (1991): "A set of relationships among people in social contexts and as self-organised groups of people who share a common sense of purpose and desire to learn and know what each other know".

The early rendition of the community of practice was characterised by several salient features. One of these was the need for reassurance and validation from colleagues – initially from other ECPs/CPs, and later from the

wider healthcare community. The ability to confirm clinical findings and disposition options provided the novice ECP/CP with a “safety net” in the movement towards a subjective sense of work role comfort/confidence. Ultimately, adequate proficiency in the work role signalled the end-point of transition. However, the subjective sense of comfort/confidence, provided the conduit to achieving adequate proficiency.

Reassurance and validation have been noted elsewhere in the related literature. In a concept analysis, Barnes (2014), found the transition from registered nurse to nurse practitioner involved a desire for feedback, analogous to reassurance and validation. Barnes further argued that feedback was subsequently associated with an increased sense of confidence, increased role clarity and mastery, and increased job performance and satisfaction. Similarly, Jones (2005) in a systematic review of role development in specialist and advanced practice nursing roles, argued that feedback from colleagues contributed to professional development. In this regard, the findings in the literature support the relative importance of reassurance and validation in the transition process to community paramedicine. These findings therefore have probative value particularly for ECP/CP educators, in ensuring that opportunities are available to provide reassurance and validation (feedback) to trainees. Moreover, the relative importance of a community of practice should not be undervalued, as some commentators argue work role transition only occurs when entering a new community of practice (Anderson, 2009).

The incipient community of practice during the Early Phase was found to be mostly a paramedic-to-paramedic construction. That is, paramedics initially formed frameworks of support that did not extend much beyond the bounds of their own induction course. However, the ECPs/CPs were also cognisant of the need to challenge the professional “siloes” mentality attributed to the healthcare of traditional paramedic services (Doy & Turner, 2004). Accordingly, as time progressed during the Early Phase, ECPs/CPs drifted towards making connections with other healthcare professionals (OHCPs). Certainly, the cumulative value of collaborative relationships, such as gaining and sharing confidence, and significantly, validation of practice, has been

previously recognised in the transition of advanced practice nurses (Richmond & Becker, 2005). Furthermore, collaboration with OHCPs has served to lessen potential boundary conflict (role overlaps leading to conflict) with OHCPs, generated by new and expanding roles (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016).

Whilst the value of collaborative relationships to the transition experience can be established in the literature, analysis of the current study's results suggests that the participant's experiences of collaboration with OHCPs vary markedly across the study sites. This result suggests an absence in some areas of an inter-professional, collaborative framework between paramedics and OHCPs. It may be wise for ECP/CP program managers and educators to consider strategies to facilitate collaboration. Evidence of the transition of advanced practice nurses include: membership in interdisciplinary professional organisations, participation in continuing education programs, lecturing at professional meetings, and willingness to share ideas (Richmond & Becker, 2005). Ultimately, the ability to work collaboratively across disciplines in healthcare is likely to improve quality of care and patient outcomes (Suter et al., 2009).

6.10 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

The ambulance workplace has been noted as a mix of various sub-cultures (Wankhade, 2012) with the Early Phase of transition seeing many ECPs/CPs enter a workplace culture significantly different from what they previously experienced. Participants have described the traditional ambulance culture in mostly antagonistic terms, consistent with previous paramedic service evaluations (Parker, 2008).

In contrast, the ECP/CP culture has appeared more supportive and collegial, enticing participants to engage in their respective programs. In other words, participants chose to *invest* in their programs by developing a sense of ownership and the strengthening of their conviction in the ethos underscoring community paramedicine. The outputs included increased motivation and incentive to succeed in the role.

The findings were relevant to the transition experience, as investment (also referred to as *employee engagement* (Rana, Ardichvili, & Tkachenko, 2014), and *organisational commitment* (Alexander, 2009)), may be a more suitable benchmark to gauge work satisfaction. Additionally, participant investment in the current study was linked to increasing confidence, through developing motivation. Gent (2016) argues that a motivated employee is more likely to engage more frequently in activities that drive confidence (a key marker of transition), such as the pursuit of continuing professional development opportunities. The experience of the participants in the current study who invested in their respective programs, garnered a sense of ownership, which led to increased motivation and finally, increasing confidence. It is conceded however, that the connections may be prospective, therefore future directions of research should examine further the impact of investment in specialist work role transition.

The second salient finding in the Early Phase was the participants' changed perception of clinical governance. Rather than being viewed as a mandatory reporting requirement, clinical governance was also utilised as a tool of reflective practice. This meta-cognitive shift (Schraw, Crippen, & Hartley, 2006), discussed in more detail in the following section, opened an avenue for participants to develop confidence (key marker of transition) through validation³⁴. In other words, clinical governance was used as a mechanism to follow-up on patients and determine the efficacy of their interventions. By determining the outcome, participants garnered a sense of validation that their actions were appropriate, ergo, confidence was reinforced. Even if the patient outcome was unsatisfactory, clinical governance afforded the participant a learning opportunity for future patient contacts. Any opportunity for learning was regarded with esteem and contributed similarly to developing work role confidence.

³⁴ Validation, in testament to the porous boundaries between core categories, is also discussed in the core category, *Engaging in a Community of Practice*.

The use of clinical governance practices to improve patient outcomes is of course, well established (Braithwaite & Travaglia, 2008) and informs ongoing professional education. However, what is unique about the study's participants was the alacrity with which they approached the use of clinical governance as a validation/confidence tool, not initiated or designed by the ECPs'/CPs' respective organisations. Whilst clinical governance has been deliberated in a variety of contexts within both the grey (Ambulance Service of NSW, 2011) and peer-reviewed literature (Baker, Lakhani, Fraser, & Cheater, 1999; Braithwaite & Travaglia, 2008), no reference has been made to clinical governance being utilised as a tool in the same context as used by ECPs/CPs. The finding not only suggests trainee ECPs/CPs readily accept cultural change, but that they also have a predisposition towards resourceful, self-initiated learning.

6.11 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

Developing critical thinking skills was a significant focus for ECPs/CPs, as the mindset of the community paramedicine practitioner varied markedly from their traditional care roots. The difference was conceptualised in terms of working in "grey" areas that were not governed by well-defined treatment pathways. Historically, paramedic protocols and guidelines directed the clinician through a step-wise approach to managing a patient – referred to by some as "cookbook medicine" (Moy, 1997). Participants additionally described the approach as "very check-box", which contributed to an undercurrent of frustration and boredom with their roles. Moreover, speculation was rife among some participants observing their colleagues that ICPs who had gone through the vocational entry pathway (colloquially referred to as "old school" paramedics), did not find working in the grey areas of community paramedicine to their liking. Some participants surmised that critical thinking in community paramedicine represented too great a departure from traditional ambulance work.

The dissonance in critical thinking between community paramedicine and traditional care can be explained as an issue of *paramedic role perception*. In

a recent article examining paramedic decision-making involving older people who have fallen, Simpson, et al. (2017) proposed a hypothesis that traditional care paramedics may not be culturally or educationally aligned to the concept of meta-cognition. It is important to note that the linkages between meta-cognition and paramedic role perception are promising, although not proven. Nevertheless, the concept is worthy of discussion as ECP/CP role perception pervades numerous aspects of transition.

Briefly, meta-cognition involves higher-order mental processes, such as making plans for learning, using appropriate skills and strategies to solve a problem, and gauging the extent of learning (Coutinho, 2007). In more simplistic terms, meta-cognition can be conceptualised as “thinking about thinking”. By being culturally and organisationally “indoctrinated” to believe that high-acuity work is the only “real work” for paramedics, Simpson, et al. (2017) suggest that this perception of their work role affects the education and training paramedics receive. Consequently, paramedics are not taught the meta-cognitive process which will enable them to consciously reflect on how to promote and enhance clinical decision making.

Simpson and colleagues’ (2017) research resonates with the current study, in suggesting that work role perception (work role expectation) impacts meta-cognition. The cultural and organisational norms of ECPs/CPs towards low-acuity patient presentations – such as that of an elderly person who has fallen - are clearly dichotomous with their traditional care colleagues. In other words, ECPs/CPs do not share the negative perceptions of working in the low-acuity space and view such cases as satisfying. Thus, the present study builds on Simpson’s (2017) hypothesis, by suggesting ECPs/CPs *do* promote meta-cognitive practices in developing critical thinking skills, assisted by the insulated cultural milieu within ECP/CP programs. Examples provided by the participants of developing meta-cognition included: case-based learning³⁵, reflective practices, simulation (discussed further in the next section –

³⁵ Case-based learning involved an oral presentation of a case scenario where the solution was discussed as a “think-aloud” group activity.

Mastering Skills), and assessment via objective structured clinical examination (OSCE). Each of these modalities provide the participant with an opportunity to raise awareness of their own thinking and cognitive errors (Jensen, Bienkowski, et al., 2016).

Paramedic decision-making is integral to the transition to community paramedicine, particularly considering the profession-wide move away from linear based treatment protocols (Jensen, Bienkowski, et al., 2016; Thompson, et al., 2014). The bridge between paramedic work role perceptions and meta-cognition is still tenuous, however, the insights gained from Simpson's (2017) research and this study show that there is a need for closer examination. Moreover, a review of pilot ECP programs in Australia argued that, critical thinking, synthesis of clinical problems and applied clinical reasoning are skills fundamental to the ECP role (Thompson, et al., 2014). Paley, Cheyne, Dalglish, Duncan, and Niven (2007) further contends that training on decision-making processes and thinking styles should be included in the National Occupational Competency Profile, a resource that defines the required content for foundational paramedic training in Canada.

The provisional implications for stakeholders of ECP/CP programs are far ranging. Recruiters into ECP/CP programs may note that the candidates who have "culturally re-set", could more readily accept the meta-cognitive approaches to working in community paramedicine. Additionally, educators could use this information to formulate course content and continuing educational opportunities including simulation-based training. Finally, managers may benefit from an awareness of the implications of changing the unique culture within ECP/CP programs.

Another salient finding in the study was that preceptorship or mentoring plays a significant role in the development of critical thinking during the Early Phase of transition. There are different definitions of preceptorship in the literature, including the idea common to most, that preceptorship is a personal relationship between individuals or within a small group that is established for professional development, role socialisation, and career advancement

(Poronsky, 2012). Preceptorship was highly valued by the participants in the present study, a conclusion ably supported by a plethora of related literature (Glynn & Silva, 2013; Neal, 2008; Thompson, et al., 2014; Whetzel & Wagner, 2008). For instance, Harrington (2011) in a literature review of preceptor programs involving new nurse practitioners, concluded that the preceptor relationship had a positive impact on new nurse practitioners in four areas of practice: quality of care, productivity, job satisfaction, and longevity in practice. Harrington conceded the analysis did not examine nurse practitioners who opted to not partake in a preceptor program. However, Underhill (2006) in a single study, compared the outcomes in a group of nurses who had not been involved in preceptor programs, and concluded that preceptorship improved career outcomes of the preceptor group.

Despite most participants in the current study advocating emphatically the value of preceptorship, time with a specifically-assigned preceptor was conspicuously short. The reasons are likely rooted in operational demands, budget constraints, and preceptor availability and suitability of preceptors. Still, given that preceptorship carries significant value to the transition experience, ECP/CP educators and facilitators have additional avenues to explore, other than the traditional face-to-face dyad of preceptorship. Advances in technology, for example, have seen the emergence of electronic mentoring (e-mentoring) which offers the advantages of greater access, convenience and reduced costs (Ensher, Heun, & Blanchard, 2003).

6.12 MASTERING SKILLS

The transition to community paramedicine required the proficiency in two distinct skills sets: clinical skills used during patient contact, and operational (non-clinical skills) used in the operationalisation of the ECP/CP role. It is important to distinguish between the skills associated with practical or operational *procedures* (which is the focus of the Mastering Skills category) and the other skills required to practice as an effective paramedic, such as critical thinking skills and management skills.

An orthodox Halstedian apprenticeship model³⁶ was the principal approach to teaching clinical skills across the ECP/CP study sites and included low-fidelity simulations, coaching and demonstration. Deeper conceptualisation and understanding were facilitated through discussion and lectures, with further consolidation and repetition featuring prominently during clinical placements and later phases of transition. For the most part, participants were welcoming of the approach undertaken to learn new clinical skills.

A significant drawback in skills training was the fragmented experience of gaining “suitable” or ECP-specific work during clinical placements. For instance, one participant recalled two days in the emergency department without ECP/CP case exposure. Comparable experiences were noted in other clinical placements such as with GPs and community nurses. The limitations of “random chance” exposure to clinical skills has been documented elsewhere in the medical literature (Wang et al., 2008) along with the effects on maintaining skill proficiency (Deakin, King, & Thompson, 2009). Moreover, this finding was replicated unequivocally in the evaluation of an ECP pilot program in Australia (Thompson, et al., 2014). The inconsistency of gaining ECP-suitable work has implications for the training needs of future ECP/CP candidates. Whilst the participants acknowledged that performing procedures on “real” patients is eminently preferable, greater emphasis on other strategies that have shown promise, including higher-fidelity simulation-based practice (Ericsson, 2004; Smith & Roehrs, 2009), is warranted.

There was a perceived lack of complexity in skill acquisition as compared to other core categories, such as the development of critical thinking. The reason not only appears to be due to the preferential use of the “see one, do one” model of instruction, but also because of the ECP’s/CP’s perception of the role. That is, rather than being skills orientated, participants were enthused by the challenges associated with critical thinking to deliver improved patient

³⁶ The Halstedian apprenticeship model has also been referred to as the “see one, do one, teach one” model (Wang, 2011).

outcomes. However, some commentators have warned about complacency in the approach to skills acquisition in paramedicine, particularly with respect to optimising the impacts of clinical placements (Michau, Roberts, Williams, & Boyle, 2009). Further research is warranted to show how skills are taught and how the opportunities for consolidation of learning are engendered.

The final prominent finding in the Mastering Skills core category related to the operationalisation of the ECP/CP role. The ECP/CP service delivery model required the paramedic to work as a single responder. For most participants, this was a significant departure from the more familiar work role context of two paramedics to each ambulance vehicle. Furthermore, the issues associated with single responder work was more poignant for Australian ECPs as they were still required to attend high-acuity emergency cases if operationally demanded. Herein lay a significant finding; ECPs experienced a *sub-transition to high-acuity single responder* within the main transition process.

Being a single responder required the participant to develop a range of strategies to adapt to the changed personal and contextual factors of working without an off-sider. It can be argued, that the participants' description of high-acuity single responder work satisfies the salient definition of a work role transition, which is "any change in employment status and any major change in job content" (Nicholson, 1984, p. 173). One participant divided high-acuity work with ECP-specific work, evenly. Given the argument above, the question arises as to whether the transition to high-acuity single responder is a distinct transition from that of community paramedicine. Despite the ECP model operating somewhat counter-intuitively to the non-traditional philosophy underpinning community paramedicine (O'Meara, 2014), the expertise of the high-acuity single responder is more appropriately classed as an operational skill to be acquired.

Participants expressed the belief that the transition to high-acuity single responder work was simply a function of job exposure, that is, repetition. Skill acquisition was less concerned about learning new clinical interventions, rather it was viewed as learning operational and clinical *priorities*. In other words,

participants learnt by experience how to manage a patient and what they could accomplish on their own. It was unsurprising then, that single responder transition has received little credence in training programs. Some participants recalled that very few hours – if any – were allocated to acquiring the skills of single responder work. Indeed, the literature makes only a passing mention about the ability of single responders to handle the stressors of working alone (Thompson, et al., 2014). With little to no additional training provided to trainee ECPs/CPs prior to deployment, this research supplies the evidence to significantly overhaul the ECP/CP training programs to include single responder training.

Finally, this thesis argues that the ECP/CP work role is unique to the health profession. Arguably, nowhere else does transition to a new work role involve retaining an old work role, based on operational demands. By way of an example, an ECP may be expected to attend a (high-acuity) patient in cardiac arrest, and then attend to a (low-acuity, ECP-specific) patient requiring a falls assessment. The ability to “flip” between high-acuity and low-acuity roles is discussed further in Chapter 8 – Late Phase.

6.13 CONCLUSION

The Early Phase makes a significant contribution to the transition experience as the core categories form the foundation on which the remaining phases are built. Conceptually, reassurance, validation and investment feature predominantly, as does the shifting perception of clinical governance and meta-cognitive approaches. There is still much to understand about the culture of learning and the rapid changes brought about by the introduction of specialist roles in paramedicine. There is no more stark example of this than the ECP/CP model of service delivery among the health professions, which is quite unique.

Having discussed the Early Phase of transition, the thesis now moves to the Middle Phase of transition. The Middle Phase saw the emergence of the competent practitioner, and was the bridge between the neophyte ECP/CP and a practitioner feeling comfortable and confident in the work role.

Chapter 7: Middle Phase – The Competent Practitioner

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The Middle Phase of transition correlates with the paramedic having achieved a basic level of competence in the ECP/CP role. Despite the increase in confidence, ECPs/CPs were still learning, “the tricks of the trade” (P93). In other words, the nuances of service delivery in community paramedicine were yet to be mastered. Chapter 6 presents the analysis of the Middle Phase of transition and examines how the participants utilised this phase as a vehicle to move closer to a subjective sense of comfort/confidence – a key indicator of transition distilled from the data. As with the previous results chapters, the analysis is followed by a discussion of the findings.

7.2 UNIQUE ASPECTS OF THE MIDDLE PHASE

Traversing the Middle Phase of transition appeared to be a challenging time for most participants. The collective view can be described simply as, “trying to stay afloat” (P17). Participants had possibly become more aware that the confidence gleaned from their previous role in traditional care was not readily transferable to their new role in community paramedicine:

...our outstanding paramedic confidence wasn't going to cut it anymore. We've had to learn how to be confident at the level of everybody else that we were working with, not just rely on our egos. [laughs] (P33)

The central focus of the transition experience was the progression of participants towards a subjective sense of work role comfort/confidence. For most participants, comfort/confidence was manifested in the ability to make sound clinical risk decisions in the disposition of patients to other than an emergency department. For example, the following participant underscored

the role of confidence in clinical risk decision making and its relative importance to the transition process:

Whereas one of the big things about being an ECP is that when you leave that patient, they may not see their doctor for two, three, four days. So you have got to have the confidence in your own decision making that that is the appropriate care plan. That took us all a while to work out. That was one of the biggest transitions... (P82)

The following participant's language, whilst profane, succinctly captured the essence of the Middle Phase. Moreover, in using the participant's own words, the interpretative distance between the researcher and participant can be reduced (Saldaña, 2015):

...but there's the 'don't fuck up' stage, I think, when you're not nervous anymore, but you're at the stage where you're, 'I think I'm on the right track, but I don't want to fuck this up. (P97)

The four core categories of transition collectively describe the entire transition experience with the Middle Phase of transition being the intermediate step between the novice and advanced (comfortable/confident) practitioner. The following sections detail the contribution of the four core categories in developing the Middle Phase – that of a *competent* practitioner.

7.3 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

During the Middle Phase of transition, the community of practice model significantly expands with the more pronounced inclusion of other healthcare professionals (OHCPs). Viewed in a different way, OHCPs undergo a unique transition of their own - developing acceptance of ECPs/CPs. By developing reciprocal acceptance, credibility and rapport with OHCPs, paramedics are able to facilitate partnerships with OHCPs that approach an equal level. The successful transition of an ECP/CP is thus contingent on the successful transition of OHCPs. Whilst the process of transition of OHCPs occurs remotely from ECP/CP transition, gaining acceptance by OHCPs still plays an integral role in the ECPs/CPs transition experience. For example, should a general practitioner retain previous biases about paramedics and not transition to

accepting ECPs/CPs as valued colleagues, the transition process for the ECP/CP is in turn delayed.

The transition for OHCPs - and by extension - the expansion of the ECP/CP community of practice, occurs principally through developing credibility, respect and rapport with ECPs/CPs. In simple terms, transition for OHCPs occurs largely through educating OHCPs of the niche in healthcare delivery that ECPs/CPs could provide:

They [OHCPs] acknowledge us for the skills and the service that we provide that they can't. There is a fair amount of respect. And I think we've built that over the years with the program too. We're not here to tread on anyone else's toes. We're here for the benefit of the patient.
(P13)

Most of the education of OHCPs is initiated by ECPs/CPs and stakeholder managers. The value of educating OHCPs is of foremost importance for ECPs/CPs:

Yes, and that is why I don't ever look at it [developing collaborative relationships with OHCPs] as a formality, because that is why we can do what we can do, because we have that connection. If we didn't have it, we wouldn't be able to do nearly all the stuff we do. (P50)

The following data reiterates the value of supporting OHCP transition and provides an impression of the full outcome benefits of developing credibility and rapport with doctors in the next phase of transition – the Advanced Phase:

And now we're at the point where - and the doctors are 100% supportive in the fact - that we'll say to them, 'This is what we've got,' and they'll say, 'Well what do you want to do? What do you think would be a good idea?' and [we're] like, 'We'll have about 10 days of Levaquin [antibiotic] and we'll do a repeat chest x-ray.' And they'll be like, 'Yes sure but do the x-ray first,' and you get more of like an on-level discussion instead of doctor being up here and paramedic being down here. It feels like you're not equal but you can hold a professional conversation and it feels like you're listened to. (P08)

One participant speculated that OHCP transition was necessitated by their prior negative experience of paramedics, "I mean sometimes they have to get over this hump because all they've seen with paramedics is that belligerence." (P22). Another participant suggested the relationship of paramedics with OHCPs was analogous to the historical relationship between doctors and nurse specialists:

It would probably mirror the same thing that happened with nurse specialists 10, 20 years ago, rather than nurses just being seen as an adjunct to the hospital and/or doctors in what they do. (P49)

Consequently, ECP/CP program designers may benefit from considering the relative importance of OHCP relationships to the overall ECP/CP transition. Moreover, the transition experience of an OHCP is conceptually similar to the subordinate transition of paramedics to single responder. Further research is warranted as to the structure, function and contribution of subordinate transitions contained within the main transition process.

The transition of OHCPs to acceptance of ECPs/CPs is a construction of *credibility and rapport*. Credibility and rapport in turn, are created through a variety of mechanisms. For example, the ability of OHCPs to see the impact of community paramedicine on their patients has a significant transformative effect on their attitude towards paramedics. The following is an extract from an ECP:

I went to a pal care [palliative care] grand round³⁷ the other day and the comments that we get back from the social workers and the nurses and the doctors in the pal care teams, is really, really positive and they love us. I know that when I go to a patient and I can relieve their suffering for a while or I can help their family cope with the situation or I can help them plan ahead. (P82)

Moreover, in the following passage, a participant says that rapport facilitates the development of trust between doctor and paramedic. The

³⁷ Grand round was a medical education tool where the clinical management of an individual patient is discussed amongst medical and allied health staff.

passage also suggests that rapport and trust are utilised in the development of work role comfort/confidence. Once again, the data identified the subjective sense of comfort/confidence as a marker of ECP/CP transition:

Initially with the doctors you didn't want to say, 'Well I think it is this and I think we should do this' but over time you develop that rapport with your physicians, especially our network of physicians; the ones that we call when we can't get a hold of the family physician. You develop that rapport and they trust you. (P05)

Linked to the transition of OHCP and relevant to the configuration of the community of practice during the Middle Phase, is the concept of *receiving validation*. The data is highly suggestive that confidence is advanced for ECPs/CPs who receive validation of their clinical decisions by OHCPs, predominantly doctors. Notably, the degree of validation the ECPs/CPs sought is inversely proportional to elapsed time. In other words, the further progressed ECPs/CPs are in the transition process, the less validation is sought from doctors. Furthermore, this result suggests that validation is related to confidence; the more confident the ECP/CP became, the less validation was required:

There were plenty of times where I had my plan, but I just wanted to run it past someone, just to see if they were happy with that. Whether it be the mentors, and I've done that with GPs, as well, with their patients, just to see if they were happy with it, and if I'm on the right track. And yes, you're 100% right, it did validate your thought process. You'd go, 'Okay, I am getting this. I'm not an idiot,' and you're happy that the next time you may not have to rely on calling someone to confirm your plan. Sometimes you can just enact a plan, because you know you're on the right track, or you've experienced it now, you've had a professional, or more experienced person confirm that you're on the right track. And I can say that is that transition period where you've then got the confidence to make your own clinical decision without referral. (P97)

Furthermore, an inverse relationship between confidence and reassurance was contended to have occurred over time:

...it is really common practice as you would probably remember. You have your buddies and you work out who is on your line [roster] and it is great to just get another opinion: 'This is what I am thinking, what do you think?' and just to get that reassurance. You find the more confident you feel with your skill set the less calls and [laughs] reassurance you need to get from your colleagues essentially. (P55)

The relatively high importance of transition for OHCPs to the overall transition process for ECPs/CPs was an unexpected result. This study opens further avenues for research on the transition that doctors, nurses and other allied health professionals undergo with respect to working with paramedics. The chapter now turns to discussing organisational and cultural change during the Middle Phase of transition.

7.4 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

During this phase of the transition process, the organisational and cultural adaptations within the ECP/CP group continue to evolve. In contrast to the dominant negative emotions of the Early Phase, participants acquired a feeling of "safety" in that they could make errors and not be chastised or ridiculed by colleagues. The following participant illustrates this feeling of safety, while also commenting on the culture brought over from traditional care during the Early Phase of transition:

And I think that was something else we've all said, is that at the beginning, you'll just be like - I don't know if it's that EMS mentality – that if you asked you were seen as weak. Whereas I've got so good at picking up the phone, going, 'Okay, I don't know if I'm speaking to the right person but this is the situation we've got. Can you help me? If not, do you know somebody that can?' And the confidence of doing that has grown and people are so receptive. (P77)

Nevertheless, acquiring a sense of safety was contingent on the ECPs/CPs commitment to continuing education. That is, it was necessary for ECPs/CPs

to demonstrate a commitment to professional development to be afforded support from colleagues if an error was made. For example, the following ECP/CP illustrated how a potentially negative outcome was opportunistically used as a learning tool:

I'd like to think that I'd never done the former, that I'd been making a bad decision because of a poor assessment, or because of a lack of knowledge of what my pathways are. I think when I have had someone say, 'Well, no, actually how about we do this,' it's more of a, 'Okay. Yes, all right.' I hadn't seen that because I wasn't aware of that disease, or I'd never experienced it before. I just wasn't that confident in my decision, and therefore I made the wrong one. But I'd take that on board as an education opportunity, and as a positive. And, you know, hopefully you have the reflection to not make that error next time. (P97)

For another participant, support was a function of being conscientious and asking for assistance when required:

I guess what I found is, you're allowed to make mistakes and that just gives you such a safety net, as long as you're conscientious, call for help when you need it, then you're allowed to make mistakes. And it's just such a feeling of comfort, such a feeling of support. So it's scary, but it's scary in a growing way that's exciting, not stressful. (P22)

Thus, acquiring a sense of safety allowed the competent ECP/CP an avenue to develop their professional practice and progress to the Advanced Phase of transition. The sense of safety was derived from an expectation amongst the ECP/CP cohort that every patient encounter was an opportunity to learn. Consequently, work role comfort/confidence became a by-product of an acquired sense of safety.

Lastly, the different service delivery philosophies between traditional and community paramedicine requires the ECP/CP to be adaptive. For instance, as ECPs/CPs spent substantially more time with patients than their traditional care counterparts, some ECPs/CPs discovered a new dimension to their role -

emotional attachment to their patients. The attachment one participant felt for one of her patients was obvious in the following excerpt:

But it is like drama. Because we had this one guy who we were really close to and he's a rough sleeper, so sleeps who knows where. But we always knew where to find him and then all of a sudden, one day he wasn't there. It was like, 'Oh!' We checked in all the hospitals and we phoned jail to see if he was in jail because we kind of got word through the street people that the police had picked him up. But jail said no, he wasn't there. Then the second day he wasn't there. The third day he wasn't there and we were like, 'What's happening?' Dreaming about it, waking up at night, thinking about where the fuck is he, what the hell has happened to him. And that had never happened to me in my life. Finally, we found out he was in jail and I have been trying to figure out why when we called twice they weren't able to tell us that. (P22)

The above quote suggested that post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) was the tentative link between transition to community paramedicine and emotional attachment to patients:

But I also think that [CP] students don't make that transition appropriately and that is where the PTSD comes in. I don't think we teach them how to deal with these things and I have not been taught how to deal with this. But I don't know if anybody knows. (P22)

Traditional paramedicine often consists of relatively brief encounters with patients during an acute phase in their injury or illness. Community paramedics on the other hand, could see the same patient frequently over many months and develop an emotional attachment, particularly with palliative care patients:

Then there was the difficulty of now becoming more a part of your patient's life and care. You know, we deal a lot with a patient's end of life care and that was a whole new thing. It's one thing to have a patient that you just come on from a 911 call and you know nothing about them and you see their tragedy and that's hard enough. Now we have patients that we see for some time, over months and no matter what kind of fences you put up, you get to know them or their families

and you see their inevitable end as well and that's a different stress to deal with. (P83)

These results imply that there is a need for a better understanding of critical incidents which can predispose ECPs/CPs to mental health issues. Paramedic services have a duty of care to their staff (Scully, 2011) and should therefore explore the changing domains of paramedic practice in which paramedics may more frequently develop an emotional attachment with a patient built over weeks or months of healthcare interactions.

7.5 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

Throughout the second phase of transition, ECPs/CPs become more autonomous practitioners, in part through the advancement of critical thinking skills. Participants embrace clinical governance as a learning tool, invest in self-reflective practices and value peer-to-peer engagement. These three elements certainly existed in other phases of transition. However, it was during the Middle Phase that these elements converged to exert the greatest influence on the development of critical thinking throughout the transition process. The following comment, for example, suggests that self-reflection was prominent in the first year of ECP/CP practice: "The first year was definitely a real steep learning curve...so I really had to evaluate my own mistakes a lot more, harshly is the wrong word, but you had to be a lot more complete." (P49)

A robust clinical governance structure has been built into each of the three community paramedicine programs. Despite the requirement for mandatory reporting in support of clinical governance, ECPs/CPs have embraced clinical governance as a learning tool. Significantly, the following passage also suggests that there is a connection between reflecting on patient feedback through clinical governance and developing confidence:

So you find out if the patient called '000' again. Got themselves to an ED [emergency department] or to the GP if it was advised by the ECP to do that. Ask how they felt five, six, seven days afterwards. So that helps... that helps to find out that you did the right job on a patient, that you chose the right pathway. And it gives you confidence. (P68)

Additionally, it was found that confidence and experience are inexorably linked. In other words, experience is an important vehicle by which ECPs/CPs gain confidence and advance through the transition process. The following participant viewed call-backs³⁸ as an important contributor to transition experience:

I have learned more from call-backs I think in that first couple of years [of being an ECP] than I had in all my years on the job. Just having that follow through, that continuity of care. It is not just 20 minutes and see you later and I have no idea really. Unless you follow up on your more interesting cases, which you do but time constraints and all that, you can't follow everybody. But love the call-back thing as an education tool for ECPs, especially new ECPs finding their way and getting a feel what happens in this case, what happened to that knee injury, what happened to that guy with the ankle, what happened to that guy with the sutures, and you get that feedback and it becomes your internal library. You can put it all together and it all adds up to experience and it guides your practice. (P16)

Call-backs were one form of self-reflective practice and were closely entwined with the principles of clinical governance. Self-reflective practice also involved participants evaluating themselves against their own set of criteria to improve clinical practice. One paramedic service placed significant importance on self-reflective practice as part of the transition process:

That's really kind of our education, there's a core amount that we provide people, and then throughout your time as a community paramedic, if you feel you need something, it's your responsibility to identify that you need it and then management will facilitate the education. (P30)

Similarly, others recognised the value of engaging in self-reflection as a means of developing critical thinking skills. One participant argued that

³⁸ Call-back is a clinical governance activity to ascertain the patient's outcome following an ECP/CP encounter and if any adverse events occurred.

although the foundations for critical thinking were laid during the initial training course, critical thinking skills were strengthened in the post-course phases of transition. The findings are relevant for program educators and managers in understanding the importance of critical thinking skills development during the Middle Phase of transition. While undoubtedly, operational and other demands exert pressure on the time available to an ECP/CP, the significance of allowing time for an ECP/CP to engage in self-reflective practices should not be undervalued. As the participant noted:

...you get the skills and the knowledge base there when you go to do the course. It is your retrospective learning after that. And it's how good your peers are, and how open your peers are to go, 'I have this, and presented like this, this, and this. What do you reckon?' 'I've done this, this, and this.' Now, it doesn't come just by the skills and knowledge, this comes with retrospective learning, and advancing your best patient outcomes, and best treatment options.' (P13)

Of particular note, was the speculation that personal character was a determinant in whether an ECP/CP successfully transitioned after negative feedback was encountered. The participant suggests negative feedback elicited from clinical governance was either a positive or negative experience – dependent on the internal dialogue of the paramedic:

I guess it's what type of person you are. Yes, some ECPs have left the role, because they just felt that they couldn't deal with the negative side, and went back to being an emergency paramedic. I guess it depends how you learn, and how you take on criticism, and whether you use that as a learning experience, or whether it's something that you really struggle with, and whether you want to expose yourself to that all the time. You know, some people can't, and some people use it as a learning experience. (P03)

The implications of the passage above extend to the selection of ECPs/CPs. Paramedics who could demonstrate a motivation to learn from both positive and negative feedback experiences were likely to progress through the transition process more readily. However, the results should be taken in

context. This study has been limited by an absence of data collected from participants who were unsuccessful in the transition process. Therefore any conclusions drawn by participants regarding unsuccessful transition is based on the perspective of those who completed their training and continued in their new work role, rather than on the direct experience of those who unsuccessfully attempted transition.

The Middle Phase of transition sees the strengthening of ECP/CP peer-to-peer engagement as a means of developing critical thinking. In essence, peer-to-peer engagement is utilised as a resource to determine the best management options for patients. Peer-to-peer engagement is yet another example of the interconnections between core categories, being closely linked with a community of practice. Additionally, the Middle Phase is conceptually aligned with receiving validation and confidence as seen within a peer-to-peer or community of practice context, "I feel confident. But it also helps very much that the group of ECPs, if I go to a job that I'm not quite sure, we call a friend. So that helps as well." (P68)

Of particular importance, one paramedic service extended the parameters of the peer-to-peer relationships for the benefit of the entire group. Individuals with specialised knowledge in one area of clinical practice such as ECG interpretation³⁹, blood analysis and wound care, shared their knowledge with their colleagues. Specialisation was relevant as it offered a unique investment by an individual clinician to the overall success of the program, by sharing information with colleagues:

I think on the job, the team that we have does a phenomenal job with making it feel comfortable and supporting you and being there. We have a group of individual little specialists that all work together when you need it. If you feel like you're kind of overwhelmed with this ECG, and you're like 'I don't know', there's something but I can't put my

³⁹ An ECG records the electrical activity of the heart and may be used in the diagnosis of injuries to the heart due to a lack of blood supply.

finger on it, we send it off to the person on the team that, that's their bread and butter. (P72)

Specialisation is not a programmed event, rather it evolves from a participant's own initiative and interest in one area of clinical practice. These concepts are not unique to a single phase of transition but exist in multiple layers across the transition process. For example, participant investment in the ECP/CP program, a form of specialisation, is noted to be an accelerator of transition. Accelerators and decelerators of transition are discussed further in Chapter 9.

7.6 MASTERING SKILLS

Participants entered the Middle Phase of transition as novice practitioners. The fundamentals of skill acquisition to this point have consisted largely of classroom-based learning and field placement under supervision. Consolidation of skills, such as catheterisation, suturing and dislocated shoulder reduction, begin in earnest during the Middle Phase with participants treating patients in the community as sole practitioners. The analysis revealed that two themes emerged during the Middle Phase of transition with respect to mastering skills: *an eagerness to perform a new skill for the first time*, and *developing confidence through repetition*.

Many participants expressed an eagerness to perform a new skill for the first time. The reason appears to be conceptually grounded in the development of confidence. In performing a skill on a "real-world" patient (that had only previously been performed under simulation or supervision) ECPs/CPs became more confident in their performance of skills. In the following passage, a participant discusses their rendering of the transition process with the reference to "stage two" aligning with the Middle Phase of transition. The connection between "first" skills, growing confidence, and transition was also made explicit:

What I would call stage two, is when I became exposed to my first catheter, my first female catheter, my first migraine⁴⁰. Yes, once I go through those first of these things, my confidence grows, and I feel more of an ECP. (P41)

The following participant also supported an eagerness to perform “first” skills mooted above. An analogy to the Intensive Care course was also drawn:

You can’t order your work in, same is when you are an ICP you just want to get those tubes⁴¹ out of the way. Get those monkeys off your back. It takes time and it is random. (P16)

The above passage alluded to the sporadic nature of “appropriate” or ECP/CP-specific cases. That is, cases where the knowledge and skills of an ECP/CP, rather than traditional care paramedics, had the most impact on patient outcomes. As with the earlier citations, the following participant suggested that a degree of work role comfort is a function of accessing “appropriate” ECP/CP-specific cases:

Now I have put digital blocks⁴² on patients. I have done dislocated knees and I have done dislocated shoulders. I have not done an annular ligament displacement of a child but I would be a little bit uncomfortable about doing my first, as you always are with your first dislocation of a finger. It is just something that has never dropped into my lap. (P88)

The findings above suggest that increased access to ECP/CP-specific cases contribute to increased confidence in skill mastery and ultimately transition. A subjective sense of comfort/confidence has been identified by participants as uniquely the most common marker of the end-point of transition. Thus, accessing ECP/CP-specific cases to develop confidence introduced the concept of *repetition*:

⁴⁰ The participant was referring to the skill of performing a neurological examination.

⁴¹ Endotracheal tube – an ICP/EMT-P skill to place a plastic tube into the trachea (windpipe) of an unconscious patient.

⁴² A digital block was an anaesthetising procedure on a finger(s) or toe(s).

Just this equal repetition of doing non-transporters and doing the jobs that we do all the time like, non-traumatic back pains and dislocations. You just get confidence in building those skills up. (P55)

The influence of repetition on transition was clear, "...doing things repetitiously and using your skills, then the transition goes smoother." (P17) Repetition also allowed the participants to explore the nuances of specific skill sets, whilst pursuing the goal of comfort/confidence:

But after having done countless numbers of urinary catheters and seeing all the permutations of different catheter presentations and so on, and some of which the patients are very sick, and some of which the patients are not very sick. Then understanding which is which - you sort of achieve a level of comfort. (P88)

The results suggest repetition of ECP/CP-specific cases is correlated with increased skill mastery and more broadly, work role comfort/confidence. The findings suggest, therefore, that ECPs/CPs should be allocated to cases best suited to their skill set and that the opportunity for skill repetition should be prioritised. With respect to skill mastery, service planners could examine mechanisms to increase the volume of appropriate cases allocated to ECPs/CPs.

7.7 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The Middle Phase of transition sees the emergence of the competent practitioner. ECPs/CPs continue to build upon their earlier knowledge and skill base in the inexorable pursuit of a subjective sense of work role comfort/confidence. In all four core categories, the actions of the participants were orientated towards advancing to the final phase of transition. Support networks were expanded to be more inclusive of OHCPs and participants reported a greater sense of "safety" in their practice. Additionally, critical thinking was accelerated by embracing clinical governance and skill consolidation, and was most active during this phase. The following section of the chapter discusses the implications of the results for ECP/CP programs and how this research complements the extant literature on work role transition.

7.8 DISCUSSION OF THE MIDDLE PHASE

The Middle Phase represents the bridge between the new-to-practice ECP/CP and the emergence of a confident/competent practitioner in the Late Phase. Although the initial nervousness and anxiety of the novice practitioner have been left behind, the descriptors during the Middle Phase are still laced with hesitancy about the work role. Participants were still learning “the tricks of the trade” (P93) in a phase consistent with other transitional experiences in paramedicine (McFarlane, 2010; Munro, et al., 2017). The dominant contributor to the transition experience during the Middle Phase was the development of an external community of practice.

7.9 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The structure of the community of practice undergoes a significant expansion towards the end of the Early Phase of transition. Formed initially to provide a framework of mutually reciprocal support within the training environment, the service delivery model in community paramedicine requires a higher degree of engagement and collaboration with OHCPs (Suter, et al., 2009). While fostering a collegial relationship with OHCPs is not the exclusive domain of the Middle Phase and beyond, the challenges to collaboration become more marked. For instance, some participants believed the negative preconceptions some doctors had of paramedics inhibited the development of mutual trust and respect between parties. In essence, doctors underwent a transformative journey or sub-transition *before* relations with ECPs/CPs could be equalised and the community of practice expanded.

Conceptually, sub-transition is not novel. The community paramedicine service model no doubt burrows into the hierarchical culture of medicine established for over a century (Desborough, 2012), in which a doctor assumes a prominent role and the nurse a subordinate role (Maylone, Ranieri, Griffin, McNulty, & Fitzpatrick, 2011). ECPs/CPs in the current study, with their expanded scope of practice, have described similar friction in crossing role-boundaries as has been reported in the nurse practitioner literature (Griffin & Melby, 2006; Manning & Neville, 2009). Whereas the benefits of collaborative

relationships between health professionals in community paramedicine are well known (Eaton, 2017; Kizer, et al., 2013; O'Meara, 2014), the manner in which inter-professional dynamics between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs develop, is poorly understood.

The paramount importance of a collegial relationship with OHCPs to carry out their work roles was highlighted in the current study. To that end, ECPs/CPs initiated various strategies to garner credibility and rapport with OHCPs, such as attending clinical reviews (grand rounds). Clinical reviews afforded the ECP/CP the opportunity to showcase their expertise and articulate more clearly their scope of practice in a collegial and educative manner. The principles behind the strategy are by no means unique. For instance, Derengowski, Irving, Koogler, and Englander (2000) recognised the importance amongst nurse practitioners, of establishing credibility through clinical expertise with doctors. Similarly, Richmond and Becker (2005) argued that a "credible house" is erected from words and decisions drawn from a solid knowledge base and sound clinical judgements. Thus, forging mutual trust and respect between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs is an integral component of the transition experience.

The importance of collegial relationships to the community paramedicine role was an expected finding. However, the *degree of significance* of OHCP sub-transition contributing to the main ECP/CP transition experience was unexpected. OHCP transition has been defined as the ability of OHCPs to view ECPs/CPs within an equal framework. Numerous elements that facilitated both ECP/CP transition and functioning in the role of an ECP/CP were dependent on reciprocal relationships with OHCPs. These elements included the establishment of credibility, preceptorship, skills acquisition and ultimately, improvement in patient outcomes. Thus, the ability of a paramedic to transition to a community paramedicine role was contingent, to a significant degree, on OHCPs' sub-transition. Although the ECP/CP programs made varying degrees of effort in establishing collegial relationships with OHCPs, this research highlights the centrality and importance of OHCP sub-transition to the overall ECP/CP transition experience. This research, however, has been limited

significantly by the lack of perspective provided by OHCPs. Ideally, further research should be done to include the sampling of OHCPs to better illuminate this area of interest.

7.10 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

A significant sign of the adaptive organisational and cultural milieu within the ECP/CP programs was the acquisition of a sense of “safety” amongst the participants because they could make clinical errors and not be chastised or ridiculed by colleagues. In marked contrast to previous experiences in traditional paramedicine (Price, Bendall, Patterson, & Middleton, 2013), a sense of safety was seen by ECPs/CPs as an opportunity for professional development and learning, rather than derision. Commentators have previously called for organisational strategies that build an open culture and provide reassurance in the ability to report clinical incidents (Barach & Small, 2000). Arguably, the ECP/CP community have accomplished an open culture by acquiring a sense of safety. The caveat however, is that a sense of safety had to be “earned”. In other words, the paramedic had to be seen to be committed to continuing professional development to be afforded support from colleagues if an error was made. Comparable findings have been noted in the literature where doctors empathetically forgave the mistakes of others who utilised self-blame as a stimulus for learning and improvement (Collins, Block, Arnold, & Christakis, 2009). In this regard, ECPs/CPs are progressive in moving away from a culture of punitive blame, to a culture of medicine, where errors are seen as inevitable but also facilitated by actions and decisions made “upstream” within a system (Waring, 2005). Thus, opportunities within ECP/CP programs for continued professional development as a driver for organisational and cultural change, should be made available and keenly encouraged.

The second salient finding in this sub-category arose due to the extended time some ECPs/CPs spent with their patients over the course of many weeks and months. Although traditional paramedicine is noted as physically and emotionally draining for both the paramedics and the patient’s family (Porter, 2013; Regehr, Goldberg, & Hughes, 2002), encounters with patients and

others are usually brief. Community paramedicine on the other hand, may see a paramedic encounter the same patient on numerous occasions over an extended period of time. Invariably, emotional connections are made with the patient and the family.

Despite a growing body of evidence related to critical incident exposure⁴³ amongst emergency paramedics (Avraham, et al., 2014; Drewitz-Chesney, 2012), the impact of critical incident exposure on the ECP/CP population is poorly understood. A participant in the current study provided an insight into the matter, saying that trainee CPs were not given the appropriate preparation in dealing with palliative care patients. The participant further argued that the lack of preparation increased the susceptibility of the paramedic to PTSD which, in turn, inhibited the transition process. The connection is plausible, given that the doctrine of traditional paramedicine is that of saving lives and conveyance to hospital (Al-Shaqsi, 2010). However, an ECP/CP may be called to a patient whom they have attended on a number of occasions, and assist the patient in the dying process. Accordingly, further research is required to better understand the psychological supportive interventions best suited to paramedics who experience posttraumatic symptomology, particularly grief and loss, following prolonged exposure to a therapeutic relationship with a patient who dies.

7.11 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

By the Middle Phase of transition, participants were becoming more autonomous practitioners. The training course, clinical placements and time with a preceptor in the community have been completed at this point. Despite now carrying the authority to practice as an ECP/CP, a strong intrinsic motivation to continue advancing in the role persisted for most participants. However, opportunities to develop clinical reasoning and critical thinking were

⁴³ Critical incident exposure is a broad concept referring to any situation that causes an exceptionally strong emotion reaction, with one possible effect being the development of posttraumatic stress disorder (Avraham, Goldblatt, & Yafe, 2014; Bennett et al., 2005; Mitchell, 1983).

not as readily accessible in the operational environment. Without the immediacy of educators, lecturers, and others nearby, ECPs/CPs sought to take greater responsibility for their learning and development. Given the unique operational and cultural environment within the community paramedicine programs, ECPs/CPs have to exercise their initiative to utilise clinical governance, self-reflective practices and, peer-to-peer engagement in order to further develop critical thinking.

As further evidence of the interconnections between core categories, clinical governance not only symbolised organisational and cultural change in the Early Phase, but was also used as a vehicle for developing critical thinking in later phases. As part of the clinical governance cycle, patient feedback and self-reflection served as a means of validating confidence. Additionally, peer-to-peer engagement, conceptually linked to a community of practice, served to further bolster validation and confidence.

The intrinsic motivation demonstrated by ECPs/CPs, has been described in the paramedicine literature as both "learner responsibility" (Cooper, 2005), and "self-regulated learning" (Schraw, et al., 2006) in the broader education literature. In essence, both terms describe the balance of ownership and responsibility for on-going continuous professional development shifting towards the paramedics themselves, rather than relying on managers to provide learning opportunities. Gent (2016), in a recent systematic review of continuing professional development in paramedicine, concludes that there is certainly a need to drive continuing professional development through the individual; however, to do so also requires a cultural shift. Undoubtedly, ECPs/CPs have demonstrated a culture aligned with the principles of contemporary continuous professional development. These principles play a significant role in fostering work role confidence and therefore are a direct contributor to work role transition.

7.12 MASTERING SKILLS

From the initial deployment as a practicing ECP/CP, participants showed a propensity to use their newly acquired clinical skills. This sentiment was

interpreted as a desire to perform “first” skills. The significance of performing a skill for the first time, not in a simulation, was clearly associated with increasing confidence – a key marker of transition. Moreover, the relevance to ECP/CP transition can be inferred from the nursing literature in which direct patient contact was determined to be an essential foundational component for successful role transition to advance practice nurse (Spoelstra & Robbins, 2010).

Naturally, completing a skill for the first time did not guarantee competency, and participants sought to garner further confidence, via repetition. Repetition however, was directly impacted by the sporadic capture of “appropriate” or ECP/CP-specific cases. In operational terms, the issue became a matter of *tasking*, that is, the preferential allocation of ECP/CP-specific cases by dispatchers in Control Centres to ECPs/CPs. Many participants were frustrated by the lack of appropriate tasking from Control Centres, thereby reducing the opportunity to use clinical skills. The issue of tasking is examined further in Chapter 9 – Accelerators and Decelerators.

Despite the frequent use of the term “repetition” in the data transcripts, the participants appeared to engage in more sophisticated cognitive processes in clinical skill acquisition, with elements akin to “deliberate practice” (Ericsson, Krampe, & Tesch-Römer, 1993). Deliberate practice is more than the simple automaticity of repetition alone. Rather, deliberate practice involves other factors such as the motivation to improve, the use of feedback and self-reflection, and making gradual refinements in skill performance (Ericsson, 2004). Elements of deliberate practice can be inferred from participants who described an awareness of the nuances of specific skill sets such as catheterisation, and a willingness to review and refine practice. Skill acquisition requires more than repetition alone (Kneebone et al., 2002), so that examining new opportunities for the applications of deliberate practice in community paramedicine would prove to be quite interesting. The outcomes may support the earlier acquisition of clinical skills and sustain a level of clinical competence of rarely utilised skills.

7.13 CONCLUSION

The Middle Phase of transition was a time of rapid growth for the new-to-practice ECPs/CPs. Although work role confidence was increasing, participants were still discovering their own identities as primary healthcare professionals. The contrast with their previous experiences in traditional paramedicine, which included long-term emotional attachment to patients and the expanding professional networks, become more noticeable. The Middle Phase also saw the fervent pursuit of work role confidence by advancing critical thinking and clinical skills. These findings suggest that a high degree of engagement in transition was on-going despite the formal qualification of “Extended Care Paramedic” or “Community Paramedic” has been bestowed after successful completion of initial training. The Middle Phase has highlighted aspects of role transition that has implications for policy (the importance of OHCPs inclusion), and practice (self-regulated learning and deliberate practice). Both are integral to the overall transition experience and warrant further investigation.

Chapter 8: Late Phase – The Advanced Practitioner

8.1 INTRODUCTION

The final developmental phase in the transition from traditional to community paramedicine was the Late Phase, subtitled “Advanced Practitioner”. In the language of clinical discourse, the term “Advanced” was selected to imply the practitioner had progressed to a high level of work role proficiency, but not yet “expert” status. However, participants’ definition of the end-point point of transition was nebulous. At the end of the Late Phase, the majority of participants defined successful transition by a subjective sense of work role “comfort” or “confidence”. Others refuted the existence of an end-point of transition altogether. Thus, defining the end-point of transition was integral to the participants’ overall understanding of transition. Moreover, each of the four core categories contributed ancillary marker(s) of transition which identified the end-point in the evolution of a core category. The combination of ancillary markers from each of the four categories defined the conceptual end-point of the overall transition experience: *Adequate proficiency*.

8.2 UNIQUE ASPECTS OF THE LATE PHASE

8.2.1 Defining the end-point of transition

At the end of the Late Phase of transition, successful transition was defined as the attainment of work role comfort/confidence. Conceptually, the Late Phase was characterised by participants striving for adequate proficiency in their work role. Herein lies the essence of defining the end-point of transition; adequate proficiency was achieved through the collective experience of the participants through each of the four core categories of transition. That is, each of the core categories had its own end-point to the Late Phase of transition, known as ancillary markers. When combined, the ancillary markers from each of the four categories defined the end-point of the

overall transition experience. In other words, the overall transition experience was wholly dependent on the evolution of the four core categories that cumulatively provided the participants with a sense of adequate proficiency in their work role. Subjectively identifying when transition occurred was therefore challenging:

But, it's a tricky area trying to find that moment of transition. And I think, because it's basically, we're on our own in the car. So, it's up to us to decide when we've transitioned. When we no longer feel like we're an amateur. And that's harder for some people than others. It does mean that you need to be very proactive with reflective practice, and with clinical governance, with getting those discussions happening with other people, to make sure that you're doing it right. (P24)

For most participants, adequate proficiency was subjectively described as a function of work role comfort: "It's comfortability (sic), but you're not in a position where you feel like you know everything, and that's all mundane from that point." (P24). However, for a few others, a more objective rendering of successful transition was provided. The following example, suggests that mentoring novice ECPs/CPs was one such objective portrayal of successful transition:

I guess, it might be a subconscious thing or not, you realise all of a sudden, junior ECPs will start asking you your thoughts, with questions. And you go, 'Hang on, they're looking to me, they're looking up to me.' I guess, that can be one of the signs that you've transitioned; that you're the one doing the mentoring versus being mentored. (P97)

Although participants acknowledged that their practice had progressed to an advanced phase, they were also aware of their limitations. For example, the following ECP/CP rejects the term "expert":

I would hate to say that we're 'experts' at any point in time. I would say 'seasoned'. I wouldn't say you're ever an expert. If you've made it to that point, then you're not really striving for anything more, but seasoned where you have enough within your typical trunk that you can withdraw from it a lot easier than when you first start out. (P72)

The time taken for ECPs/CPs to transition successfully varied. If transition is defined by the achievement of adequate proficiency, most participants speculated transition took between six months and three years. The reasons for the disparity in the time involved were multifactorial. One reason was that the progress in transitioning was dependent on how the individual interacted with the core categories of transition. Another reason was the influence exerted by “accelerators and decelerators” of transition, discussed in the following chapter. Thus, all participants engaged with the core categories of transition to varying degrees. However, influences such as educational background, engagement in clinical governance activities and exposure to ECP/CP-specific work volume contributed to individualising the pathway to transition and therefore, the time taken to transition.

Importantly, some participants argued that the work role in community paramedicine was a continually evolving process, therefore no true end-point of transition existed. In the following passage, the continuous introduction of new skills is suggested as the reason for an unattainable end-point of transition:

I would say you get to a comfortable point. But then I think at the point of comfort is when typically, there's something new introduced. For instance, lab draws⁴⁴. We get to a point of comfort with them, but now we're being challenged by recognising and treating point-of-care⁴⁵ stuff. So, we're delving into that area. Like blood transfusions, that's a whole new realm. Within community, we may get comfortable within that, but then they'll add a different product and that will challenge us all over again to learn more. So, I wouldn't say there's a definitive transition. It's an ongoing thing but you start to get comfortable with certain things within the transition. (P72)

The data did not provide any perceptible differences in the progression of transition among participants who could define an end-point and those who

⁴⁴ Taking blood from a patient and sending it away for laboratory testing.

⁴⁵ Taking blood from a patient and conducting laboratory tests at the bedside using a handheld device.

could not. However, most agreed continual professional development was necessary to maintain currency:

I think there is a dynamic learning environment that is always going to be there. But as far as an end-point, it would be confidence and knowing that the safety of what I am doing is maintained. (P80)

Sufficient data existed to explain the shared experience of transition amongst the participants. Ultimately however, the issue as to whether a universally agreed end-point of transition existed among participants may simply be a matter of semantics. From the issue surrounding the existence of an end-point of transition, the concept of cycling-in-and-out of transition had emerged.

8.2.2 Cycling in-and-out of the end-point of transition

An unexpected finding during the analysis was an ECP's/CP's ability to cycle in-and-out of the end-point of transition. For some participants, successful transition (defined as achieving adequate proficiency in the work role) was not a singular event. Broadly speaking, the ECP/CP role was viewed as a continually evolving position, requiring close adherence to professional development activities in order to maintain adequate proficiency. If, for example, a level of adequate proficiency in the role was not maintained, the paramedic could cycle out of the end-point of transition. It would then be incumbent upon the paramedic to re-engage in the transition process, to once again achieve adequate proficiency and thus achieve successful transition. In the following passage, the participant explains why the ECP/CP role was continually evolving:

The ECP role is ever evolving, we're constantly adding new techniques, new devices, new everything, so that transition is never truly over, but you definitely get more comfortable within your role. (P72)

In essence, the argument for paramedics cycling in-and-out of transition shared a similar aetiology to the argument for an absence of an end-point of transition. That is, both arguments were premised on the continual evolution

of the ECP/CP work role. The following excerpt explains how the work role can change over time:

...if you're not working as an Extended Care Paramedic for a while, if you had two years off without doing the role, you'd come back and it'd be a very different role. Because, management and the community, different expectations, or different pathways⁴⁶, and it's a constantly evolving role in this state [jurisdiction]. (P03)

Viewed differently, the knowledge and skills acquired through initial training and the transition experience, were only valid in maintaining adequate proficiency for a fixed period of time. With the introduction of new knowledge and skills providing a more targeted service to the community, the point of achieving adequate proficiency shifted:

And there's a whole lot of people around the area that have done the course a few years ago, and you can already see that their skills and confidence is dwindling. You know, you'll back them up sometimes, and they'll go, 'Look, I had this shoulder [dislocation], but I just wasn't confident popping it back in. I knew you were around the area, can you just give us a hand?' So, you do start to lose your skills, definitely. (P40)

Thus, degradation of clinical skills, such as reducing a dislocated shoulder or catheterising a patient, was one of the tell-tale signs of cycling out of transition:

I think it'd been probably two years, since I'd been on ECP car dedicated dispatch to ECP. And of course, I get a catheter. At least it was a male one, it's obvious where it has to go. But, you should have seen it. It was horrible. I built the sterile field incorrectly, and I threw my gloves across the room, I was so annoyed with myself. I thought I was at least competent and safe at it, but I don't think I was very good at it. Luckily, the patient was demented, and didn't really see me swearing at myself, having to sit there and stare at the equipment for

⁴⁶ Pathways provide guidance in clinical practice.

a minute, going, 'Okay. What do I need?' And it was seriously back to complete novice. (P97)

However, cycling-in-and-out of transition was not a phenomenon experienced by all participants. The more susceptible participants were those who were employed on a casual basis or were often engaged in other work roles, such as traditional paramedicine. The results highlight the relative importance of continuing professional development with respect to cycling out of transition. Additionally, further research is required to better understand the requisite conditions for paramedics to cycle out of transition.

8.3 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The ancillary marker of transition for the community of practice was *equalising relationships with OHCPs*. Notably, equalising relationships was also contingent on a successful parallel transition of OHCPs experienced during the Middle Phase. Following successful OHCP transition, collegial relationships matured between paramedics and OHCPs, to the point where both parties were mutually respectful of the contribution each could bring to patient care. The following interaction between paramedic and doctor, recollected by a participant, serves as an exemplar for the Late Phase community of practice:

And now we're at the point where - and the doctors are 100% supportive in the fact - we'll say to them, 'This is what we've got', and they'll say, 'Well what do you want to do? What do you think would be a good idea?' And we'll say, 'We'll have about 10 days of Levaquin [antibiotic] and we'll do a repeat chest x-ray.' And they'll be like, 'Yes sure, but do the x-ray first.' You get more of like an on-level discussion instead of doctor being up here and paramedic being down here. (P08)

Another ECP/CP conveyed the common sentiments of other paramedics in defining the collaborative relationship with OHCPs, "...for the first time in my career as a paramedic I feel like I'm looked at as a medical colleague, versus just that of a paramedic or that ambulance driver." (P46) ECPs/CPs also experienced trust and respect which exceeded that offered to them in their

traditional paramedic role. Attaining collegial trust and respect also served as a marker of transition:

But in terms of transition, there is that point where I realised that he [a doctor] trusted me and he trusted my assessment. It was reciprocal I guess, and at that point I realised that he was not going to tell me I was useless and I could not do the job. The relationship became a really collaborative thing. I think I noticed that was when I was more of a ECP than just an ICP. (P77)

Thus, equalising relationships between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs was manifested as mutual trust and respect. In turn, the ECP/CP role was seen by OHCPs as having value and garnered acceptance. Continuing further, acceptance was significant to reinforce in the minds of OHCPs the niche in the healthcare system that community paramedicine serviced:

...so knowing you are accepted and your role is respected and is seen to be of value is very important. A lot of people early on didn't know what it was going to look like, so we had to give it time to breathe, to grow a bit. But they realised that this is something that only we can own. Some other agency is not going to come along, even community nursing, which is probably our closest comparison I guess. (P16)

Ultimately, the fact that the relationships were equalised through trust, respect, and acceptance from OHCPs, allowed ECPs/CPs to develop work role confidence. In effect, the data described a feedback cycle between equalising relationships and ECP/CP confidence (Figure 8.1). That is, an increase in ECP/CP confidence advanced the equality of relationships between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs, which in turn, further increased the confidence of ECPs/CPs. Through ECP/CP confidence, OHCPs were made

Figure 8.1 Community of practice feedback cycle

more aware of the collaborative role ECPs/CPs played in improving patient outcomes, thereby garnering further trust and respect from OHCPs. Of great significance to the transition experience in the community of practice feedback cycle, was the emergence of ECP/CP *work role comfort/confidence*, a commonly reported measure of successful transition.

The following passage discusses how an increase in work role confidence (e.g. presenting information to a doctor without prompting) allows the doctor to trust in the paramedic’s ability to provide accurate clinical assessment and give appropriate instructions to the patient:

If the CP presents the needed information without prompting, I find the physician is far more confident/comfortable in providing orders [instructions] for a patient. Our program encourages our CPs to actually propose treatment plans when confident for what is indicated. For example, we’ll report, ‘60 y/o male, two-day history of redness and unilateral swelling to lower right leg, with skin breakage, cellulitis appearance, no previous MRSA or tests. I’d like to start him on Keflex, 500 mg PO QID for 10 days.’ This requires that we have a more in

depth understanding of pathophysiology and pharmacology than provided in our traditional EMS education. (P83)

During the Late Phase of transition, ECP/CP work role confidence within the community of practice meant more than an intuitive feeling about one's own practice. While it is beyond the scope of this thesis to engage in discourse analysis, it is evident that the participant's views, as quoted below, show confidence with his assertive prose:

So it's more of just having that confidence to say, 'I know what I'm doing here.' And the doctors, RNs, and physicians that work with us, a lot of the time I do the assessment and then I phone up and say, 'Okay, this is what I've got. This is what I'm thinking...' (P08)

Finally, the metamorphosis of the community of practice into its final rendering occurred during the Late Phase. In previous phases of transition, the community of practice largely served as an educative and supportive structure for learner ECPs/CPs. In the Late Phase, the focus of the community of practice shifts markedly to ECPs/CPs engaging collaboratively with OHCP on a more equal level. That is to say, ECPs/CPs had reached such a level of confidence in their work roles, that it was no longer necessary to contact other clinicians for reassurance prior to enacting a treatment plan:

That is when I believe you really have done the complete transition. It doesn't matter what happens during the day. You don't have to make a lot of phone calls to ask a lot of questions. For me most the time when I call for advice it is like, I am in a situation and I know what I am supposed to do but I always make that phone call to check and say, 'What do you think about this? This is what has happened'. (P50)

These findings suggest the contribution of the community of practice to the overall transition experience for paramedics was significant. Through engagement in a community of practice, participants were provided with a vehicle to develop comfort/confidence in their work roles via a feedback loop with OHCPs. Counterintuitively, confidence was also manifested in the community of practice by ECPs/CPs requiring less communication with colleagues to validate patient management options. The metamorphosis of the

community of practice through the transition experience was supported similarly through a changed organisational and cultural milieu. In the next section, for example, it is apparent that organisational culture supported the integration of paramedics into healthcare teams.

8.4 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

The Late Phase of transition was a time of final organisational and cultural adjustments. In doing so, ECPs/CPs were well positioned to observe the gap widening between the two work cultures. The following participant conceptualised the cultural shift in terms of a change in the philosophical approach or “mentality” to service delivery in community paramedicine:

It's a very different culture [from traditional paramedicine]. [Community paramedicine] is a lot more supportive. A lot more open with discussion of cases. It's just this mentality of on-road [traditional care] where it's my way or the highway. If you're treating, everyone shuts up. You have all power. If you make a decision, it's a decision that happens. There's no feedback and there's no communication on scene. It's slowly moving away from that to be perfectly honest. (P12)

The significance of ECPs/CPs embracing the organisational and cultural change in community paramedicine, as evidenced by a change in philosophical approach to service delivery, serves as an ancillary marker of transition. In other words, a changed philosophical approach to service delivery in community paramedicine became an integral component for the participant to achieve a subjective sense of comfort/confidence and adequate proficiency. Another participant encapsulated the philosophical shift towards shedding traditional care perspectives on healthcare needs:

So, I think to be successful and to really flourish in this role, you have to stop looking at your patients from an EMS perspective. By that I mean, the patient is looked at purely from whether or not they need the emergency department or whether they have a healthcare need. Some people, I think through both experience and just temperament, were more likely to shed that EMS perspective quickly. I think we all, including myself, went into this transition with still that very strong EMS

perspective. But I think some of us shed it more quickly, and embraced the fact, 'I'm just going to look at my patient for their healthcare, and we'll supply that healthcare need.' And that is a successful patient event. (P83)

Others supported the remarks of their colleagues in describing the philosophical shift of service delivery from traditional paramedicine to community paramedicine as a “full on mental switch” (P33) or as a change in “mindset that we're no longer going to be headed out to deal with a crisis versus integrating healthcare” (P46). In the following passage, the participant provided a salient example of the change in mindset to community paramedicine and the contribution to work role comfort:

I think changing your mindset alone can make you a little more comfortable. Whereas working 911 [emergency care], you are basically there to identify any immediate life threatening problems and get the patient to the hospital. In other words, you are there to help people live. This sounds a little weird but in community [paramedicine], sometimes you are there to help people die. I just mean that palliative care call is for me where things really changed. Because I am so uncomfortable in that situation. As a paramedic, I feel like I am there to ventilate⁴⁷, to start IVs⁴⁸, to help people live. Then you realise, everyone dies, we all die, this person does not want to step foot in a hospital for the rest of their life. They are happy if they die tonight, they just want to be helped or they just want to be comfortable. Or they may literally be palliative and have cancer and dying and you are just there to deal with symptom management and to make them comfortable. Maybe give pain control and be comfortable in that situation to realise this is not an emergency situation anymore. There is a lot of them out there. It's different, at least it was for me. (P31)

The change in service delivery philosophy during the Late Phase was also manifested in the absence of professional egos. Put differently, participants

⁴⁷ Assist the patient to breathe.

⁴⁸ Insertion of a plastic tube into a patient's vein to administer drugs or fluids.

described a high level of “team spirit” and absence of professional arrogance: “There were no egos [in the team], so that was good. There was no arrogance, there was just a team spirit and that is inclusive of us and of everybody else.” (P16). This cultural shift in community paramedicine was evident in the following passage:

I’ve phoned brand new ECPs and asked them their opinion, because I don’t know what I’m doing. And that’s great. Just because I’ve got a few more years’ extra experience doesn’t mean I know everything. And some of us might have some new piece of information to shine a light on. (P24)

The cultural shift that occurs between the Early and Late Phases of transition, including the development of a team spirit, may be contextualised as an *esprit de corps*. The sense of team belonging and commitment to a unified objective had a substantial influence on accelerating the transition process for participants. Other accelerators and decelerators of the transition process will be discussed further in the subsequent chapter.

8.5 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

As with the other core categories, the final rendering of critical thinking in the Late Phase was the result of the culmination of previous phases. The defining qualities of critical thinking in the Late Phase also contributed markedly to a conceptualisation of successful transition. Broadly speaking, two defining qualities of critical thinking in the Late Phase were evident and served as ancillary markers of transition: *recognising subconscious thought* and the seamless ability to “flip” between *high-acuity and low-acuity roles*.

During the Late Phase, participants spoke of an ability to “subconsciously” formulate patient management plans. That is, the ability of participants, without conscious perception, to make weighted judgments in the best interests of the patient, via the integration of numerous clinical and non-clinical variables. The extract below elaborated on subconscious thought processes in community paramedicine:

I think when you're making decisions subconsciously...you're already forming a visual diagnosis in your head, and you're already thinking two, and three steps ahead. And you're doing that all concurrently, and it's all happening subconsciously. I guess that's probably that end-point when you know you've transitioned. (P97)

Another participant continued to further illuminate the non-clinical variables involved in critical thinking. Importantly, the participant also connected Late Phase critical thinking with successful transition:

...it's more than just simply the medical emergency or the medical ailment. There's sometimes family dynamics, there's the environment that they live in, it's their cultural background, where they came from. It's so multi-dimensional that I think there are so many unknowns. If you are comfortable walking into all those unknowns all the time and knowing that you're going to deliver care to your patient, that made their situation better after you've been there, then I guess that's the transition. That's the confidence that I have. That I know I'm going to find some means to give them a direction. (P46)

By the Late Phase of transition, participant work role experience in community paramedicine had played a significant part in the evolution of each core category. For one participant, pattern recognition developed through experience was integral to the development of critical thinking skills:

I think when I can approach a situation competently because I've experienced similar types of issues in patients in the past and I have spoken with a physician over similar types of problems. If I've come up with an amicable treatment plan that has worked out well, I think I tend to be more confident and more comfortable. I feel like I'm definitely doing an excellent job and really providing a good service for the patient. (P31)

For others though, articulating a true sense of what constitutes an advanced level of critical thinking was problematic; one participant blithely offered, "it's the vibe of the thing" (P97). However, as the concluding sentence

in the extract below implies, critical thinking for some ECPs/CPs was an intuitive practice:

Every patient is different, and every pathway is. And so I think, if you're comfortable with that, if you recognise that you're not going to know what to do with every case, but you have plans of how to safely navigate that, that adds to the feeling of comfortability, and having transitioned. Knowing what to do, if you don't know what to do. (P24)

Achieving an advanced level of critical thinking skills was significant to the overall transition experience by assisting in defining the end-point of transition. In other words, achieving an advanced level of critical thinking was commensurate with achieving a high level of work role comfort/confidence. In the following passage, developing confidence (drawn from foundational clinical skills in patient assessment) is connected with critical thinking skills:

Paramedics learn a systematic approach to patient assessments and treatments that enables them to find a confident flow in a sense. That confidence grows into an ability to be an independent critical thinker. This is magnified in Community Paramedics. Exceptional critical thinking enables and supports patient care, in collaboration/consultation with a physician, and assists us in anticipating what, when and why a care plan should or could be executed. (P33)

The higher-level thinking skills evident throughout the Late Phase were also apparent in the paramedic's ability to "mind flip" between community paramedicine and traditional care. The mind flip refers to a change in the paramedic's service delivery mindset, that is, switching between delivering care with a community paramedicine focus or a traditional care focus. Additionally, the learned ability to flip between mindsets was of greater relevance to the ECP model of care in NSW and South Australia. The ECP model utilised ECPs as an acute (urgent) care resource and subsequently could be dispatched to high-acuity cases that have traditionally been the core business of the paramedic service. The Community Paramedic model in Alberta did not utilise CPs in the same manner, unless the paramedics happened across a case

requiring immediate intervention, such as a cardiac arrest. In the following excerpt, the participant discussed the change in mindset when attending an ECP-appropriate case:

...if you can determine within a few minutes whether or not it [the patient's presentation] is ECP-appropriate, your mind flips. It is a genuine flip of your state of mind and you go into a far more holistic and less logistical mindset...It is that process of thinking and how you set up your brain to deal with a patient. Whether or not the case is time critical, are very different ways of thinking in a sense. And that is that switch that I was talking about. (P49)

Recalling a conversation with a colleague, the next participant elaborated on the mind flip, suggesting a successful ECP required two "brains". In the passage, the traditional paramedic care mindset was likened to an "ED-brain" and the community paramedicine mindset was the "GP-brain":

He [a colleague] calls it 'the two brains'. So he reckons to be a good ECP, you need a good ED-brain and a good GP-brain. He said that you have got to be able to walk into a situation and know when you to use your ED-brain and when you should use your GP-brain. They're totally different brains. (P35)

The ability to shift between "two brains" was certainly recognised as a transformative process. The above participant continued, "I mean, this is what is fun about mentoring ICPs in to ECPs. You get to see this [shift between two brains] and you get to watch them grow and develop. And that is a very special thing." (P35) Additionally, another participant also ascribed to a transition in thinking between ICP and ECP-roles:

But now, because I do more ECP, I've got time [on scene with the patient]. Whereas I see the ICP [role] as a time poor, where they need to do all these interventions that are high risk, in a hurry. We need to pack this patient up, and we need to get going in 20 minutes or so, depending on what's going on. So, I find I actually have to take a step back and think, to transition back into that kind of thinking. (P41)

Work role confidence enabled the participant to alternate between providing high-acuity and low-acuity care. Mastering skills was an integral component in developing confidence and accelerated the overall transition experience.

8.6 MASTERING SKILLS

By the Late Phase of transition, most participants had achieved a skill level commensurate with achieving an overall sense of adequate proficiency in their work roles. Competency in skills, mostly forged during the earlier phases of transition, was largely due to *repetition and experience*, “It comes back down to a frequency. If you are doing a skill for sterile fields frequently, then absolutely you are going to have a quicker transition in to being confident in doing that for sure” (P80). As for experience, “that transition to me, is probably a mastery of your skills and knowledge. You build it up to the phase where you’re comfortable in applying that skill and knowledge, because you’ve got the experience.” (P13)

Unlike the other three core categories, ancillary markers for *Mastering Skills* during the Late Phase were characterised by participants engaging primarily in the processes of *consolidation* and *skill maintenance*. Consolidation was in part an extension of the process of skill repetition to further extend the participant’s confidence in delivering skills:

I feel confident in my skills now after a year. I think a whole other year, at least two years, when you are doing a new skill set is a really good amount of consolidation time. So for the foreseeable future, at least two years I would like to stay on the ECP car. (P55)

Participants also communicated the importance of rostered work time to engage not only in skill consolidation, but skill maintenance as well. Skill maintenance, occurring after the skill had been consolidated, maintained a level of proficiency to ensure the participant did not cycle out of transition:

...with our education days built into our roster, that’s a great way of us being able to not only consolidate our skills, but also, if there has been a skill you haven’t done in some time, you can take the opportunity to

practice that with some colleagues. Or, you can focus in on where you think you're still weak. (P97)

Another participant concurred, citing the relative importance of reviewing existing skills, along with an opportunity to examine new skills, "[Training days] are very important. Just to review skills that you may not have done for a few months. Seeing what's the latest research in point of care, all sorts of different things." (P68). Although mastering skills for most participants was centred on the clinical subset, operational skills such as attending cases as a single responder, were also of substantial importance, "I feel like I have transitioned because I don't have any anxiety at work anymore about whatever job they put on me now...I feel like I have mastered the art of single responding." (P55)

An understanding of mastering skills in the Late Phase had implications not only for the ECPs/CPs themselves, but for program managers and ECP/CP educators alike. The data suggested rostered work time was a necessary component to consolidate and maintain skills. Moreover, consolidation and skill maintenance carried the same degree of importance to the overall transition experience as the initial acquisition of skills. Furthermore, without consolidation and skill maintenance, the study showed that the paramedic was at a higher risk of cycling out of transition.

8.7 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

The Late Phase was the final phase of the transition experience, where transition was described as a point of comfort/confidence in their work role. Conceptually, the end-point of transition has been defined as achieving adequate proficiency in the ECP/CP work role, with each of the four core categories contributing ancillary markers of transition (Figure 8.2). Through the combination of all four ancillary markers of transition, the participant could achieve a subjective sense of comfort/confidence.

Figure 8.2 Ancillary markers of transition in the Late Phase

8.8 DISCUSSION OF LATE PHASE

The Late Phase of transition heralded the final steps before an ECP/CP crossed the threshold of transition to a work role in community paramedicine. Most participants reasoned transition had occurred successfully after a sense of work role “comfort” or “confidence” had been achieved. Conceptually however, the transition threshold has been defined through the participant’s collective experience of each of the four core categories of transition: the ability to elevate thinking to intuitive levels, forge collegial relationships with other professionals, embrace organisational and cultural change, and maintain the skills vital in delivering a healthcare service. Ultimately, these experiences have coalesced to define the single end-point of transition – *Adequate proficiency in the work role*.

Embedded in the term “adequate proficiency” is a subtle distancing from the new-to-practice nursing transition literature, most notably in the work of Benner (1984). Benner’s work is considered “one of the most influential books on nursing theory in recent times” (Gardner, 2012, p. 339) by introducing the

concept that novice nurses develop expertise through five stages. However, the distinctions between work roles in community paramedicine and new-to-practice nursing limits the transferability of Benner's theory. Moreover, some authors have questioned the capacity of the Dreyfus model (from which Benner is strongly influenced) to explain the acquisition of clinical problem-solving skills (Peña, 2010). In homage to Benner's seminal work, the second last stage (Stage 4) of Benner's model titled, "Proficient", was the inspiration for naming this study's final phase, "Adequate proficiency". However, herein lies a significant variance between theoretical models; Benner's last stage titled "Expert", is comparable to work role mastery, and reaches years beyond the end-point of transition to community paramedicine. Although sharing similar attributes with Benner's Expert stage, such as an intuitive and holistic appreciation of the clinical picture, participants in the current study adamantly rejected the moniker of "expert" as a marker of transition, preferring the descriptive term of achieving "comfort/confidence". True to the interpretivist foundations of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2014), comfort/confidence has been abstracted to mean, adequate proficiency in the work role.

In contrast to the new-to-practice nurse transition literature, the difference between nurse practitioner transition and community paramedicine transition narrows. Barnes (2014, p. 6), for instance, arguably a leading author in the scholarship of nurse practitioner transition, cites Meleis, Sawyer, Im, Messias, and Schumacher (2000) in defining the outcome of transition as "a subjective sense of well-being, increased confidence and competence, good connections with others, mastery of skills, and autonomous practice." A number of these elements are concordant with achieving adequate proficiency in the ECP/CP work role. Significantly, the term "confidence", found to be a key marker of transition in the current study and evident in the definition above, also features prominently as a marker of transition in other studies of nurse practitioner transition (Cusson & Strange, 2008; Maylone, et al., 2011; Mercer, 2007; Poronsky, 2013).

The comparable outcomes between nurse practitioner transition and that of community paramedicine transition, particularly the pursuit of work role confidence, suggest a degree of transferability from nursing to community paramedicine. In simple terms, transferability is achieved when the story of one study resonates with another study (Tracy, 2010). However, the transferability of findings should be interpreted with caution as the journey through transition varies between disciplines. For instance, Barton (2007a) speaks of nurse practitioners disengaging from their previous role as a registered nurse. In contrast, ECPs, and to a lesser extent CPs, are required to be functional in dual roles. That is, in a traditional care paramedic role and a community paramedicine role. Consequently, closer scrutiny of nurse practitioner theory is warranted in terms of its transferability to the community paramedicine setting.

Cycling in-and-out of transition is another illustration of how the participants rationalised the differences between the transition to community paramedicine and other work role transitions in paramedicine. Participants viewed the role of an ECP/CP as being in a state of continual evolution due to the constant introduction of new knowledge, clinical procedures and experiences. For this reason, some participants felt that there was no definable end-point to transition. Cycling in-and-out of transition has not featured predominantly elsewhere in the general transition literature, as cycling out of transition implied the event occurred *after* transition was achieved. In this sense, cycling in-and-out of transition is a post-transition event and therefore not part of the transition experience. However, the analysis of this study's results suggests that cycling out of the end-point of transition (adequate proficiency), followed by re-acquiring adequate proficiency, is a valid extension of the transition experience.

It is possible that cycling in-and-out of transition is not a unique finding in transition theory and is, more likely, a matter of semantics. Maintaining adequate proficiency in the work role is essentially a function of continuous professional development (CPD) and clinical skill maintenance. Certainly, CPD has been demonstrated previously as a necessity for paramedics to maintain

currency and safety of practice (Deakin, et al., 2009; Gent, 2016) and forms the foundation of lifelong learning in other health professions (Eason, 2010). The contribution of this research however, is to emphasise the significance of CPD and skill maintenance in post-transition practice, to ensure that the ECPs/CPs do not slide backwards out of adequate proficiency. CPD and skill maintenance is discussed in greater detail later in this chapter.

8.9 ENGAGING IN A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

The rendition of the community of practice in the Late Phase presented in stark contrast to the relatively simplistic framework articulated during the Early Phase. The Late Phase community of practice was forged through an interplay of ECPs/CPs earning trust and respect, along with being accepted and valued by OHCPs. Complemented by the sub-transition of OHCPs during the Middle Phase (and continued to an extent during the Late Phase), relationships between OHCPs and ECP/CPs equalised. Subsequently, equalising relationships increased ECP/CP work role confidence, thereby facilitating the transition process.

The current study contributes significantly to the understanding of the dynamic interplay between trust, respect and acceptance in the equalising of relationships between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs. Although the need for collaborative networks is well established in community paramedicine (Choi, et al., 2016; Reaburn, Zolcinski, & Fyfe, 2017; Thompson, et al., 2014), most publications lack detail on *how* these relationships are formed. However, in a recent study examining the association between public engagement and the integration of a community paramedicine program, O'Meara, et al. (2016) briefly noted that the degree of trust a doctor afforded a paramedic could impact the integration of paramedic services into the community. However, the issue of trust apparently did not resonate with most of the other participants in that study. The finding of O'Meara, et al. (2015) is in direct contrast to the current study, which highlights the development of interprofessional trust as an integral element in the development of an interprofessional community of practice.

Moreover, the findings of the current study are closely aligned with previous investigations of interprofessional relationships in cognate health fields. For instance, Pullon (2008) studied 18 nurses and doctors working in a primary care setting in New Zealand and developed a theoretical model of the development of interprofessional trust (Figure 8.3). The keystones of Pullon's model drew many parallels to the development of an ECP/CP community of practice including that interprofessional trust had to be earned rather than automatically given, that an understanding of roles leads to mutual respect, and that mutual respect in turn leads to interprofessional trust. It was also shown that professional competence (credibility) was essential in the development of trust.

In comparing both models, the centrality of developing trust and respect within an interprofessional dynamic is highlighted across two related health professions. It should be noted however, that although the current study supports Pullon's findings, the transferability of findings to paramedicine should be considered judiciously. Pullon's model was focused on understanding the development of interprofessional trust between nurses and doctors, whereas the current study aims to understand how the interplay of trust, respect and acceptance facilitate the development of work role confidence.

Figure 8.3 The development of interprofessional trust. Adapted from "Competence, respect and trust: Key features of successful interprofessional nurse-doctor relationships," Pullon, S., 2008, *Journal of Interprofessional Care* 22(2), p. 143

Knowledge of interprofessional collaboration to improve patient healthcare outcomes is well established (Gilbert, Yan, & Hoffman, 2010). However, the manner in which collaboration is implemented carries nuanced differences throughout various health professions, affected by policy makers, organisational managers, care teams and the health professionals themselves (Mulvale, Embrett, & Razavi, 2016). This research has reaffirmed the importance of fostering mutual trust, respect and acceptance in the development of an interprofessional community of practice. Given the wide diversity in how collaboration is conceptualised (D'Amour, Ferrada-Videla, San Martin Rodriguez, & Beaulieu, 2005), this study is timely in that it may assist in the development of a formalised community of practice framework between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs.

8.10 ADJUSTING TO ORGANISATIONAL AND CULTURAL CHANGE

The current study has found that the journey involved in the transition from a traditional paramedicine culture to that of a community paramedicine setting was considerable. The description by participants of their experiences in traditional paramedicine aligned with those previously reported elsewhere in the literature: a command and control culture with a tendency to blame, hierarchical and resistant to change (Wankhade & Brinkman, 2014). In contrast, the culture within the ECP/CP programs during the Late Phase was seen to be supportive, collegial and open, being consistent with some other community paramedicine programs (Thompson, et al., 2014). Moreover, participants described the approach to service provision as a “mental switch”, referring to a service delivery mindset realigned with the philosophy underpinning community paramedicine.

The mental switch professed by some participants was akin to achieving an enhanced sense of role clarity. That is not to say though that participants entered their respective programs naively. Rather, by the Late Phase of transition, participants were cognisant of their unique niche within the healthcare system and their contribution to the patient’s outcomes. The significance of role clarity can perhaps be best understood when contrasted with the approach of traditional care paramedics to low-acuity work.

Many traditional care paramedics perceive their role in terms of responding to emergencies and providing care to patients with life-threatening conditions (Brydges, Spearen, Birze, & Tavares, 2015; Devenish, et al., 2016; Lazarsfeld-Jensen, 2014). Thus, providing non-acute long-term care is perceived to be contradictory to the traditional core business of paramedic services. Moreover, the measurement of organisational performance has been weighted disproportionately towards response times (urgency of an ambulance call-out) rather than patient outcomes (Wankhade & Brinkman, 2014). In contrast, ECPs/CPs maintain a different perception of their role in that patient outcomes are a paramount focus. This “cultural reset” within community paramedicine has been described elsewhere in the literature (Martin, et al.,

2015; Simpson, et al., 2017; Thompson, et al., 2014) and significantly, denotes an acceptance of organisational and cultural change.

The change in service delivery philosophy also extended to an absence of professional ego. In other words, participants discarded the learned culture of professional “arrogance” in traditional paramedicine and embraced an elevated level of team commitment and belonging. Contextualised as an *esprit de corps*, this sense of team spirit contributed significantly to the degree of occupational engagement and commitment to the participant’s respective programs. Commitment in turn, has engendered perceptions of job satisfaction, involvement, and retention (Alexander, 2009; Lum, Kervin, Clark, Reid, & Sirola, 1998). Furthermore, workforce sustainability has been linked to positive transformative changes in paramedic culture, particularly in new-to-practice paramedics (Lazarsfeld-Jensen, et al., 2014).

In achieving the “mental switch” shedding of professional ego and the culmination of previous phases, participants attained the ancillary marker of transition: embracing organisational and cultural change. An understanding of the cultural change process better illuminates the constructs that facilitate the transition process. ECP/CP educators and program managers may subsequently be better equipped to design initiatives that maximise employee engagement. Examples include encouraging ECPs/CPs to solve work-related problems on their own, develop new skills, and participate in decision-making processes (May, Gilson, & Harter, 2004; Rana, et al., 2014). Further research should consider the effects of other variables impacting on organisational and cultural change such as the level of education (Alexander, 2009) and social support needs (Alexander, 2009; Ng & Sorensen, 2008).

8.11 DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

By the Late Phase of transition, critical thinking had been elevated to a sub-conscious process. Participants described an ability to seamlessly formulate patient management plans that incorporated numerous non-clinical variables in a relatively brief period of time. In other words, the advanced level

of critical thinking achieved by the participants was comparable to intuitive practice.

The discussion of intuitive practice in the paramedicine literature is limited. Although numerous studies have demonstrated ECPs/CPs are capable of sound clinical risk decisions suggestive of intuitive practices (Coates, Rawstorne, & Bengner, 2012; Jensen, Marshall, et al., 2016; Ruest, Stitchman, & Day, 2014), the discussion is often focused on patient outcomes rather than cognitive processes. Snooks et al. (2005) however undertook a study to examine the decision-making processes of traditional care paramedics using non-conveyance protocols⁴⁹. The participants spoke of an intuitive “sixth sense”, combined with knowledge and experience, to make clinical risk decisions. However, Snooks fails to expand further on how intuition is developed.

Intuition has received significantly more attention across other disciplines, including nursing. Whilst difficult to quantify and measure (English, 1993), most definitions of intuition include, rapid perception (pattern recognition), lack of awareness of the process engaged, presence of emotions and a holistic understanding of the situation (Benner & Tanner, 1987; Chilcote, 2017; Gobet & Chassy, 2008). Participants in the current study satisfied these criteria in the Late Phase to claim intuitive practices. Moreover, the intuitive practices demonstrated by the participants align with Benner’s seminal work of nursing expertise (Benner, 1984). However, questions persist concerning the role of intuition in clinical decision making, given the advent of evidenced-based guidelines and preference for more linear thinking processes (Chilcote, 2017).

Cognitive psychologists have generally considered intuition to be synonymous with heuristics (Pretz, 2008). Heuristic thinking is a form of “mental shortcut”, a type of thinking that is rapid, contextual, holistic and

⁴⁹ Non-conveyance protocols allowed paramedics to assess and triage patients to self-care and/or primary care or community-based services (Snooks, et al., 2005).

rooted in emotions (Chilcote, 2017; Norman, 2009). The value of heuristics is that it can be economical, resourceful and an effective clinical decision-making tool when used by an experienced clinician (Croskerry, 2002). However, intuition is prone to errors, otherwise known as cognitive biases. Emotions, for instance, are known to affect intuition (Benner, 1984; Gobet & Chassy, 2008).

In a study of paramedic decision making when caring for older people who have fallen, Simpson, et al. (2017) noted paramedic heuristic decision making was affected by the negative perception of the patient's presentation. In other words, cognitive biases occur due to the paramedic's role perception that an elderly person who has fallen did not constitute an "appropriate" emergency requiring a paramedic response. However, the same study also noted that ECPs perceived falls as a "legitimate" caseload. Further to Simpson et al's argument, the absence of negative perceptions of the ECP/CP role, combined with the experienced background of the ECP/CP cohort, suggests heuristic or intuitive practice has a legitimate place in community paramedicine.

Certainly, there will always be a requirement for more conscious, logical and linear thinking, particularly in regard to the application of evidence-based practices (Chilcote, 2017). However "flesh-and-blood" clinical intuition and clinical acumen still play an important role in the decision making process (Croskerry, 2002, p. 1202). The implications for community paramedicine is to encourage trainee ECPs/CPs and accompanying educators to use intuitive practices as part of patient care. However, the use of intuition should still be validated through established clinical governance pathways.

A further manifestation of intuitive practice described by participants include the seamless ability to "mind flip" between high-acuity and low-acuity cases attended by ECPs. This implies the ability to rapidly judge a patient's presentation as either requiring traditional (high-acuity) interventions or community paramedicine interventions. This finding has not been reported elsewhere in the literature and represents a unique contribution to paramedicine. Previous publications in the nursing literature have canvassed

blended clinical nurse specialist and nurse practitioner roles (Hanson & Hamric, 2003). However, ECP is unique in the clear duality of component roles. That is, the ECP role is a combination of both a traditional care role and community paramedicine role.

An understanding of the implications of the duality of roles under the ECP auspice has been lacking in both the literature and by paramedic services. Consequently, the ability for an ECP to rapidly change service delivery mindsets has not been reflected either in ECP training or in continuing professional development programs. This research encourages program planners and managers to view the ECP role as dual roles. Additionally, although a preliminary conclusion suggests the mind flip between high-acuity and low-acuity was facilitated by intuitive practices, further research is required to better understand how the process occurs.

8.12 MASTERING SKILLS

The final component in the Mastering Skills core category was the consolidation and maintenance of procedural skills. Participants considered consolidation an extension of skill repetition. Simply put, the more often a skill was performed, the more proficient the ECP/CP became. Continuing from the Middle Phase, consolidation via repetition was dependent on the sporadic capture of ECP/CP-specific cases, discussed further in the following chapter. Skill maintenance, however, carried greater complexities.

The analysed findings indicated concern over procedural skill decay, that is, the loss of some or all of a skill necessary to perform a procedure after a period of non-use (Wang, et al., 2008). The issue is significant because ECPs/CPs were expected to perform skills that may be used infrequently. Moreover, skill decay was a principal reason for participants to cycle out of transition. In other words, participants lost confidence in their ability to perform in the ECP/CP work role following a loss of skill acumen. The issue of dual roles for ECPs is therefore significant as the maintenance of both high-acuity and low-acuity skill sets was dependent largely on the nature of the cases ECPs attend. A heavier loading of high-acuity cases, for instance, may

result in a loss of confidence in ECP-specific skills. Conversely, loading of “appropriate” ECP-specific cases could result in the decay of a high-acuity skill set.

Loss of confidence in performing specific ECP/CP clinical skills and, to a lesser extent, loss of traditional care skills, are consistent with previous reporting of community paramedicine programs (Thompson, et al., 2014). Maintenance of skills requires deliberate practice (Ericsson, 2004), an often cited method for skill maintenance in paramedicine is via continuing professional development (CPD) (Deakin, et al., 2009). Gent (2016) has recently argued for a cultural shift in paramedicine to drive CPD ownership through the individual learner. The current study has demonstrated that a high degree of ownership and investment exists amongst the ECP/CP cohort, concomitant with embracing cultural change. Thus ECPs/CPs are well placed to utilise CPD in skill maintenance.

The challenge for ECP/CP educators and program managers is to be cognisant of the contribution of CPD, not only in the prevention of procedural skill delay but also in preventing ECPs/CPs from cycling-out of transition. Additionally, whilst operational demands exist, ECPs/CPs should be afforded the time to consolidate and maintain skills. Previous studies have examined timelines for clinical skill decay in medicine (Wang, et al., 2008). Further studies in community paramedicine would similarly be well advised to acquire a better understanding of the timing for ECP/CP-specific skill decay.

8.13 CONCLUSION

The Late Phase of transition represented the culmination of the transition experience. In a linear process that is built on the evolution of the core categories in the previous phases of transition, an ECP/CP practitioner emerges comfortable and confident in their work role. Moreover, the ECPs/CPs acquired a heightened awareness of their niche within the healthcare system, were able to reason intuitively, operated within a sophisticated interprofessional community of practice and were adept at procedural skills. An understanding of the Late Phase and its constituent parts will better inform trainee ECPs/CPs,

educators and other stakeholders of the strategies that will achieve transition in the shortest time frame. Additionally, by defining the end-point of transition, ECPs/CPs gain a common yardstick with which to gauge their progress towards transition.

Chapter 9: Accelerators and Decelerators of the Transition Experience

9.1 INTRODUCTION

Having examined the phases of transition, Chapter 9 addresses the second research question, "What are the factors that accelerate or decelerate the transition process?" The question was postulated in the belief that the transition process only moved in a linear progression, mirroring the researcher's bias concerning the research process. This assumption negated the existence of other factors that may have halted or indeed, *reversed* the transition process. Unexpectedly, the data revealed that participants were able to cycle-out of transition, in effect reversing the transition process. Before continuing, it is important to differentiate between the *accelerators*, *decelerators* and *reversing factors* of transition.

The accelerators and decelerators of transition governed the factors which either sped up or slowed down the forward momentum of the participant through the transition experience. The factors that influenced the acceleration or deceleration of transition were categorised as either personal or group factors. As implied, personal factors such as personality characteristics and career background were significant at the individual level. Group factors⁵⁰ included population-sized factors at a community or organisational level, for example, innovative management practices. Factors that led to a participant cycling-out of transition (reversing factors), only became relevant post-transition and did not influence the initial transition experience. Therefore, the

⁵⁰ The term "Group" factors was selected over other descriptors including "systems" factors or "macro/meso" factors, due to the inherently broad scope of factors influencing the rate of paramedic transition to community paramedicine.

reversing factors discussed in the previous chapter were neither accelerators nor decelerators of the transition experience.

Lastly, the presence of one factor may accelerate the transition process and therefore logically, an absence or fleeting presence of the same factor consequently could possibly decelerate the transition process. Indeed, Glen and Waddington (1998) utilise this logic in determining the factors facilitating or impeding transition by staff nurses to clinical nurse specialists. However, it is an oversimplification to assume an accelerator was simply the opposite of a decelerator. The analysis of 36 participant interviews revealed nuanced differences in otherwise similar areas affecting the speed of transition due to the varied knowledge and experiences of the ECPs/CPs. Ultimately, the factors influencing transition were the result of the interpretation of the researcher, consistent with the constructivist grounded theory approach (Charmaz, 2014).

9.2 ACCELERATORS

9.2.1 Personal factors

Personal factors that accelerated the transition process included: *personality characteristics, career and life experiences, and increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases*. Personality characteristics included the attitudes and character traits participants suggested as complementary to the work role of an ECP/CP, thereby accelerating the transition process. Particularly the importance of attitude is emphasised below, as opposed to the acquisition of knowledge and skills, in the transition process:

And it all comes down to that attitude. 90% of people can get skills and knowledge. They can get it. They're bringing out educated people out of the universities that have got more baseline knowledge that what I ever started with...mastering your craft is all to do with your attitude. (P13)

Moreover, the implication in the above definition of attitude is that *dedication to the work role* was a key factor in accelerating the transition process. The dedication to the work role was illustrated by a fellow participant thus:

We're getting [recruiting] people who love what they do, but are finding that they just need to go in a new direction or have a change or whatever. So we're getting people who are 'dialled-in', who have a desire to do it. We're not getting what we call the 'dinosaur paramedics' who are like, 'I just don't want to do this job anymore, so I'm going to pick this other easier job', which it isn't. (P08)

Another personality characteristic that accelerated the transition process was psychological resilience. Previous studies have suggested that people with high psychological resilience will likely respond more favourably to organisational change than those with low resilience (Shin, Taylor, & Seo, 2012). In the following passage, the participant defined resilience as the ability to be critical of negative events whilst maintaining flexibility:

I think emotionally you need to be quite resilient. You need to be able to be flexible and take criticism in the right way that it's intended. Or ignore it if it's just criticism for the sake of being critical. I think that's the main thing: flexibility and resilience. Because we work at a high clinical level, the expectation on us is quite high, and you need to be able to deal with the stress that comes with that. So, I guess, that's the sort of quality that comes with resilience as well. (P03)

Other personal factors that possibly accelerated the transition process included being "receptive and open to new ideas" (P08), "keen on extra study, keen to learn new things" (P12), "caring and compassionate" (P55) and altruistic. "It's about what we can do for the patients" (P82), as one participant remarked. Indeed, altruism, in the form of patient-focus rather than self-focus, was a recurrent theme in the data:

...if you ask me what one of the most important key personality traits you want for an ECP, it's got to be patient-focus. It's not about the prestige. It's not about the pay. It's all patient-focus. (P13)

Career and life experiences were also major factors in accelerating the transition process, with a career background in nursing being the most influential. Success in the community paramedicine role was dependent in part on the paramedic having a sound understanding of the linkages between

healthcare agencies as well as with the contribution of each agency in the patient's journey through the health system. Therefore, those with a nursing background were initially more adept in the ECP/CP role than those with just a paramedic background:

I think it [nursing] helps you with your referral, understanding how and when you refer a patient, what's going to happen and where they're going to go. And having had experience in the health, allied health, areas of health outside of ambulance, you understand the systems, and how it's going to work, or not work. (P15)

The relevance of a nursing background could also be illustrated from the perspective of ECPs/CPs *without* a nursing background and the associated time taken to transition:

I started out and I didn't have any real understanding of nursing or real understanding of hospital policy and the way that hospital works. For me personally, it [the transition] took longer because I had to get my anxiety levels down because I was doing a whole new role knowing that the responsibility is mine to make that correct decision of whether or not this person is viable or non-viable for a referral. (P80)

Another reason a nursing background accelerated the transition process was because some nursing clinical skills were readily transferable to the community paramedicine domain:

So, I think I just felt that having that acute setting nursing background helped. Like skill set wise, definitely. Because, I can pretty much say, I already knew all the ECP skills. And not to say I'm arrogant... just that, you know, it was just stuff that I'd already done previously. (P23)

This is not to say that a nursing background was regarded as an essential prerequisite to work successfully as an ECP/CP. Rather, those with a pre-existing knowledge of the wider healthcare system and related clinical skills entered the field of community paramedicine further along the transition experience than their colleagues without a nursing background. The following excerpt from a participant with a nursing background confirms that point:

I think [a nursing background] has definitely been helpful, but absolutely essential? No, I don't think so. But I think you can be a successful community paramedic without having a nursing background. (P08)

This sentiment likely resonated across the study cohort as all 36 participants both with and without prior nursing experience reported a successful transition to the ECP/CP role. As another participant put it, "I think also being a non-nurse, it's not that hard. Because, let's be honest, a skill's a skill and you'll only be proficient at it if you repeatedly do it." (P23) A few participants also expressed their views on the relevance, partial or otherwise, of a nursing background to the ECP/CP role. For example, the following participant's observations suggest that a nursing background had limited applicability to the ECP role: "But I think the biggest thing that paramedics have that nurses don't, is the problem solving and the lateral thinking." (P82)

The final personal factor that accelerated the transition process was the increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases. That is, patient presentations where an ECP/CP could employ specific treatment pathways and interventions to improve the patient's journey through the health care system. At a more fundamental level, increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases was closely aligned with the concept of repetition, principally seen in the Middle Phase of transition. However, an increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases underscored the participant's engagement with all four core categories of transition in becoming a holistic practitioner, rather than focusing on singular concepts such as skill repetition. For example, the following participant suggested transitioning was more than simply learning new skills:

I think in terms of physical skills it is just repetition, yes. I didn't find those things to be an issue. It was more becoming comfortable with that whole assessment and diagnostic approach and knowing that even if I had not come across a situation before, I would be able to come up with a plan, and I know when to consult with a colleague or when to consult with a doctor to come up with that plan. So I think it was

more just developing that confidence in critical thinking in the ECP context. (P82)

Whilst increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases had relevance at the individual level, the means of securing appropriate cases for ECPs/CPs held relevance at the organisational level. In other words, the way paramedic services dispatched cases, particularly to ECPs, was an organisational (group) factor affecting the speed of transition and are discussed later in the chapter.

9.2.2 Group factors

Two group factors emerged from the data that accelerated the transition process: *esprit de corps* and *innovative management practices at the local level*. An *esprit de corps* signified a feeling of solidarity, fraternity and mutual support amongst the ECP/CP cohort. An *esprit de corps* was evident during all four core categories of transition, allowing the evolution of a work culture that was unique from the participant's previous roles. Engaging in collaborative practices was an essential contributor to developing an *esprit de corps*:

Because you are working on your own and you really didn't have anybody above you watching you all the time, it was up to you to self-regulate that. You had to say to the others, 'Hey I think I could have done this better, how could I have done it?' I actually really enjoyed that fraternity that is within the ECP ranks. (P49)

Moreover, the following participant emphasised the sense of team-belonging as a contributor to the transition process: "Just being a part of those conversations [about patients] and your input being valued, really helped transition me towards doing a better job as an ECP. So is that team environment." (P77) Continuing further, the sense of team spirit drew out a protective instinct amongst some participants:

I think we're very protective of our own, and I think that's very team-specific, as well. We have four different teams, lots of different shift lines, and we're very protective of those on our team. So, if we see one of my peers on my team struggling emotionally, we are very protective about that, and make sure that we protect their mental health. (P03)

For others, the introduction of a different uniform from their traditional paramedic colleagues also contributed to a sense of solidarity and uniqueness in their work role:

Initially, we required a different functional uniform in order to set us apart from our 'emergent' EMS colleagues. More importantly, in the early program development days, we also needed a way to create a sense of commonality amongst this group of people who were gathering the courage to try something completely unheard of before. Not only did uniforms help us to stand out so we could be easily recognised and distinguishable in the different care settings we attended, they also helped us brand the services we could provide. We were taken more seriously as other members of the healthcare team learned they were going to get the same quality of interaction (assessment & intervention) no matter which CP showed up, largely due to a similar appearance. This allowed them to approach us more confidently. (P33)

An *esprit de corps* fostered solidarity, fraternity and mutual support, which united ECPs/CPs in their goal of achieving a common end:

...it grants us this sense of community amongst its team members. We are all working towards a common goal as opposed to just coming in, clocking in and being 'us against them mentality', where it is kind of more of a team orientated approach. (P50)

Broadly speaking, the manifestations of an *esprit de corps*, such as the collaborative relationships between ECP/CP peers, played an influential role across all four core categories of transition. Undoubtedly, without *esprit de corps*, the transition process would have taken significantly longer to complete.

The second group factor to accelerate the process of transition was innovative management practices at the local (program manager) level. Conceptually, these practices could readily be identifiable as *frameworks of support* for ECPs/CPs. The management practices and related frameworks had several influences on accelerating the transition process. One such influence was providing *a sense of investment or ownership* of the participant's

respective program. Ownership, defined as a participant's valued contribution to the overall goals of the program, was demonstrated in the following excerpt:

I think it all comes down to support. There is a difference in feeling supported. We know [program manager] would step up to bat for us in any situation. Because we have helped, in a sense, build our referral pathways and build our patient care pathways and our treatment and our interventions. As we have had ideas, we have gone to him and said, 'Maybe let's think about this and maybe let's see if we can help this population of patients by considering this (whatever)'. He has always just been so open to the idea and if we could find some rationale and support it just a little bit, he was happy to pursue it. Just having that faith in leadership and having him have so much faith in our ideas and not feeling like you are being second guessed and not feeling like you are just talking and somebody is pretending to listen. (P33)

Aligned with program ownership (facilitated through innovative management practices) was a sense of security and confidence derived from managers advocating for and supporting ECPs/CPs. Advocating for participants contributed to a sense of work role *comfort/confidence* (a marker of transition), thereby accelerating the transition process:

...understanding that somebody [a manager] really has your back when we are building our policy or building our procedure or trying to make sure we are not half doing things by accident. It provides so much confidence and it provides so much reassurance that you are not going to get yourself necessarily in a pickle, but you have the right people on board to be able to pursue your patient care as you would without any hesitation. (P33)

From factors that accelerate transition, the chapter nows examine factors that decelerate transition. Decelerators slow the transition process and are similarly subdivided into personal and group factors. Although decelerators were evident throughout the core categories of transition, such as experiencing isolation as a single responder, analysis suggested some

participants were more cognisant of other personal and group factors impacting the speed of transition.

9.3 DECELERATORS

9.3.1 Personal factors

Personal factors limiting the speed of transition did not feature as prominently in the data as accelerating factors. One possible explanation was that all 36 participants reported a successful transition and therefore recalled the accelerators better than the decelerators of transition. Additionally, the criteria for inclusion in the study stipulated participants must be “currently or previously qualified ECPs or CPs.” In effect, paramedics who unsuccessfully attempted the transition process were ineligible to participate. It is conceivable that paramedics who were unsuccessful in the transition process may have contributed new theoretical directions, thus the exclusion of this cohort is a limitation of the study. Nevertheless, the single personal decelerator identified in the data was *negative mindset*.

Negative mindset referred to an attitude towards the work role that was aligned conceptually to motivation. Most participants identified comfort/confidence as an end-point of transition, thus the loss of confidence in managing more complex cases due to a negative mindset was a significant finding. In the following passage, one participant illustrated how motivation was affected by a negative mindset:

...it's very easy to do the course, if you like, to be an ECP. And then, if that motivation is not there, because we're dispatching ourselves for example, you'll find people who'll lose confidence in the complex. And I say 'complex' as compared to maybe doing a catheter change, for example. So, any complex case, for example, assessing a suture type presentation, or a neurological presentation, if you're not motivated and continue striving to understand what it is that we do, keep up with the changing things in medicine, you become one who wants to do the low skill base. (P41)

The implications for understanding the relationship between motivation and confidence extend to other areas of transition that require high-levels of intrinsic motivation, such as developing clinical reasoning. Arguably, the implications also extended to the recruitment of ECPs/CPs. One participant discussed the consequences of selecting motivated and passionate clinicians into community paramedicine programs:

The [program manager] has done a phenomenal job at selecting those who have the right ideas or passion behind it. I know a lot of people, like you've said, try to get out of the real-world EMS because they don't want to work nights, and that's not what it's about. It's about our patients and enhancing their care within the healthcare system, doing what's right for them at the right time. I think the great majority of people who do want to get into community medicine do it for the right reasons. They're passionate about learning about community and wanting to be a part of it. (P72)

The passage above also demonstrably linked motivation, passion, and willingness to be challenged with the core category *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change*. ECPs/CPs who retained a negative mindset were likely to be in opposition to the cultural norms within the ECP/CP ranks. Therefore, a negative mindset would be characterised as a decelerator since it delays the ancillary marker of transition. Without the presence of all four ancillary markers, the overall transition experience was prolonged.

9.3.2 Group factors

Participants spoke of two factors contributing to the deceleration of the transition process: *non-ECP specific tasking of cases* and *lack of management support*. Both of these factors have been discussed to some extent previously. However, analysis revealed nuanced differences in the data between similarly themed areas that warrant further discussion. The first to be examined, non-ECP specific tasking of cases, was one such example of a factor whose influence was apparent in other core areas of transition. The factor differs at this point because participants emphasised the *tasking* of cases as the principal issue. Additionally, non-ECP specific tasking of cases was only an issue for the

Extended Care Paramedic cohort as Community Paramedics were not utilised for traditional high-acuity workloads.

Non-ECP specific tasking of cases describes the tasking of ECPs to cases that likely would not benefit the patient compared to the care given by a traditional care paramedic. Tasking of ECPs occurred through a central Control Centre in both ECP study sites. Referrals to ECPs were also accepted from traditional paramedics and OHCPs. Additionally, one dispatch model rotated an ECP through the Control Centre to maximise the efficacy in the tasking of ECPs. However, during times of relatively low accuracy in ECP-specific dispatch, the transition process decelerated:

It slows it [the transition process] down because you are not doing ECP work. So you don't get to do those skills that you are taught to do. You probably become quite proficient in being a single responder and identifying the urgent needs of others, but you don't get much chance to practice your ECP [specific skills]. So acquiring those skills and moving on from a novice or beginner learner are affected by that. (P17)

Along comparable lines, the winter months generally are a busier time of year for traditional ambulance caseloads (Cantwell, Dietze, Morgans, & Smith, 2013). The following participant told how less high-acuity work towards the end of winter allowed for a greater opportunity to engage in ECP-specific skills, thereby increasing comfort/confidence (a marker of transition):

That is probably at a time where winter was slowing down, so I guess I was not being used for as much of the high acuity stuff. So, I was therefore doing more of my ECP skills and building my confidence up that way. (P55)

The second decelerating factor identified in the data was a lack of management support. Whilst arguably a lack of management support could simply be regarded as the opposite of innovative management, participants emphasised that a lacked coherent approach to supporting ECPs/CPs, was a decelerating factor. For example, the following participant correlated the value of "smoother" management, with transition:

If you have got a smoother management, your transition is a lot easier because you know what you need to do. That plays a role in it too, the management structure. If anything is well managed and organised, the transition is always going to be easier. (P17)

“Smoother” management implied that it was advantageous to have a management framework in place to support the participant in the transition process. To illustrate this, a participant argued that having a local level “sympathetic” or supportive line manager (DOM⁵¹), provided better outcomes for the paramedics:

There is no one funded for a position of a DOM you could take up the hierarchy or command. [Management support] only came from within that sector and if that DOM was sympathetic towards ECP, then you got quite a good result. (P55)

The remarks above also held true for senior management/executive levels. The disconnect between paramedic staff and senior management was manifested in the resistance towards an ECP/CP program:

There was a great deal of uncertainty. We had an idea, we knew what ECP's were capable of and what we were doing. We realised that we had stepped so far ahead of the mark from standard ambulance in what we were doing and what paramedics were capable of. It was frustrating that the rest of ambulance was not catching up. They [senior managers] didn't recognise the worth of the role, both in a financial sense but also in the strength of the program. We did not even know that the program would continue. We were met with resistance from upper ambulance management. (P88)

Some participants concluded, therefore, that managers were not active facilitators of the transition process. One participant went further by suggesting the relationship with managers was counterproductive:

I feel that management is working against the [ECP] group, rather than for the group, and we all feel a bit disenchanted by management. So,

⁵¹ DOM – Duty Operations Manager

I think, in terms of transition, the peers help each other, management doesn't. (P03)

The full effects of non-ECP specific tasking and lack of management support were very negative. Participants spoke of their frustration, the decrease in morale, and how they begrudged doing certain tasks. These views are encapsulated in the following data: "It's frustrating when you're driving sometimes 20, 30, 40 minutes, and you see the traffic, and then you get there, and you go, 'Oh, this is not my job.'" (P97); "Certainly the morale is affected by this ongoing focus on productivity with no understanding of how it actually applies to the ECP work" (P82); "I really begrudged going to inappropriate jobs on my own" (P55). The negative effects manifestly signalled a management framework that was not orientated towards facilitating ECP/CP transition.

9.4 CHAPTER SUMMARY

Factors that accelerated or decelerated transition were interwoven throughout the fabric of the transition experience. However, this chapter presents personal and group factors that are sufficiently refined in the analysis to warrant further discussion. A greater number of accelerating rather than decelerating factors have been identified in the data, due likely to all 36 participants reporting successful transition. Personal factors such as resilience, a nursing background and greater exposure to ECP/CP-specific work accelerated the transition process, whereas a negative mindset was found to slow the process. Group factors accelerating transition included an *esprit de corps* and innovative management practices were noted in the analysis. As for the factors that decelerated transition, the study showed that a lack of management support was not the only negative factor affecting management practices. There was also the absence of a coherent approach to supporting ECPs/CPs. Finally, the non-ECP specific tasking of cases was a significant factor affecting the deceleration of the transition process.

9.5 DISCUSSION OF THE ACCELERATORS AND DECELERATORS OF TRANSITION

The second research question sought to determine the factors that either accelerated or decelerated the transition process. These factors were identified as either personal or group factors. Personal factors, as defined in this study, were the factors that affected the rate of transition at an individual level. Group factors influenced transition above that of the individual and included the ECP/CP cohort, community paramedicine programs, paramedic services and parent health agencies. It is important to note however, that each element in the core categories of transition was in effect, an accelerator or decelerator. In other words, the degree of engagement a trainee ECP/CP had with an element affected the rate of the transition process. For instance, a lack of repetition in developing clinical skills during the Middle Phase, whilst unlikely to preclude a participant from achieving successful transition, would more probably decelerate or extend the transition process. Through further distillation of the data, some factors more than others were found to influence the rate of transition across multiple core categories. Subsequently, these factors were categorised as either accelerators or decelerators. An understanding of the factors that influence the rate of transition may assist trainee ECPs/CPs and educators in targeting intervention points that will positively influence the transition process.

9.6 ACCELERATORS

9.6.1 Personal factors

Three personal factors were found to accelerate the transition process: personality characteristics, nursing background and increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases. Personality characteristics referred to the attitude the paramedic brought to the community paramedicine program. Attitude, in turn, was further refined to suggest dedication to the work role and was a key factor in accelerating the transition process. Whilst an example of dedication to the work role was presented in Chapter 6 Early Phase of transition, dedication also permeated all four phases of transition. Synonymous with organisational

commitment (Alexander, 2009) and employee engagement (Rana, et al., 2014), a dedicated attitude was manifested as a high degree of motivation to engage in all core categories of transition. Moreover, employee engagement has been linked to employee outcomes and organisational success (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Therefore, the challenge lies not only in recruiting prospective ECPs/CPs with an attitude and resilience to undertake community paramedicine practice, but also in the fostering of a work environment that complements the trainee's inherent motivation to transition successfully.

A unique finding of this thesis and not reported elsewhere in the peer-reviewed literature, was the influence of a nursing background on transition. A nursing background was found to be an accelerator of transition for two reasons. First, nursing provided the participant with a more holistic understanding of the patient's trajectory through the healthcare system, and in particular, the primary care sector. The finding is congruent with two previous evaluations of ECP programs in both Australia (Thompson, et al., 2014) and the UK (Mason, et al., 2009). Second, some nursing clinical skills, such as catheterisation, were readily transferable to the community paramedicine setting. The transferability of skills was unsurprising given some characteristics of community nursing models mirrored those of community paramedicine (O'Meara, 2014). Significantly, participants emphasised that procedural skill acquisition was relatively simple, compared to the acquisition of the foundational clinical reasoning skills underlying the procedural skills.

The holistic understanding of the healthcare system and pre-exposure to clinical skills established a baseline level of confidence at the start of ECP/CP training that was higher for trainees with a nursing background, compared to those who did not have a nursing background. However, far from being an essential prerequisite to transition, the division between participants with and without a nursing background, had dissipated by the end-point of transition. Although initial interpretation of the results may suggest that former nurses make "better" trainee ECPs/CPs, this is an oversimplification. The work role of an ECP/CP is multifaceted with other diverse qualities such as good

interpersonal skills, compassion and empathy, clinical competence, experience, and problem-solving ability being also valued attributes.

The final personal factor to accelerate the transition process was an increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases. More than simple repetition, exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases allowed the participant to experience a wider scope of patient presentations and engage more dynamically with the other core categories of transition. In simple terms, increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases accelerated the transition process. The appropriate *allocation* of ECP/CP-specific cases has been categorised as an organisational (group) factor and is discussed later in the chapter.

9.6.2 Group factors

The two group factors that accelerated the transition process included an *esprit de corps* and innovative management practices at a local (program manager) level. An *esprit de corps* was contextualised as a sense of team belonging, being protective of colleagues, and group solidarity. An esprit de corps evolved as a supportive framework within the ECP/CP programs and was anchored in the core category, *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change*. However, the degree to which esprit de corps accelerated the transition process is difficult to measure. Few other studies have qualitatively examined the impact of workplace culture outcomes in community paramedicine, although the benefits of a supportive workplace culture in a healthcare setting are well recognised (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016; Richmond & Becker, 2005). Given the positive outcomes in both the current study and supporting literature, strategies to deliberately promote an *esprit de corps* culture within community paramedicine programs should be further examined.

Associated with the evolution of an esprit de corps were the innovative management practices seen in one of the study sites. The practices were deemed innovative as the participants were afforded a relatively high degree of input in shaping the services that the program delivered. Participants frequently recalled instances where opinions were brought to the program manager, duly considered, and subsequently acted upon. A supportive

program manager promoted the development of a sense of investment (ownership), security and confidence in the participants. Moreover, advocating for participants contributed to a sense of work role comfort/confidence (a marker of transition), thereby accelerating the transition process.

Innovative management practices were clearly identified as an accelerator of the transition process since the practices significantly bolstered the intrinsic motivation of participants to succeed in the role. Similar sentiments relative to the importance of feeling supported by line management have been made in evaluations of other community paramedicine programs (Mason, et al., 2009; Thompson, et al., 2014). Dedication to innovative management practices should be a clear organisational goal. Therefore managers, policy makers and those responsible for operationalising community paramedicine programs should be aware of the influential role management practices exert on the speed of the transition process.

9.7 DECELERATORS

9.7.1 Personal factors

The only personal decelerator identified in the data was a negative mindset. Although motivation derived from innovative management practices positively influenced transition, a negative mindset inversely affected motivation and subsequently slowed the transition process. The negative mindset was apparent in some participants who showed a lack of motivation to be challenged in various aspects of the ECP/CP work role. Moreover, as the workplace culture of ECPs/CPs was aligned to qualities such as motivation, passion and willingness to be challenged, a negative mindset conflicted with this prevailing ethos. The finding is significant as a good “fit” between organisational culture and employee has been suggested for promoting commitment, satisfaction and performance (O'Reilly, Chatman, & Caldwell, 1991; Verquer, Beehr, & Wagner, 2003).

The implications for understanding the inter-relationship between negative mindset, motivation and confidence extends to all core categories of transition. For instance, motivation is required to forge mutual trust and

respect with OHCPs. On the other hand, a negative mindset would preclude a participant from working towards opportunities to engage with OHCPs thereby retarding confidence and slowing progress towards the end-point of transition. Additionally, recruitment of ECP/CP candidates who demonstrate strong motivation and absence of a negative mindset should be encouraged, as they will likely experience a quicker transition.

9.7.2 Group factors

Two group factors contributed to the deceleration of the transition process, the elements of which have been canvassed earlier throughout the core categories. However, nuanced differences in the analysis of the data have shifted the interpretive “lens” on the data to reveal different insights on transition. The first factor discussed here is the non-ECP specific tasking of cases.

Clearly linked to the increased exposure of ECP/CP-specific cases discussed earlier in the chapter, non-ECP specific tasking of cases emphasises the *tasking* or *allocation* of cases by dispatchers as the principal issue. That is, the tasking of cases where the attendance of an ECP would likely benefit the patient more so than the attendance of a traditional care paramedic. Significantly, the issue was less prevalent for CPs who dispatch themselves through a central office, and are therefore removed from the emergency workload of the parent EMS agency. In this way, a CP could, for instance, accept a referral from a doctor and assess whether the patient fell within the CP scope of practice prior to dispatching a colleague. In contrast, ECPs were reliant on a central Control Centre which also handled emergency dispatch, although in one study site, an ECP was co-located in the Control Centre to assist in the allocation of ECP-specific cases.

The presence of a clinician in the Control Centre appears to increase the sensitivity of correctly dispatching an ECP to an ECP-specific case. Gray and Walker (2008) in a study of ECPs in the UK, noted that clinically directed dispatch of ECPs allowed for the better utilisation of alternate pathways over the traditional computer-aided dispatch system. Similarly, in an evaluation of

a multi-site ECP pilot program in Australia, Thompson, et al. (2014, p. 11) concluded that having an ECP in the Control Centre, “assisted greatly” with ECP case allocation and management.

A clinician directed dispatch allowed for a more targeted use of resources by “cherry-picking” ECP-specific cases that traditional computer aided dispatch failed to identify. Whilst the increased exposure of ECPs to ECP/CP-specific cases accelerated the transition process at a personal level (discussed earlier in the chapter), non-ECP specific tasking of cases was influenced by policy at an organisational level, and was therefore deemed a group decelerator. The evidence from this study strongly suggests paramedic services should adopt policies that include clinicians in determining the appropriateness of ECP/CP dispatch. Moreover, Thompson, et al. (2014, p. x), in a study evaluating the implementation of ECP programs across five sites in Australia, concluded that the cost-efficiency of ECP programs is “critically affected by the accuracy of call centre staff in identifying appropriate cases and dispatching ECPs appropriately.”

The final decelerating factor encountered in the analysis was a perceived lack of management support. The emphasis in this instance was on managers outside of the ECP/CP programs and included higher echelons of management within each agency. The disconnect with senior management contributed to a range of negative perceptions which led to uncertainty and continuing frustration in the role. The importance of supportive senior managers has been recognised previously as a key factor of success in ECP programs (Mason, et al., 2009; Thompson, et al., 2014). More importantly, it is within the power of senior managers to foster employee engagement by creating empowering, safe and supportive environments for their staff (May, et al., 2004).

A key challenge for the future involves educating managers external to the community paramedicine programs about the niche occupied by ECPs/CPs in the health system. By appreciating the common values and their shared visions of improving patient healthcare outcomes, managers would be better motivated to foster supportive transition environments for ECPs/CPs.

Innovative management practices will probably be needed to better accommodate the non-traditional approaches to transition in community paramedicine, since the quality of leadership, vision and commitment at an executive level can have a wide-ranging influence on the attitude exhibited towards ECPs/CPs.

9.8 CONCLUSION

Collectively, the accelerators and decelerators of transition influence every phase of the transition experience. However, it is important to acknowledge that the elements that constitute the core categories can similarly affect the rate of transition. Furthermore, generalising the relative importance of an accelerator and decelerator to the transition experience is problematic given the variations between study sites which include operational structure, existing support networks, individual participant backgrounds and attitudes, among others. Broadly speaking, the rate of transition is influenced by a multitude of factors which give rise to numerous potential intervention points. The intervention points provide an opportunity to influence the progression of the transition experience, thereby fielding higher quality ECPs/CPs in a shorter period of time. Finally, the findings are limited by the omission of paramedics who unsuccessfully attempted transition. Further research is required to understand why paramedics may fail to transition to the ECP/CP role.

Chapter 10: Conclusions

10.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 10 incorporates all the research findings into an overarching discussion of paramedic transition to community paramedicine. A summary of the findings is presented first, followed by the theoretical model of paramedic transition to a specialist work role in community paramedicine. The significance of the study is then discussed largely in terms of the limited transferability of extant work role transition theories. The implications and recommendations are subsequently explored. Next, the limitations and strengths of the study are examined, along with recommendations for future research. The thesis ends with the conclusions gleaned from the study.

10.2 SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

Community paramedicine is an umbrella term for two distinct models of paramedic service delivery. The aim is to navigate a patient more efficiently through the health system and provide disposition options other than presentation to an emergency department (Long, 2016). Two questions framed this research: *"How do paramedics transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine?"* and, *"What are the influencing factors that accelerate or decelerate the transition process?"* To answer the research questions, ECPs (n=25) from two Australian jurisdictions and CPs (n=11) from a Canadian provincial health service participated in the study. The data from the three study sites were pooled and interpreted using constructivist grounded theory methodology (Charmaz, 2014).

Qualified Paramedics transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine through four phases. The first phase is termed a "passive" phase, in that the decision to engage in a career in community paramedicine is made during the Pre-transition Phase. Qualified Paramedics, many of whom are credentialed at the highest clinical level in their respective paramedic

services, enter a junctional point in their careers. The junctional point is defined as the intersection at which two career “needs” meet. These are: a desire to improve patient outcomes, and seeking out new career options. The paramedic’s decision to transition to community paramedicine or return to traditional paramedicine is influenced by the individual’s prior perception of the ECP/CP role.

Following the Pre-transition Phase, paramedics engage in three “active” phases during the process of transitioning to community paramedicine. Within each transition phase four core categories of transition exists: *Engaging in a Community of Practice*, *Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change*, *Developing Critical Thinking* and *Mastering Skills*. Each core category contributes ancillary markers of transition which define the end-point of the evolution of that core category. The four ancillary markers of transition coalesce to provide a single and definable end-point to the transition experience. The salient concepts of the active stages of transition are presented below.

The Early Phase is characterised by negative emotions such as nervousness, stress and anxiety. Within this milieu, novice practitioners seek a “safety net” by obtaining reassurance and validation from their immediate peers through an incipient community of practice. Validation, in turn, fosters a sense of growing confidence in the new work role. Paramedics initiated transformative changes in their perceptions of workplace culture by investing in their respective programs and utilising clinical governance in novel ways. For them, the foundations of critical thinking continued to be laid through the adoption of novel approaches to learning. Furthermore, through instruction and consolidation, new clinical skills were acquired. For some ECPs though, acquiring the non-clinical skills to work as a high-acuity single responder was met principally through repetition.

The Middle Phase begins with a competent practitioner learning the “tricks of the trade”. Significantly, progression through the transition process for paramedics is contingent in part on the sub-transition of OHCPs.

Furthermore, receiving validation and reassurance from OHCPs promoted confidence – a key marker of successful transition. Associated with OHCP transition, continuing education plays a significant role in developing a sense of “safety” among the paramedics. Meanwhile, critical thinking is facilitated through three key elements: clinical governance activities, self-reflective practices and peer-to-peer learning. Finally, gaining confidence in skills is supported through repetition.

The Late Phase draws upon the four ancillary markers of transition to define the end-point of transition experience: *Adequate proficiency in work role*. In a finding not reported elsewhere in the paramedicine literature, paramedics could cycle in-and-out of the end-point of transition, depending on the level of work role proficiency. Through forging mutual trust, respect and acceptance with OHCPs, paramedics equalised relationships with their medical colleagues. Moreover, equalising relationships helps in completing the “mental switch” to the community paramedicine paradigm. Paramedic decision-making also evolves to the level of heuristic cognition. Additionally, the final stage is characterised by the paramedic’s ability to seamlessly “flip” between high-acuity and low-acuity cases. In the end, the evolution of skill mastery within the transition process is concluded with further consolidation and skill maintenance.

The second question postulated in this research sought to illuminate the factors which either accelerate or decelerate the transition process. Analysis of the results revealed that some personal factors significantly accelerated the transition process. These included having a nursing background, an increased exposure to ECP/CP-specific cases, and having certain distinguishing personality traits. Two group factors were also responsible for accelerating the transition process. One of these was an “esprit de corps” which engendered a feeling of solidarity and mutual support in the group. Another was the utilisation of innovative management practices. On the other hand, some decelerating factors slowed the transition process. These included the negative mindset of the paramedic, the tasking of non-ECP specific cases, and lack of management support.

10.3 THEORETICAL MODEL OF PARAMEDIC TRANSITION TO A SPECIALIST ROLE IN COMMUNITY PARAMEDICINE

The following page presents a theoretical model⁵² of the process of paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine (Figure 9.1). Although transition to community paramedicine is presented predominantly as a linear process, it is significant to note that there are porous boundaries between core categories and phases of transition. That is, elements within each core category and phase are not rigidly fixed in one position, and the boundaries between phases are not clearly delineated. Elements that may vacillate between core categories and phases are due to the individual differences between participants, such as their educational backgrounds, life experiences, ideologies, and perspectives. Denoted by broken lines in the theoretical model, the permeability allows for the subtle movement of elements between categories and phases. Additionally, by permitting connections between elements, the porous boundaries highlight the interrelationship and interdependence between core categories and phases. Thus, the resultant theory is not a predictive model of the transition experience, or to be more precise, the theory offers an abstract understanding of the relationships between elements, core categories and phases in the transition to community paramedicine.

Based on the theoretical model, the following definition of paramedic transition to community paramedicine has been developed:

The transition to community paramedicine is a multi-phase process initiated by Qualified Paramedics entering a junctional point in their careers. Through engaging, adjusting, developing and mastering four core categories permeating the transition phases, paramedics can achieve adequate proficiency in the work role. But despite striving for a new professional identity, a paramedic never fully disengages from their previous role in traditional paramedicine.

⁵² A theoretical model is a diagrammatic representation of a theory.

Figure 10.1 Theoretical Model of Paramedic Transition to a Specialist Role in Community Paramedicine

10.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The foremost significance of this PhD study is that the findings contribute to the evolution of community paramedicine as a specialist arm of paramedic practice. Through the contribution of new empirical knowledge of paramedic transition to community paramedicine, this research illuminates numerous intervention points along the transition continuum that may assist paramedics to more efficiently navigate the transition experience. Modifications tailored to the individual requirements of ECP/CP trainees create the optimum environment to support paramedic work role transition, thereby reducing the time taken to field confident/competent practitioners in the community. The findings of this research therefore add to the robustness and legitimacy of the community paramedicine service delivery model within the auspices of paramedicine.

Undoubtedly, the key stakeholders in the transition process to community paramedicine, such as paramedics, industry educators and administrators of ECP/CP programs, have a broad concept of the process of transition. To date, the sparse information alluding to the process of paramedic transition to community paramedicine has been confined to non-peer reviewed reports of ECP/CP programs (Alberta Health Services, 2015; Ambulance Service of NSW, 2010; Coffman, et al., 2017; Thompson, et al., 2014). However, the value of the current study is to distil the nuanced relationships between the elements that comprise the transition experience. The precision gained in understanding the relationships between the various elements of transition, within a conceptual and temporal framework, has broader implications for the efficiency and effectiveness of community paramedicine programs. To further illustrate the unique contribution that this PhD research offers in understanding the process of transition to community paramedicine, the chapter turns to discuss the limited transferability of extant work role transition theories from the general literature, nursing and traditional paramedicine fields.

Transferability refers to “the range and limitations for application of the study findings, beyond the context in which the study was done” (Malterud,

2001b, p. 484). Broadly speaking, the transferability of work role transition theory from other disciplines to community paramedicine is limited principally due to *context*. That is, the uniqueness of the work role context of community paramedicine in areas such as organisational structure, culture, interprofessional relationships and patient populations, renders the transferability of transition theory from other disciplines as problematic. Moreover, the unique relationships between elements, core categories and phases apparent in the transition to community paramedicine are not adequately explained through other transition theories.

For instance, Nicholson (1984), published a predictive model of the outcomes of work role transition. Briefly, he contends that the outcomes are the result of the interplay between two adjustment processes: personal development and role development. Personal development involves an individual adapting himself/herself to the new role, whilst role development involves adapting the role to fit the individual. The theory proposes that personal and/or role adjustments are influenced by the further interplay of other factors such as job discretion and novelty of role demands. However, the dimensions of these factors must first be measured. For example, West and Rushton (1989) utilised psychometric tests, questionnaires and diary recordings to define nursing job discretion in terms of:

- Acting independently of superiors,
- setting work targets,
- choosing the order in which different parts of the job are done, and
- choosing with whom to deal in order to carry out job duties.

Herein lies the first of two limitations in the applicability of Nicholson's (1984) model to the work role transition to community paramedicine. First, the model is a generic framework of work role transition, originating from the field of organisational psychology (Glen & Waddington, 1998). In this sense, Nicholson's model is *without context*. In other words, the interpretation of the model requires the input of data based on the perceptions of individuals

undergoing transition and therefore cannot be applied “off the shelf”. The second limitation is that Nicholson’s model is a predictive model of work role transition, where the value of the model resides in determining the degree of adjustments a person or role may experience during the work role transition. Whilst other authors have suggested Nicholson’s model can explain the transition of experienced nurses to specialist roles (Barton, 2007b), the model fails to explain the specific relationships between elements in the transition to community paramedicine. A finer understanding of the interconnections between elements allows for more targeted intervention strategies to facilitate the transition experience for inductees to community paramedicine.

Equally, the transferability of transition theory from other streams of paramedicine is affected by the context in which the transition occurs. For example, Devenish, et al. (2016) recently published a study on the topic of professional socialisation of university educated paramedics making the transition from university students to qualified paramedics. However, the issues faced by new-to-practice paramedics are significantly distinct from those experienced by seasoned clinicians transitioning to a specialist role. By way of example, the current study’s Early Phase is crudely analogous to the Formal Socialisation Phase in Devenish and colleagues’ model. Although both phases can be characterised as a “learning and developing” phase (Devenish, et al., 2016, p. 10), elements such as adjusting to the university culture and applying to multiple services for employment are clearly not applicable to qualified paramedics transitioning to a specialist role. The disconnect between elements limits the extent to which the professional socialisation model explains the process of transition to community paramedicine.

Although paramedic professional socialisation models are limited in their explanatory power with respect to specialist work role transition, the relationship between models however, is complementary. In simple terms, professional socialisation models are concerned with the transition of workers to a new professional group. Work role transition models on the other hand, focus on the transition of workers from an established work role to another work role within a chosen profession. Therefore, the current study of specialist

work role transition extends beyond the range of paramedic professional socialisation models. By combining theories of paramedic professional socialisation and work role transition to community paramedicine, a broader picture of transition from novice university student through to specialist paramedic emerges. This is the first known opportunity in paramedicine to examine longitudinally the transitions experienced by paramedics spanning an entire career.

Elements of other transition theories from cognate disciplines demonstrate greater congruence with the findings of the current study despite the lack of contextual similarities. For instance, Table 10.1 following, illustrates the parallels between Boychuk Duchscher’s (2009) interpretation of transition shock in nursing graduates (discussed in Chapter 5) and the experiences of participants in the current study. Distinctively though, no common elements were noted in the current study’s findings with the “Physical” category of Boychuk Duchscher’s (2009) conceptual framework. The likely reason is due to participants in the current study being experienced paramedics prior to transition, as opposed to new-to-work nursing graduates.

Table 10.1
Common Elements in Duchscher (2009) Transition Shock Conceptual Framework and Paramedic Transition to Community Paramedicine

Transition Shock Category (Duchscher, 2009)	Common Element	ECP/CP Transition Core Category
Intellectual	Theory/practice incongruencies	Developing Critical Thinking
Intellectual	Limited practice/pattern recognition	Mastering Skills
Intellectual	Limited tacit/practical knowledge	Developing Critical Thinking
Intellectual	Organisational naiveté	Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change

Transition Shock Category (Duchscher, 2009)	Common Element	ECP/CP Transition Core Category
Intellectual	Professional role-relations immaturity	Engaging in a Community of Practice
Intellectual	Limited performance feedback	Engaging in a Community of Practice
Emotional	Intense and overwhelming period	Engaging in a Community of Practice
Emotional	Seeking validation and reassurance	Engaging in a Community of Practice
Emotional	Require positive reinforcement	Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change
Socio-Developmental	Role uncertainty and unfamiliarity	Adjusting to Organisational and Cultural Change
Socio-Developmental	Intra-interdisciplinary relations	Engaging in a Community of Practice
Socio-Developmental	Insufficient exposure to role models	Developing Critical Thinking

Despite the range of common elements, the omission of an entire category limits the transferability of Boychuk Duchscher's model to community paramedicine. However, the congruence between models also suggests a degree of *plausibility* in the application of transition theories between cognate health professions. Indeed, Denscombe (2014) argues that although each case may be unique, it may also be an example from a larger group. Therefore, the possibility of transferability should not be immediately dismissed. Thus, the question arises: "*Can a work role transition theory from a cognate health profession adequately explain the process of work role transition in community paramedicine?*"

Conceptually, specialist work role transition in traditional paramedicine and nursing is most closely aligned to work role transition in community paramedicine. Examples of similar elements of specialist work role transition in traditional paramedicine and nursing include:

- Reasons for entering specialist roles (McFarlane, 2010)
- Emotional responses to transitioning (Barnes, 2014; Brown & Olshansky, 1997; Cusson & Strange, 2008; Glen & Waddington, 1998)
- Desire for feedback (Barnes, 2014)
- Desire for validation (Cusson & Strange, 2008)
- Importance of frameworks of support during transition (Barnes, 2014; Considine & Hood, 2004; Cusson & Strange, 2008; Kelly & Mathews, 2001)
- High significance attributed to developing clinical reasoning skills (Barton, 2007a; Considine & Hood, 2004)
- Value of preceptorship (Heitz, et al., 2004)
- Role boundary conflict (Glen & Waddington, 1998)
- Role ambiguity (Barnes, 2014; Barton, 2007a; Kelly & Mathews, 2001; Spinks, 2009)
- Drawing on pre-existing skill sets (Brown & Olshansky, 1997)
- Credibility as a function of maintaining clinical competency (Ball, 1999).

The parallels between elements of transition to community paramedicine and other transition theories are compelling. However, no single amalgam of individual elements of general transition, traditional paramedicine and nursing transition theory can adequately illuminate the complex interplay between elements, core categories and phases of specialist transition to community paramedicine. The significance and uniqueness of this PhD research is

therefore demonstrated by positioning this study beyond the practical transferability of other work role transition theories.

Work role transition theories from traditional paramedicine and cognate health professions may, however, play a role in the future evolution of transition theory in community paramedicine. The work role in community paramedicine is continually developing, thus the applicability of the current model in explaining the relationships between transition elements may decline over time. Transition theories from other disciplines may contribute “sensitizing concepts” (Charmaz, 2014) or tentative tools to develop ideas to explain the process of transition to community paramedicine.

This research has therefore created new knowledge about the process of transition of qualified paramedics to a specialist role in community paramedicine. The evidence from this thesis may provide guidance in a range of policies and practices of community paramedicine programs sharing similar service delivery philosophies. For example, training an ECP in an Australian paramedic service has been estimated to cost approximately \$30,000 (Thompson, et al., 2014), therefore information to guide in the selection and retention of ECPs/CPs is highly relevant. From a broader perspective, examples of savings to the wider health system through patient contact with community paramedicine programs ranges from US\$719 per patient contact in the United States (Coffman, et al., 2017), £140 per patient contact in the United Kingdom (Dixon, et al., 2009) and possibly up to A\$998 per patient contact in Australia (Thompson, et al., 2014). An understanding of the process of transition could inform the selection criteria, thereby increasing the efficacy of the selection process and decreasing the risk of expending resources on a candidate who may not be suited to the position.

Of particular importance, the findings of this research highlight the presence of four core categories comprising the transition experience. Whilst similarities were drawn to previous experiences of work role transition in disciplines such as nursing (Arrowsmith, et al., 2016; Poronsky, 2013), medicine (Brennan, et al., 2010; Westerman, et al., 2010) and other allied

health professions (Seah, Mackenzie, & Gamble, 2011), transition to community paramedicine presents its own unique milieu. For instance, the evolution of a community of practice has been identified as an integral component of a successful transition. For many participants in the current study, the level of engagement with OHCPs had not been previously realised. In this regard, the current study provides strong supporting evidence for the conclusions drawn by other studies from Canada and the United States highlighting the importance of paramedics developing collegial relationships with other health practitioners (Hauswald, et al., 2005; Martin-Misener, et al., 2009; Tavares, Bowles, & Donelon, 2016). Consequently, targeted opportunities to engage in interprofessional dynamics should be explored.

An understanding of other unique aspects of transition to community paramedicine will assist trainee ECPs/CPs to more efficiently navigate the transition experience. Cycling in-and-out of transition, for example, is a phenomenon not articulated elsewhere in the literature relating to paramedicine. By appreciating the value of continuing professional development and skill maintenance, the possibility of cycling-out of transition is lessened. Furthermore, knowledge of the accelerators and decelerators of transition provides targeted intervention points along the transition continuum in pursuit of work role comfort/confidence. For example, the evidence from the current study indicates that an increased exposure to ECP/CP-suitable cases accelerates the transition process. As established elsewhere in the extant literature, dispatch strategies can be optimised by the inclusion of an ECP/CP in the dispatch decision pathway (Gray & Walker, 2008).

The application of this research extends beyond paramedic services. For example, this research should prove to be particularly valuable to universities and colleges which could translate the findings into their curriculum. At the time of writing, only two Australian universities (2017; Monash University Extended Care Paramedic, 2017) but no Canadian university, offer postgraduate qualifications in community paramedicine. With a growing interest in community paramedicine models worldwide (Martin, et al., 2015), undoubtedly the number of universities and colleges offering specialist

qualifications in community paramedicine will increase over time. Moreover in a previous study, a formal qualification has been demonstrated to increase work role confidence in clinical nurse specialists (Gibson & Bamford, 2001). The current research highlights integral aspects of the transition process which informs the knowledge base of practice in community paramedicine. Universities and colleges could subsequently use this information to focus their community paramedicine programs.

The generation of new knowledge undoubtedly informs training curricula, but also has a wider application towards the professionalisation of paramedicine. The development of a unique body of knowledge is recognised as a prominent factor in the professionalisation of paramedicine (O'Meara, 2012; Williams, et al., 2012). The significance of this study has therefore been demonstrated through the generation of new knowledge regarding the process of work role transition to community paramedicine. Although individual elements of extant work role transition theories may draw parallels to the community paramedicine transition, this is the first study to explain the nuanced relationships between the elements, core categories and phases that comprise the community paramedicine transition experience. The following section further illustrates the significance of the study through the implications and recommendations arising from the Pre-transition Phase and each of the core categories of transition. Prominent examples from the paramedic services involved in this PhD research that may inform other national and international community paramedicine programs, have been included also.

10.5 IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Constructivist grounded theory was selected as the most appropriate methodology to produce a theoretical understanding of paramedic transition to community paramedicine. The findings, however, are not designed, nor are they intended to be, generalisable in the sense that specific recommendations stemming from the research can be applied "off the shelf" to other community paramedicine programs. Rather, the conceptual findings distilled from the analysis identify the broader implications for community paramedicine.

Consequently, it is at the discretion of individual community paramedicine programs to choose *how* the outputs of this research are applied practically in their own settings.

The broad implications for community paramedicine can be considered under three headings: Paramedic Education and Practice, Paramedic Workforce Planning and, Paramedic Research. Recommendations detailing specific action based on the community paramedicine programs that participated in the current research are offered as examples that may be applied to community paramedicine programs elsewhere.

10.5.1 Paramedic education and practice

The findings of the current study closely align paramedic education and paramedic practice and as such, both areas are discussed concurrently. The most prominent contribution that the current research lends to paramedic education and practice is an understanding of the nuanced relationships between the various elements, categories and phases of transition to community paramedicine. Moreover, this understanding provides ECP/CP educators and practitioners targeted intervention points along a paramedic's transition continuum, to more efficiently progress the ECP/CP trainee through the transition experience. For example, clinical governance was not simply seen as a mandatory reporting requirement by the participants, it was utilised as a learning and reflective practice tool. By appreciating the relative value of engaging in clinical governance activities, ECP/CP programs should consider exploiting clinical governance activities to their full extent.

Important implications for transnational curricula development, both at tertiary institutions and "in-house" programs, can also be proposed from the findings. For instance, the findings of the current study note that greater value was placed on the development of critical thinking skills rather than clinical procedural skills. Development of critical thinking skills has been facilitated by clinical governance, self-reflective practices and peer-to-peer engagement, culminating in an ability to intuitively perform in the role. As the results highlight the importance of the structured development of critical thinking

skills, activities designed to enhance clinical decision making should be prominent in the ECP/CP curricula.

The findings of this study provide a valuable insight into the evolution of a community of practice within the community paramedicine setting. The salient features include the progression from an internally focused community of practice, defined by paramedic-to-paramedic engagement, and concludes with equalised relationships with OHCPs. Significantly, the evolution of this core category was dependent on the successful sub-transition of OHCPs to accept ECPs/CPs as respected colleagues. The evidence from this study suggests that a community of practice provides the essential framework in building collegial working relationship between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs. Consequently, opportunities for ECPs/CPs to develop credibility and rapport with OHCPs, such as participation in inter-disciplinary meetings, grand rounds and case reviews, should be made available. Commensurate changes of organisational policy would likely be required in many paramedic and partner health services to draw greater attention to the importance of inter-professional collaboration.

Finally, although procedural skills were not as highly valued as critical thinking skills by the participants, proficiency in procedural skills was a major determinant as to whether a paramedic cycled-out of transition. Skill maintenance should therefore be a consideration for ECP/CP program planners and educators to ensure the availability of skill maintenance activities, such as high-fidelity simulations. Additionally, strategies to improve the efficacy of ECP/CP dispatch to target more “suitable” cases should be explored.

10.5.2 Paramedic workforce planning

The Pre-transition Phase represents a junctional point in a paramedic’s career. Mostly through a deep sense of frustration due to an inability to provide better healthcare options to patients, paramedics have sought new career challenges and pathways to improve patient outcomes. Interpretations of the ECP/CP role have determined whether paramedics engaged in the transition to community paramedicine, or exited to other career options. The Pre-

transition Phase describes the conditions, circumstances and events necessary to be present prior to engaging the “active” phases of transition. Taken together, the findings suggest elements of the Pre-transition Phase have the potential to inform the selection criteria for prospective ECP/CP candidates. For example, the recruitment of prospective ECPs/CPs should include the determination that the applicant’s service delivery philosophies are congruent with the community paramedicine paradigm. Also, greater consideration should be afforded to applicants with a demonstrable understanding of the wider healthcare system.

Workforce planning also entails an estimation of the skills and capabilities required by paramedics to meet future service delivery expectations. Arguably, community paramedicine is a relatively obscure healthcare paradigm within “mainstream” healthcare. However, the current study should give ECPs/CPs added confidence to find an assertive voice in promoting their value and impact on patient outcomes. ECPs/CPs exude a confidence in their ability to deliver a clinical service by subjectively defining the end-point of transition as “adequate proficiency in the work role”. Greater awareness of the ECP/CP role, perhaps through engaging OHCPs as mentors in clinical placements and improving paramedic-patient-GP collaboration, may foster greater acceptance amongst the healthcare community.

10.5.3 Paramedic research

One of the challenges for the paramedic profession has been to develop its own body of knowledge, rather than rely on other disciplines to guide the profession. This is the first study to qualitatively examine the transition to community paramedicine thereby adding to the science of ECP/CP transition. In this way, the current study allows paramedics to take greater ownership of their profession and enhance its professional standing (Griffiths & Mooney, 2011).

The implications of the current study also inform the future direction of paramedicine research. For instance, the sub-transition of OHCPs to accepting paramedics as equals is an integral component of the main transition process.

However, as no OHCPs such as GPs or community nurses were involved in the study, a clear understanding of OHCP transition is not possible within the available data. Future research may consider the factors that influence OHCP transition as well as paramedic transition to community paramedicine.

10.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Several limitations are present in the study. First, the recruitment strategy utilised purposive sampling in the recruitment of the participants. Purposive sampling selected participants based on their ability to contribute important or different perspectives on the transition to community paramedicine (Robinson, 2014). Consequently, all 36 ECPs or CPs were willing to discuss their experiences of transition, although other motivations to participate, such as a desire to promote their respective ECP/CP programs may have been present.

Significantly, the self-selection of participants resulted in the omission of paramedics from the study who had *unsuccessfully* attempted the transition process, that is, paramedics who were unsuccessful in attaining the end-point of transition, defined as “adequate proficiency in work role”. An exploration of the reasons why transition was unsuccessful would contribute new perspectives to the understanding of the transition experience. Attempts were made via snowball sampling to recruit paramedics who had unsuccessfully attempted transition, however, none were forthcoming. Future studies could consider examining those paramedics who attempted the ECP/CP training course and were unsuccessful.

In the same vein, other significant stakeholders in ECP/CP transition such as industry educators, program managers and OHCPs were not included in the study. The inclusion of other significant stakeholders may have contributed a greater depth of understanding to the transition experience. In particular, the inclusion of OHCPs may have better illuminated the processes involved in the sub-transition of OHCPs integral to the overall transition of paramedics to community paramedicine. However, the inclusion of other stakeholders was

outside of the scope of the current study which was further limited by the three year time-frame of the PhD study.

A final limitation to the study relates to the transferability or applicability of the research findings to other community paramedicine settings. The transferability of the current research is best viewed in terms of understanding conceptually the relationships between the elements of transition and the subsequent ability of the findings to inform and facilitate insights within other community paramedicine programs. In other words, the findings of this PhD study do not propose a “one size fits all” approach to paramedic transition to community paramedicine. Rather, the value of this research is to enable the transferability of findings based on thick descriptions of the research settings and use of purposive sampling strategies.

10.7 STRENGTHS OF THE STUDY

This thesis provides a unique perspective of paramedic transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine. Using the extant literature, community paramedicine was mapped, for the first time, in terms of the two dominant service delivery models. For this reason, data collection occurred across three paramedic services employing both Extended Care Paramedics and Community Paramedics. Moreover, the inclusion of Australian and Canadian paramedic services strengthens the study by offering an international perspective.

The concept of the researcher as an active respondent in the research process has long been recognised (Pezalla, Pettigrew, & Miller-Day, 2012). Therefore, as a former Extended Care Paramedic, my experience of transition to a specialist role in community paramedicine can be viewed as both a strength and a weakness. Having experienced the transition process, I have an intimate and unique conceptualisation of the elements comprising transition. A close familiarity with the subject matter can be regarded as an advantage in terms of identifying nuanced and subtle avenues of theoretical interest unique to community paramedicine. Conversely, my experiences of transition have the potential to skew the analysis towards an

overrepresentation of my own views and beliefs. Techniques employed to ensure rigour (see Chapter 4) limit the effect of research bias in this PhD study.

10.8 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE STUDY

Community paramedicine is a poorly understood speciality within paramedicine. Indeed, the literature review showed there are few published studies that examined community paramedicine models from a theoretical perspective. Continuing research is essential to provide community paramedicine with a theoretical base from which to evolve, rather than continuing a reliance on descriptive and ambiguous studies (O'Meara, 2014). The current study has illuminated aspects of community paramedicine related to paramedic education and practice, along with other workforce development issues. Future research could further explore the nature of collaborative practices between ECPs/CPs and OHCPs. The current research has identified the fundamental importance of a community of practice and collegial working relationships to the overall success of paramedic transition to community paramedicine. An improved understanding of the process of OHCPs transition, including the cross-institutional barriers to collaboration, would offer a more holistic conceptualisation of paramedic transition to community paramedicine.

Further exploration of the accelerators and decelerators of transition may illicit tangible effects beyond the transition process. For instance, the findings suggest paramedics with nursing experience may enter the transition process in a more advanced position than their other paramedic colleagues without nursing experience, due to a more holistic understanding of the healthcare system. Future research may determine the extent to which nursing experience complements the role of ECP/CP. The obvious implications of the findings are to refine the recruitment policy of ECPs/CPs. However, future research may enlighten the debate on the relevance of the combined undergraduate Nursing/Paramedic double-degrees.

Workforce capability development is another area within community paramedicine that may benefit from further research. For example, the current study determined that the management and operations of community

paramedic programs have a direct influence on the speed by which a paramedic experiences transition. Future research may further clarify the role that program and operational managers play in determining workplace practices which influence the transition to community paramedicine, particularly ECP/CP dispatch policies and procedures. Ultimately, further research is vital to drive the innovation and influence of community paramedicine.

10.9 CONCLUSION

Paramedicine is in a state of rapid evolution. The introduction of specialist work roles has challenged fundamentally the professional and clinical boundaries that has traditionally defined the profession. Rather than extrapolating knowledge from other disciplines, this PhD study offers an assertive voice in establishing community paramedicine as a specialist work role in paramedicine. Furthermore, this research has demonstrated that paramedic transition to community paramedicine is a developmental process comprised of nuanced relationships between various elements, core categories and phases of transition. By creating a developmental portfolio informed by the findings of the current study, paramedics may benefit from targeted and on-going support at various points along the transition experience.

The most compelling reason for the continued development of the community paramedicine model is the growing demand on paramedic services to provide appropriate and equitable healthcare to a population that is not only ageing, but where demand for unscheduled and community-based care is increasing. Extending traditional paramedic services to incorporate community-based models through the creation of emerging models of practice has enormous possibilities for reducing demand on acute hospital based services and more efficiently navigate the patient through the healthcare system. Thus, furthering understanding about how paramedics make the transition from traditional paramedicine to community paramedicine may prove important in assisting paramedic services to position themselves to better meet community and patient demands.

Bibliography

- Abrashkin, K., Washko, J., Zhang, J., Poku, A., Kim, H., & Smith, K. (2016). Providing acute care at home: Community paramedics enhance an advanced illness management program-preliminary data. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, *64*(12), 2572-2576. doi:10.1111/jgs.14484
- Acker, J., Johnston, T., & Lazarsfeld-Jensen, A. (2014). Industrial paramedics, out on site but not out of mind. *Rural Remote Health*, *14*(4), 2856-2873.
- Al-Shaqsi, S. (2010). Models of International Emergency Medical Service (EMS) Systems. *Oman Medical Journal*, *25*(4), 320-323. doi:10.5001/omj.2010.92
- Alberta Health Services. (2015). *Calgary Zone Community Paramedic Program 2015 Activity Report*: Internal AHS report: unpublished.
- Alberta Health Services. (2016). Alberta Health Services 2015-16 Annual Report. Retrieved 1 April, 2017, from <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/assets/about/publications/ahs-pub-2015-2016-annual-report.pdf>
- Alberta Health Services. (2017a). Calgary Zone Community Paramedic Program. Retrieved 6 August, 2017, from <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/ems/Page15295.aspx>
- Alberta Health Services. (2017b). EMS in the Calgary Zone. Retrieved 3 August, 2017, from <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/ems/page12555.aspx>
- Alexander, M. (2009). The relationship between paramedics' level of education and degree of commitment. *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, *27*(7), 830-837. doi:10.1016/j.ajem.2008.06.039
- Alfaro-LeFevre, R. (2009). *Critical thinking and clinical judgment: A practical approach to outcome-focused thinking*. St. Louis: Saunders.
- Ambulance Service of NSW. (2010). *Extended Care Paramedic Program Report on Activity and Performance - 2007 to 2010*. Internal ASNSW report: unpublished.
- Ambulance Service of NSW. (2011). *Extended Care Paramedic Clinical Governance*. Internal ASNSW report: unpublished.

- Ambulance Service of NSW. (2015). Demand for our services. Retrieved 14 November, 2015, from NSW Health, <http://www.ambulance.nsw.gov.au/Our-performance/Demand-for-our-services.html>
- Ambulance Victoria. (2015). Types of Paramedics. Retrieved 26 April, 2015, from <http://www.ambulance.vic.gov.au/Paramedics/Types-of-Paramedics/MICA-paramedics.html>
- Anderson, J. (2009). The work-role transition of expert clinician to novice academic educator. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 48(4), 203-208. doi:10.3928/01484834-20090401-02
- Arrowsmith, V., Lau-Walker, M., Norman, I., & Maben, J. (2016). Nurses' perceptions and experiences of work role transitions: A mixed methods systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 72(8), 1735-1750. doi:10.1111/jan.12912
- Ashforth, B., & Saks, A. (1995). Work-role transitions: A longitudinal examination of the Nicholson model. *Journal of Occupational & Organizational Psychology*, 68(2), 157-175. doi:10.1111/j.2044-8325.1995.tb00579.x
- Australian Government. (2017). Primary Health Care in Australia. Retrieved 8 August, 2017, from <http://www.health.gov.au/internet/publications/publishing.nsf/Content/NPHC-Strategic-Framework~phc-australia>
- Australian Institute of Health and Welfare. (2014). Australia's hospitals 2013-14: At a glance. Retrieved 27 November, 2015, from <http://www.aihw.gov.au/publication-detail/?id=60129551440>
- Avraham, N., Goldblatt, H., & Yafe, E. (2014). Paramedics' experiences and coping strategies when encountering critical incidents. *Qualitative Health Research*, 24(2), 194-208. doi:10.1177/1049732313519867
- Baker, R., Lakhani, M., Fraser, R., & Cheater, F. (1999). A model for clinical governance in primary care groups. *BMJ Clinical Research*, 318(7186), 779-783. doi:10.1136/bmj.318.7186.779
- Ball, C. (1999). Revealing higher levels of nursing practice. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing*, 15(2), 65-76. doi:10.1016/S0964-3397(99)80002-0
- Barach, P., & Small, S. (2000). Reporting and preventing medical mishaps: Lessons from non-medical near miss reporting systems. *British Medical Journal*, 320(7237), 759-763. doi:10.1136/bmj.320.7237.759

- Barnes, H. (2014). Nurse Practitioner role transition: A concept analysis. *Nursing Forum, 50*(3), 137-146. doi:10.1111/nuf.12078
- Barnes, H. (2015). Exploring the factors that influence nurse practitioner role transition. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners, 11*(2), 178-183. doi:10.1016/j.nurpra.2014.11.004
- Barton, T. (2007a). Student nurse practitioners - A rite of passage? The universality of Van Gennep's model of social transition. *Nurse Education in Practice, 7*(5), 338-347. doi:10.1016/j.nepr.2006.11.005
- Barton, T. (2007b). Student nurse practitioners – A rite of passage? The universality of Van Gennep's model of social transition. *Nurse Education in Practice, 7*(5), 338-347. doi:10.1016/j.nepr.2006.11.005
- Batt, A., Ward, G., & Acker, J. (2017). *Paramedic patient advocacy: A review and discussion* [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- Benner, P. (1984). *From novice to expert: Excellence and power in clinical nursing practice*. Menlo Park, California: Addison-Wesley, Nursing Division.
- Benner, P., & Tanner, C. (1987). Clinical judgment: How expert nurses use intuition. *The American Journal of Nursing, 87*(1), 23-31. doi:10.2307/3470396
- Bennett, C. (2009). A healthier future for all Australians: An overview of the final report of the National Health and Hospitals Reform Commission. *Medical Journal of Australia, 191*(7), 383-387.
- Bennett, P., Williams, Y., Page, N., Hood, K., Woollard, M., & Vetter, N. (2005). Associations between organizational and incident factors and emotional distress in emergency ambulance personnel. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology, 44*(2), 215-226. doi:10.1348/014466505X29639
- Bernard, H., Wutich, A., & Ryan, G. (2016). *Analyzing qualitative data: Systematic approaches*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE.
- Berridge, E., Freeth, D., Sharpe, J., & Roberts, C. (2007). Bridging the gap: Supporting the transition from medical student to practising doctor - a two-week preparation programme after graduation. *Medical Teacher, 29*(2-3), 119-127. doi:10.1080/01421590701310897
- Bigham, B., Kennedy, S., Drennan, I., & Morrison, L. (2013). Expanding paramedic scope of practice in the community: A systematic review of the literature. *Prehospital Emergency Care, 17*(3), 361-372. doi:10.3109/10903127.2013.792890

- Birks, M., & Mills, J. (2011). *Grounded theory: A practical guide*. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Boyчук Duchscher, J. (2001). Out in the real world: Newly graduated nurses in acute-care speak out. *The Journal of Nursing Administration*, *31*(9), 426-439. doi:10.1097/00005110-200109000-00009
- Boyчук Duchscher, J. (2008). A process of becoming: The stages of new nursing graduate professional role transition. *Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, *39*(10), 441-450. doi:10.3928/00220124-20081001-03
- Boyчук Duchscher, J. (2009). Transition shock: The initial stage of role adaptation for newly graduated registered nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *65*(5), 1103-1113. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2008.04898.x
- Braithwaite, J., & Travaglia, J. (2008). An overview of clinical governance policies, practices and initiatives. *Australian Health Review*, *32*(1), 10-22. doi:10.1071/AH080010
- Brennan, N., Corrigan, O., Allard, J., Archer, J., Barnes, R., Bleakley, A., . . . De Bere, S. R. (2010). The transition from medical student to junior doctor: Today's experiences of tomorrow's doctors. *Medical Education*, *44*(5), 449-458. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2923.2009.03604.x
- Brown, M., & Olshansky, E. (1997). From limbo to legitimacy: A theoretical model of the transition to the Primary Care Nurse Practitioner role. *Nursing Research*, *46*(1), 46-51. doi:10.1097/00006199-199701000-00008
- Bryant, A., & Charmaz, K. (2010). Grounded theory in historical perspective: An epistemological account. In *The SAGE Handbook of Grounded Theory, 2007* (pp. 31-57). London: SAGE.
- Bryce, J., & Foley, E. (2014). Is it advanced or expanded practice? *Australian Nursing and Midwifery Journal*, *22*(1), 17.
- Brydges, M., Spearen, C., Birze, A., & Tavares, W. (2015). A culture in transition: Paramedic experiences with community referral programs. *Canadian Journal of Emergency Medicine*, *17*(6), 631-638. doi:10.1017/cem.2015.6
- Caffrey, S., Clark, J., Bourn, S., Cole, J., Cole, J., Mandt, M., . . . Swanson, E. (2014). Paramedic specialization: A strategy for better out-of-hospital care. *Air Medical Journal*, *33*(6), 265-273. doi:10.1016/j.amj.2014.07.020

- Canadian Government. (2005). Statistics Canada. Retrieved 3 August, 2017, from <http://www.statcan.gc.ca/eng/start>
- Cantwell, K., Dietze, P., Morgans, A., & Smith, K. (2013). Ambulance demand: Random events or predicable patterns? *Emergency Medicine Journal, 30*(11), 883-887. doi:10.1136/emered-2012-201852
- Caroline, N. (1995). *Emergency Care in the Streets* (5th ed.). Boston: Little, Brown and Company.
- Catterall, M. (2012). The role of paramedics with extended practice: Exploring the healthcare context. *Journal of Paramedic Practice, 4*(10), 569-575.
- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing grounded theory* (2nd ed.). London: SAGE.
- Charmaz, K. (2017a). The power of constructivist grounded theory for critical inquiry. *Qualitative Inquiry, 23*(1), 34-45. doi:10.1177/1077800416657105
- Charmaz, K. (2017b). Special invited paper: Continuities, contradictions, and critical inquiry in grounded theory. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 16*(1), 1-8. doi:10.1177/1609406917719350
- Chilcote, D. (2017). Intuition: A concept analysis. *Nursing Forum, 52*(1), 62-67. doi:10.1111/nuf.12162
- Chilton, M. (2012). A brief analysis of trends in prehospital care services and a vision for the future. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 2*(1), 5.
- Choi, B., Blumberg, C., & Williams, K. (2016). Mobile integrated health care and community paramedicine: An emerging emergency medical services concept. *Annals of Emergency Medicine, 67*(3), 361-366. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2015.06.005
- Coates, D., Rawstorne, S., & Benger, J. (2012). Can emergency care practitioners differentiate between an avoided emergency department attendance and an avoided admission? *Emergency Medicine Journal, 29*(10), 838-841. doi:10.1136/emered-2011-200484
- Coffman, J., Wides, C., Niedzwiecki, M., & Geyn, I. (2017). Evaluation of California's Community Paramedicine Pilot Project Retrieved 22 May, 2017, from Healthforce Center University of California San Francisco, http://www.emsa.ca.gov/Media/Default/PDF/Evaluation%20of%20California%20B9s%20CP%20Pilot%20Program_final.pdf

- Colbeck, M. (2014). Australasian Consultant Paramedic – an idea whose time has come. *The Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, 11(5), 1-3.
- College of Paramedics. (2015). Paramedic career framework. Retrieved 15 June, 2016, from https://www.collegeofparamedics.co.uk/downloads/Post-Reg_Career_Framework_3rd_Edition.pdf
- Collins, M., Block, S., Arnold, R., & Christakis, N. (2009). On the prospects for a blame-free medical culture. *Social Science & Medicine*, 69(9), 1287-1290. doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.08.033
- Collis, J. (2010). Adverse effects of overcrowding on patient experience and care: John Collis presents the findings of a systematic literature review of how the number of people in emergency departments affects service delivery. *Emergency Nurse*, 18(8), 34-39.
- Comans, T., Currin, M., Quinn, J., Tippett, V., Rogers, A., & Haines, T. (2011). Problems with a great idea: Referral by prehospital emergency services to a community-based falls-prevention service. *Injury Prevention*, 19(2), 134-138. doi:10.1136/injuryprev-2011-040076
- Considine, J., & Hood, K. (2004). Career development year in emergency nursing: Using specific educational preparation and clinical support to facilitate the transition to specialist practice. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 4(3), 168-176. doi:10.1016/S1471-5953(03)00076-3
- Cooper, S. (2005). Contemporary UK paramedical training and education. How do we train? How should we educate? *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 22(5), 375-379. doi:10.1136/emj.2004.019208
- Cooper, S., & Grant, J. (2009). New and emerging roles in out of hospital emergency care: A review of the international literature. *International Emergency Nursing*, 17(2), 90-98. doi:10.1016/j.ienj.2008.11.004
- Cooper, S., O'Carroll, J., Jenkin, A., & Badger, B. (2007). Collaborative practices in unscheduled emergency care: Role and impact of the emergency care practitioner-qualitative and summative findings. *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 24(9), 625-629. doi:10.1136/emj.2006.043943
- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2015). *Basics of qualitative research* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE.
- Coutinho, S. (2007). The relationship between goals, metacognition, and academic success. *Educate*, 7(1), 39-47.

- Creswell, J. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. London: SAGE.
- Croskerry, P. (2002). Achieving quality in clinical decision making: Cognitive strategies and detection of bias. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 9(11), 1184-1204. doi:10.1111/j.1553-2712.2002.tb01574.x
- Cusson, R., & Strange, S. (2008). Neonatal nurse practitioner role transition: The process of reattaining expert status. *The Journal of Perinatal & Neonatal Nursing*, 22(4), 329-337. doi:10.1097/01.JPN.0000341365.60693.39
- Cutcliffe, J., & McKenna, H. (2004). Expert qualitative researchers and the use of audit trails. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 45(2), 126-133. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2648.2003.02874.x
- D'Amour, D., Ferrada-Videla, M., San Martin Rodriguez, L., & Beaulieu, M. (2005). The conceptual basis for interprofessional collaboration: Core concepts and theoretical frameworks. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 19(S1), 116-131. doi:10.1080/13561820500082529
- De Witt, L., & Ploeg, J. (2006). Critical appraisal of rigour in interpretive phenomenological nursing research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 55(2), 215-229. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03898.x
- Deakin, C., King, P., & Thompson, F. (2009). Prehospital advanced airway management by ambulance technicians and paramedics: Is clinical practice sufficient to maintain skills? *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 26(12), 888-891. doi:10.1136/emj.2008.064642
- Denscombe, M. (2014). *The good research guide: For small-scale social research projects* (4th ed.). Maidenhead, England: McGraw-Hill/Open University Press.
- Derengowski, S., Irving, S., Koogle, P., & Englander, R. (2000). Defining the role of the pediatric critical care nurse practitioner in a tertiary care center. *Critical Care Medicine*, 28(7), 2626-2630. doi:10.1097/00003246-200007000-00074
- Desborough, J. (2012). How nurse practitioners implement their roles. *Australian Health Review*, 36(1), 22-26. doi:10.1071/AH11030
- Devenish, A., Clark, M., & Fleming, M. (2016). Experiences in becoming a paramedic: The professional socialization of university qualified paramedics. *Journal of Creative Education*, 7(06), 786-798. doi:10.4236/ce.2016.76081

- Devers, K., & Frankel, R. (2000). Study design in qualitative research: Sampling and data collection strategies. *Education for Health: Change in Learning & Practice*, 13(2), 263-271. doi:10.1080/13576280050074543
- Dick, W. (2003). Anglo-American vs. Franco-German emergency medical services system. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 18(1), 29-37. doi:10.1017/S1049023X00000650
- Dixon, S., Mason, S., Knowles, E., Colwell, B., Wardrope, J., Snooks, H., . . . Nicholl, J. (2009). Is it cost effective to introduce paramedic practitioners for older people to the ambulance service? Results of a cluster randomised controlled trial. *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 26(6), 446-451. doi:10.1136/emj.2008.061424
- Doy, R., & Turner, K. (2004). The giraffe: The emergency care practitioner; Fit for purpose? The East Anglian experience. *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 21(3), 365-366. doi:10.1136/emj.2004.014407
- Drewitz-Chesney, C. (2012). Posttraumatic stress disorder among paramedics: Exploring a new solution with occupational health nurses using the Ottawa Charter as a framework. *Workplace Health and Safety*, 60(6), 257-263. doi:10.3928/21650799-20120516-51
- Eason, T. (2010). Lifelong learning: Fostering a culture of curiosity. *Creative Nursing*, 16(4), 155-159. doi:10.1891/1078-4535.16.4.155
- Eaton, G. (2017). Taking healthcare to the community: The evolving role of paramedics. *Journal of Paramedic Practice*, 9(5), 190-191.
- Edith Cowan University. (2016). Community Paramedicine Specialisation. Retrieved September 11, 2016, from <http://www.ecu.edu.au/degrees/courses/master-of-paramedical-science/unitset?id=SPAALN&crsCd=L60>
- Edith Cowan University. (2017). Community Paramedicine Specialisation. Retrieved 2 July, 2017, from Edith Cowan University, <http://www.ecu.edu.au/degrees/courses/master-of-paramedical-science/unitset?id=SPAALN>
- English, I. (1993). Intuition as a function of the expert nurse: A critique of Benner's novice to expert model. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 18(3), 387-393. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2648.1993.18030387.x
- Ensher, E., Heun, C., & Blanchard, A. (2003). Online mentoring and computer-mediated communication: New directions in research. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63(2), 264-288. doi:10.1016/S0001-8791(03)00044-7

- Ericsson, K. (2004). Deliberate practice and the acquisition and maintenance of expert performance in medicine and related domains. *Academic Medicine, 79*(10), 70-81.
- Ericsson, K., Krampe, R., & Tesch-Römer, C. (1993). The role of deliberate practice in the acquisition of expert performance. *Psychological Review, 100*(3), 363-406. doi:10.1037/0033-295X.100.3.363
- Freidson, E. (1988). *Profession of medicine: A study of the sociology of applied knowledge*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Gardner, L. (2012). From novice to expert: Benner's legacy for nurse education. *Nurse Education Today, 32*(4), 339-340. doi:10.1016/j.nedt.2011.11.011
- Gent, P. (2016). Continuing professional development for paramedics: A systematic literature review. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 13*(4), 1-9.
- Gibson, F., & Bamford, O. (2001). Focus group interviews to examine the role and development of the clinical nurse specialist. *Journal of Nursing Management, 9*(6), 331-342.
- Gilbert, J., Yan, J., & Hoffman, S. (2010). A WHO report: Framework for action on interprofessional education and collaborative practice. *Journal of Allied Health, 39*(3 part 2), 196-197.
- Glaser, B., & Strauss, A. (1967). *Discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Piscataway: Routledge Ltd.
- Glen, S., & Waddington, K. (1998). Role transition from staff nurse to clinical nurse specialist: A case study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing, 7*(3), 283-290. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2702.1998.00216.x
- Glynn, P., & Silva, S. (2013). Meeting the needs of new graduates in the emergency department: A qualitative study evaluating a new graduate internship program. *Journal of Emergency Nursing, 39*(2), 173-178. doi:10.1016/j.jen.2011.10.007
- Gobet, F., & Chassy, P. (2008). Towards an alternative to Benner's theory of expert intuition in nursing: A discussion paper. *International Journal of Nursing Studies, 45*(1), 129-139. doi:10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2007.01.005
- Gray, J., & Walker, A. (2008). AMPDS categories: Are they an appropriate method to select cases for extended role ambulance practitioners? *Emergency Medicine Journal, 25*(9), 601-603. doi:10.1136/emj.2007.056184

- Gray, J., & Wardrope, J. (2007). Introduction of non-transport guidelines into an ambulance service: A retrospective review. *Emergency Medicine Journal*, *24*(10), 727-729. doi:10.1136/emj.2007.048850
- Gresens, A. (2017). Community paramedics: Need of legal education specific to the pre-hospital non-emergency environment (discussion based on Texas). *Journal of Paramedic Practice*, *9*(5), 208-212.
- Griffin, M., & Melby, V. (2006). Developing an advanced nurse practitioner service in emergency care: Attitudes of nurses and doctors. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *56*(3), 292-301. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.04025.x
- Griffiths, P., & Mooney, G. (2011). *The Paramedic's guide to research: An introduction*. Berkshire, England: Open University Press.
- Grix, J. (2002). Introducing students to the generic terminology of social research. *Politics*, *22*(3), 175-186. doi:10.1111/1467-9256.00173
- Guest, G., Bunce, A., & Johnson, L. (2006). How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field Methods*, *18*(1), 59-82. doi:10.1177/1525822X05279903
- Hallberg, L. (2006). The "core category" of grounded theory: Making constant comparisons. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on health and well-being*, *1*(3), 141-148. doi:10.3402/qhw.v1i3.4927
- Hansman, C. (2008). *Communities of Practice: Creating learning environments for educators*. North Carolina: NewBay Media.
- Hanson, C., & Hamric, A. (2003). Reflections on the continuing evolution of advanced practice nursing. *Nursing Outlook*, *51*(5), 203-211. doi:10.1016/S0029-6554(03)00158-1
- Harden, R. (1988). What is an OSCE? *Medical Teacher*, *10*(1), 19-22. doi:10.3109/01421598809019321
- Harrington, S. (2011). Mentoring new nurse practitioners to accelerate their development as primary care providers: A literature review. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*, *23*(4), 168-174. doi:10.1111/j.1745-7599.2011.00601.x
- Hasson, F., Keeney, S., & McKenna, H. (2000). Research guidelines for the Delphi survey technique. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *32*(4), 1008-1015. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2648.2000.01567.x

- Hauswald, M., Raynovich, W., & Brainard, A. (2005). Expanded emergency medical services: The failure of an experimental community health program. *Prehospital Emergency Care, 9*(2), 250-253. doi:10.1080/10903120590924942
- Heitz, L., Steiner, S., & Burman, M. (2004). RN to FNP: A qualitative study of role transition. *Journal of Nursing Education, 43*(9), 416-420.
- Howkins, E., & Ewens, A. (1999). How students experience professional socialisation. *International Journal of Nursing Studies, 36*(1), 41-49. doi:10.1016/S0020-7489(98)00055-8
- Hoyle, S., Swain, A., Fake, P., & Larsen, P. (2012). Introduction of an extended care paramedic model in New Zealand. *Emergency Medicine Australasia, 24*(6), 652-656. doi:10.1111/j.1742-6723.2012.01608.x
- Huot, K. (2013). *Transition support for new graduate paramedics* Master's thesis. Royal Roads University.
- Jalali, S., & Wohlin, C. (2012, 19-20 September, 2012). Systematic literature studies: Database searches vs. backward snowballing. In *International Conference on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement* (pp. 29-38).
- Jensen, J., Bienkowski, A., Travers, A., Calder, L., Walker, M., Tavares, W., & Croskerry, P. (2016). A survey to determine decision-making styles of working paramedics and student paramedics. *Canadian Journal of Emergency Nursing, 18*(3), 213-222. doi:10.1017/cem.2015.95
- Jensen, J., Marshall, E., Carter, A., Boudreau, M., Burge, F., & Travers, A. (2016). Impact of a novel collaborative long-term care-EMS model: A before-and-after cohort analysis of an Extended Care Paramedic program. *Prehospital Emergency Care, 20*(1), 111-116. doi:10.3109/10903127.2015.1051678
- Johnson, R., & Waterfield, J. (2004). Making words count: The value of qualitative research. *Physiotherapy Research International, 9*(3), 121-131. doi:10.1002/pri.312
- Jones, M. (2005). Role development and effective practice in specialist and advanced practice roles in acute hospital settings: Systematic review and meta-synthesis. *Journal of Advanced Nursing, 49*(2), 191-209. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2004.03279.x
- Joyce, C., & Piterman, L. (2008). Trends in GP home visits. *Australian Family Physician, 37*(12), 1039-1042.

- Joyce, C. M., Wainer, J., Piterman, L., Wyatt, A., & Archer, F. (2009). Trends in the paramedic workforce: A profession in transition. *Australian Health Review*, *33*(4), 533-540.
- Kapborg, I., & Fischbein, S. (1998). Nurse education and professional work: Transition problems? *Nurse Education Today*, *18*(2), 165-171.
- Keeney, S., Hasson, F., & McKenna, H. (2011). *The Delphi technique in nursing and health research*. Chichester, West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Kelley, A., Ettner, S., Morrison, R., Du, Q., Wenger, N., & Sarkisian, C. (2011). Determinants of medical expenditures in the last 6 months of life. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, *154*(4), 235-242. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-154-4-201102150-00004
- Kelly, N., & Mathews, M. (2001). The transition to first position as nurse practitioner. *Journal of Nursing Education*, *40*(4), 156-162. doi:10.3928/0148-4834-20010401-05
- Kennedy, S. (2011). *The future of emergency medical services: Less emergency, more medical services* Master's thesis. Royal Roads University (Canada), Ann Arbor.
- Kennedy, S., Kenny, A., & O'Meara, P. (2015). Student paramedic experience of transition into the workforce: A scoping review. *Nurse Education Today*, *35*(10), 1037-1043. doi:10.1016/j.nedt.2015.04.015
- Kizer, K., Shore, K., & Moulin, A. (2013). Community paramedicine: A promising model for integrating emergency and primary care. Retrieved 15 May, 2017, from Institute for Population Health Improvement, UC Davis, https://www.ucdmc.ucdavis.edu/iphi/publications/reports/resources/IPHI_CommunityParamedicineReport_Final%20070913.pdf
- Kneebone, R., Kidd, J., Nestel, D., Asvall, S., Paraskeva, P., & Darzi, A. (2002). An innovative model for teaching and learning clinical procedures. *Medical Education*, *36*(7), 628-634. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2923.2002.01261.x
- Koch, T., & Harrington, A. (1998). Reconceptualizing rigour: The case for reflexivity. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *28*(4), 882-890. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2648.1998.00725.x
- Kralik, D., Visentin, K., & Van Loon, A. (2006). Transition: A literature review. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *55*(3), 320-329. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03899.x

- Kramer, M. (1974). *Reality shock: Why nurses leave nursing*. Mosby.
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Lazarsfeld-Jensen, A. (2014). Telling stories out of school: Experiencing the paramedic's oral traditions and role dissonance. *Nurse Education in Practice, 14*(6), 734-739. doi:10.1016/j.nepr.2014.10.001
- Lazarsfeld-Jensen, A., Bridges, D., & Carver, H. (2014). Graduates welcome on-road: A culture shift in ambulance preceptorship made clear through retrospective analysis. *Focus on Health Professional Education, 16*(1), 20-30. doi:10.11157/fohpe.v16i1.37
- Lazarsfeld-Jensen, A., Bridges, D., & Loftus, S. (2011). Transitions: Command culture and autonomous paramedic practice. Retrieved 13 July, 2017, from Charles Sturt University, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269279385_TRANSITIONS_Command_culture_and_autonomous_paramedic_practice
- Li, L., Grimshaw, J., Nielsen, C., Judd, M., Coyte, P., & Graham, I. (2009). Evolution of Wenger's concept of community of practice. *Implementation Science, 4*, 11. doi:10.1186/1748-5908-4-11
- Liamputtong, P. (2009). *Qualitative research methods* (3rd ed.). South Melbourne: Oxford University Press.
- Lincoln, Y., & Guba, E. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, California: SAGE.
- Long, D., Clark, M., Lim, D., Devenish, S. (2016). What's in a name? The confusion in nomenclature of low-acuity specialist roles in paramedicine. [Commentary]. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 13*(3), 1-2.
- Lum, L., Kervin, J., Clark, K., Reid, F., & Sirola, W. (1998). Explaining nursing turnover intent: Job satisfaction, pay satisfaction, or organizational commitment? *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 19*(3), 305-320. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1099-1379(199805)19:3<305::AID-JOB843>3.0.CO;2-N
- Lusty, R. (2013). Career crossroads: A Delphi study of the motivations and concerns of mid-career teachers in NSW Department of Education and Communities primary schools. *Leading and Managing, 19*(2), 88-105.
- Macey, W., & Schneider, B. (2008). The meaning of employee engagement. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology, 1*(1), 3-30. doi:10.1111/j.1754-9434.2007.0002.x

- Malterud, K. (2001a). Qualitative research: Standards, challenges, and guidelines. *Lancet*, *358*(9280), 483-488. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(01)05627-6
- Malterud, K. (2001b). Qualitative research: Standards, challenges, and guidelines. *The Lancet*, *358*(9280), 483-488. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(01)05627-6
- Manning, L., & Neville, S. (2009). Work-role transition: From staff nurse to clinical nurse educator. *Nursing Praxis in New Zealand*, *25*(2), 41-53.
- Martin-Misener, R., Downe-Wamboldt, B., Cain, E., & Girouard, M. (2009). Cost effectiveness and outcomes of a nurse practitioner-paramedic-family physician model of care: The Long and Brier Islands study. *Primary Health Care Research and Development*, *10*(1), 14-25. doi:10.1017/S1463423608000959
- Martin, A., O'Meara, P., & Farmer, J. (2015). Consumer perspectives of a community paramedicine program in rural Ontario. *Australian Journal of Rural Health*, 278-283. doi:10.1111/ajr.12259
- Mason, M. (2010). Sample size and saturation in PhD studies using qualitative interviews. *Qualitative Social Research*, *11*(3). doi:10.17169/fqs-11.3.1428
- Mason, S., Knowles, E., Colwell, B., Dixon, S., Wardrope, J., Gorringer, R., . . . Nicholl, J. (2007). Effectiveness of paramedic practitioners in attending 999 calls from elderly people in the community: Cluster randomised controlled trial. *British Medical Journal*, *335*(7626), 919-922. doi:10.1136/bmj.39343.649097.55
- Mason, S., O'Keeffe, C., Coleman, P., O'Hara, R., Dixon, S., Rick, J., . . . Stride, C. (2009). A multi-centre community intervention trial to evaluate the clinical and cost effectiveness of emergency care practitioners. Retrieved 21 April, 2015, from University of Sheffield, http://www.netscc.ac.uk/hhdr/files/project/SDO_FR_08-1519-98_V01.pdf
- May, D., Gilson, R., & Harter, L. (2004). The psychological conditions of meaningfulness, safety and availability and the engagement of the human spirit at work. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, *77*(1), 11-37. doi:10.1348/096317904322915892
- Maylone, M., Ranieri, L., Griffin, M., McNulty, R., & Fitzpatrick, J. (2011). Collaboration and autonomy: Perceptions among nurse practitioners. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*, *23*(1), 51-57. doi:10.1111/j.1745-7599.2010.00576.x

- McConnell-Henry, T., James, A., Chapman, Y., & Francis, K. (2009). Researching with people you know: Issues in interviewing. *Contemporary Nurse: A Journal for the Australian Nursing Profession*, 34(1), 2-9. doi:10.5172/conu.2009.34.1.002
- McFarlane, P. (2010). *Understanding the challenges: The factors that drive the decision to enter and exit Intensive Care Paramedic practice in Australian ambulance services* Master's thesis. The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland.
- McRae, I., & Pham, M. (2016). When is a GP home-visit program financially viable? *Australian Journal of Primary Health*, 22(6), 554-558. doi:10.1071/PY15074
- Meleis, A., Sawyer, L., Im, E., Messias, D., & Schumacher, K. (2000). Experiencing transitions: An emerging middle-range theory. *Advances in Nursing Science*, 23(1), 12-28. doi:10.1097/00012272-200009000-00006
- Mercer, A. (2007). *Role transition and the nurse practitioner: An investigation into the experience of professional autonomy* Doctoral dissertation. Bournemouth University.
- Michau, R., Roberts, S., Williams, B., & Boyle, M. (2009). An investigation of theory-practice gap in undergraduate paramedic education. *BMC Medical Education*, 9(1). doi:10.1186/1472-6920-9-23
- Mills, J., Bonner, A., & Francis, K. (2008). The development of constructivist grounded theory. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 5(1), 25-35. doi:10.1177/160940690600500103
- Mitchell, J. (1983). When disaster strikes: The critical incident stress debriefing process. *Journal of Emergency Medical Services*, 8, 36-39.
- Mohamed, T., Kennedy, A., & Oliver, B. (2017). Grounded theory and the conundrum of literature review: Framework for novice researchers. *The Qualitative Report*, 22(4), 1199-1210.
- Monash University Extended Care Paramedic. (2017). Retrieved 2 July, 2017, from Monash University, <http://med.monash.edu.au/cehpp/postgrad/extended-care-paramedic.html>
- Morgeson, F., & Humphrey, S. (2006). The Work Design Questionnaire (WDQ): Developing and validating a comprehensive measure for assessing job design and the nature of work. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91(6), 1321-1339. doi:10.1037/0021-9010.91.6.1321

- Morse, J. (1993). *Critical Issues in Qualitative Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE.
- Moy, J. (1997). Development of clinical guidelines. In M. Mengel & S. Fields (Eds.), *Introduction to Clinical Skills* (pp. 449-465). Boston: Springer.
- Mulvale, G., Embrett, M., & Razavi, S. (2016). 'Gearing Up' to improve interprofessional collaboration in primary care: A systematic review and conceptual framework. *BMC Family Practice*, *17*(1), 83-96. doi:10.1186/s12875-016-0492-1
- Munro, G., O'Meara, P., & Kenny, A. (2017). Paramedic transition into academic roles in universities: A demographic and qualification survey of paramedic academics in Australia and New Zealand. *Irish Journal of Paramedicine*, *1*(2).
- National Health and Medical Research Council. (2014). National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007) - Updated May 2015. Retrieved 1 August, 2017, from Australian Government, https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/files/nhmrc/publications/attachments/e72_national_statement_may_2015_150514_a.pdf
- Neal, T. (2008). *Mentoring, self-efficacy, and nurse practitioner students: A modified replication* Doctoral Dissertation. Ball State University, Indiana.
- Ng, T., & Sorensen, K. (2008). Toward a further understanding of the relationships between perceptions of support and work attitudes: A meta-analysis. *Group & Organization Management*, *33*(3), 243-268. doi:10.1177/1059601107313307
- Nicholson, N. (1984). A Theory of work role transitions. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, *29*(2), 172-191. doi:10.2307/2393172
- Nolan, M. (2011). Community Paramedicine: Submission to the Standing Committee on Health. Retrieved 10 September, 2017, from https://www.google.com.au/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKewiEybiDo5rWAhVKiLwKHQj9BMwQFggmMAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.aph.gov.au%2FDocumentStore.ashx%3Fid%3D64bef864-1745-43aa-a8dd-105899d68f1f&usg=AFQjCNEM1Cj_AeeIYISVBjXiasWT4omxAq
- Nolan, M., Hillier, T., & D'Angelo, C. (2012). Community Paramedicine in Canada. Retrieved 24 March, 2016, from Emergency Medical Services Chiefs of Canada, <https://www.nasemso.org/Projects/RuralEMS/documents/CommunityParamedicineCanada.pdf>

- Norman, G. (2009). Dual processing and diagnostic errors. *Advances in Health Sciences Education, 14*(1), 37-49. doi:10.1007/s10459-009-9179-x
- NSW Ambulance. (2015). NSW Ambulance Year in Review 2013/14. Retrieved 16 November, 2016, from NSW Health, <http://www.ambulance.nsw.gov.au/Media/docs/YearinReview2014FIN-AL2-fd3c85ac-26fa-40cc-92c1-f07b5afe1ff2-0.pdf>
- NSW Ambulance. (2016). Extended Care Paramedics - Meeting future out of hospital aged care needs. Retrieved 12 May, 2017, from NSW Health, <http://www.phemc.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Lauren-Cowgill.-Extended-Care-Paramedic-1.pdf>
- NSW Ambulance. (n.d.-a). Extended Care Paramedics. Retrieved 12 May, 2017, from NSW Health, http://www.ambulance.nsw.gov.au/media/docs/ECP_V3-7e0f7019-8d7b-41a1-9999-34f4b9573bb6-0.pdf
- NSW Ambulance. (n.d.-b). Integrated Care Strategy. Retrieved 27 August, 2017, from NSW Health, http://www.ambulance.nsw.gov.au/media/docs/Integrated%20Care_Sstrategy_V3-d46f9dda-0351-4729-9409-21da0f7a5f38-0.pdf
- NSW Government. (2017). Population. Retrieved 3 August, 2017, from <https://www.nsw.gov.au/about-new-south-wales/population/>
- NSW Health. (2016). *NSW Health 2015-16 Annual Report*. North Sydney: NSW Health.
- O'Brien, K., Moore, A., Dawson, D. A., & Hartley, P. R. (2014). An Australian story: Paramedic education and practice in transition. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 11*(3), 1-13.
- O'Meara, P. (2009). Paramedics marching toward professionalism. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 7*(1), 1-5.
- O'Meara, P. (2012). Searching for paramedic academics: Vital for our future, but nowhere to be seen! *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 4*(4), 1-3.
- O'Meara, P. (2014). Community paramedics: A scoping review of their emergence and potential impact. *International Paramedic Practice, 4*(1), 5-12. doi:10.12968/ippr.2014.4.1.5

- O'Meara, P., & Grbich, C. (2009). *Paramedics in Australia: Contemporary challenges of practice*. Frenchs Forest, NSW: Pearson Education Australia.
- O'Meara, P., Ruest, M., & Martin, A. (2015). Integrating a Community Paramedicine program with local health, aged care and social services: An observational ethnographic study. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, *12*(5), 1-6.
- O'Meara, P., Ruest, M., & Stirling, C. (2014). Community paramedicine: Higher education as an enabling factor. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, *11*(2), 1-9.
- O'Meara, P., Stirling, C., Ruest, M., & Martin, A. (2016). Community paramedicine model of care: An observational, ethnographic case study. *BMC Health Services Research*, *16*(1), 39-48.
doi:10.1186/s12913-016-1282-0
- O'Meara, P., Tourle, V., Madigan, V., & Lighton, D. (2012). Getting in touch with paramedic student career intentions. *Health Education Journal*, *71*(3), 376-385. doi:10.1177/0017896911406962
- O'Meara, P., Tourle, V., Stirling, C., Walker, J., & Pedler, D. (2012). Extending the paramedic role in rural Australia: A story of flexibility and innovation. *Rural and Remote Health*, *12*(2), 1-13.
- O'Reilly, C., Chatman, J., & Caldwell, D. (1991). People and organizational culture: A profile comparison approach to assessing person-organization fit. *The Academy of Management Journal*, *34*(3), 487-516. doi:10.2307/256404
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2015). *OECD Reviews of Health Care Quality: Australia 2015*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Paley, J., Cheyne, H., Dalglish, L., Duncan, E., & Niven, C. (2007). Nursing's ways of knowing and dual process theories of cognition. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *60*(6), 692-701. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04478.x
- Paramedics Australasia. (2009). Paramedicine Role Descriptions. Retrieved 19 April, 2015, from Paramedics Australasia, http://www.paramedics.org/content/2009/07/PRD_211212_WEBONLY.pdf
- Parker, R. (2008). The management and operations of the Ambulance Service of NSW Retrieved 12 April, 2017, from NSW Government,

<http://www.ambulance.nsw.gov.au/Media/docs/081020councilreport-83758ed3-d308-46ff-8a4d-0882822581fa-0.pdf>

- Patterson, D., & Skillman, S. (2013). *A national agenda for community paramedicine research*. Seattle, Washington: University of Washington.
- Peña, A. (2010). The Dreyfus model of clinical problem-solving skills acquisition: A critical perspective. *Medical Education Online, 15*, 1-11. doi:10.3402/meo.v15i0.4846
- Pezalla, A., Pettigrew, J., & Miller-Day, M. (2012). Researching the researcher-as-instrument: An exercise in interviewer self-reflexivity. *Qualitative Research, 12*(2), 165-185.
- Philippon, D., & Braithwaite, J. (2008). Health system organization and governance in Canada and Australia: A comparison of historical developments, recent policy changes and future implications. *Healthcare Policy, 4*(1), 168-186. doi:10.12927/hcpol.2008.19991
- Phillips, C., Esterman, A., Smith, C., & Kenny, A. (2013). Predictors of successful transition to registered nurse. *Journal of Advanced Nursing, 69*(6), 1314-1322. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2012.06123.x
- Pong, R., DesMeules, M., & Lagacé, C. (2009). Rural–urban disparities in health: How does Canada fare and how does Canada compare with Australia? *Australian Journal of Rural Health, 17*(1), 58-64. doi:10.1111/j.1440-1584.2008.01039.x
- Poronsky, C. (2012). A literature review of mentoring for RN-to-FNP transition. *Journal of Nursing Education, 51*(11), 623-631. doi:10.3928/01484834-20120914-03
- Poronsky, C. (2013). Exploring the transition from Registered Nurse to Family Nurse Practitioner. *Journal of Professional Nursing, 29*(6), 350-358. doi:10.1016/j.profnurs.2012.10.011
- Porter, S. (2013). *An exploration of the support needs of ambulance paramedics* Doctoral dissertation. Victoria University.
- Pretz, J. (2008). Intuition versus analysis: Strategy and experience in complex everyday problem solving. *Memory & Cognition, 36*(3), 554-566. doi:10.3758/MC.36.3.554
- Price, R., Bendall, J., Patterson, J., & Middleton, P. (2013). What causes adverse events in prehospital care? A human-factors approach. *Emergency Medicine Journal, 30*(7), 583-588. doi:10.1136/emered-2011-200971

- Productivity Commission. (2014). Report on Government Services 2014. Retrieved 23 November, 2015, from Australian Government, <http://www.pc.gov.au/research/recurring/report-on-government-services/2014>
- Pullon, S. (2008). Competence, respect and trust: Key features of successful interprofessional nurse-doctor relationships. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 22(2), 133-147. doi:10.1080/13561820701795069
- Queensland Health. (2014). Ministerial taskforce on health practitioner expanded scope of practice. Retrieved 14 May, 2015, from Queensland Government, https://www.health.qld.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0031/161977/ministerial-taskforce-report.pdf
- Råheim, M., Magnussen, L., Sekse, R., Lunde, Å., Jacobsen, T., & Blystad, A. (2016). Researcher–researched relationship in qualitative research: Shifts in positions and researcher vulnerability. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 11(1), 1-12. doi:10.3402/qhw.v11.30996
- Ramalho, R., Adams, P., Huggard, P., & Hoare, K. (2015). Literature review and constructivist grounded theory methodology. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung*, 16(3).
- Rana, S., Ardichvili, A., & Tkachenko, O. (2014). A theoretical model of the antecedents and outcomes of employee engagement: Dubin's method. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 26(3-4), 249-266. doi:10.1108/JWL-09-2013-0063
- Raven, S., Tippett, V., Ferguson, J., & Smith, S. (2006). *An exploration of expanded paramedic healthcare roles for Queensland*. Brisbane: Queensland Department of Emergency Services.
- Reaburn, G., Zolcinski, R., & Fyfe, S. (2017). Rural paramedic practitioner—a future model of care. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine*, 14(1), 1-6.
- Reeve, C., Pashen, D., Mumme, H., De La Rue, S., & Cheffins, T. (2008). Expanding the role of paramedics in northern Queensland: An evaluation of population health training. *Australian Journal of Rural Health*, 16(6), 370-375. doi:10.1111/j.1440-1584.2008.01018.x
- Regehr, C., Goldberg, G., & Hughes, J. (2002). Exposure to human tragedy, empathy, and trauma in ambulance paramedics. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 72(4), 505-513. doi:10.1037/0002-9432.72.4.505

- Reichertz, J. (2007). Abduction: The logic of discovery of grounded theory. In A. Bryant & K. Charmaz (Eds.), *The Sage Handbook of Grounded Theory* (pp. 214-228). London: SAGE.
- Reynolds, L. (2008). *Beyond the front line: An interpretative ethnography of an ambulance service* Doctoral dissertation. University of South Australia, Adelaide.
- Richmond, T., & Becker, D. (2005). Creating an advanced practice nurse-friendly culture: A marathon, not a sprint. *AACN Clinical Issues*, 16(1), 58-66. doi:10.1097/00044067-200501000-00007
- Robinson, O. (2014). Sampling in interview-based qualitative research: A theoretical and practical guide. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11(1), 25-41. doi:10.1080/14780887.2013.801543
- Rolfe, G. (2006). Validity, trustworthiness and rigour: Quality and the idea of qualitative research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 53(3), 304-310. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03727.x
- Ruest, M., Stichman, A., & Day, C. (2014). Evaluating the impact on 911 calls by an in-home programme with a multidisciplinary team. *International Paramedic Practice*, 1(4), 125-132.
- Ryan, D. (2009). Standards and Criteria for the Accreditation of Nursing and Midwifery Courses leading to Registration, Enrolment, Endorsement, and Authorisation in Australia-with Evidence Guide. Retrieved 2 June, 2015, from Australian Nursing and Midwifery Council, <http://www.nursingmidwiferyboard.gov.au/documents/default.aspx?record=WD10/1371&dbid=AP&chksum=oowuEdRfEOPZ/1hrmtoMbA==>
- SA Ambulance Service. (2013). *ECP Information Night*. Adelaide: Internal SAAS publication: unpublished.
- SA Ambulance Service. (2014a). Annual Report 2013-14. Retrieved 23 April, 2015, from <http://www.saambulance.com.au/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=vESiYWzXc2s%3d&tabid=122>
- SA Ambulance Service. (2014b). *Student Information Handbook Extended Care Paramedic (ECP) Program*. Adelaide: Internal SAAS handbook: unpublished.
- SA Ambulance Service. (2016). Annual Report 2015-16. Retrieved 23 February, 2017, from SA Ambulance Service Corporate Communications, <http://www.saambulance.com.au/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=Kuvvcrydkxw%3D&tabid=122>

- Saldaña, J. (2015). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. London: SAGE.
- Schraw, G., Crippen, K., & Hartley, K. (2006). Promoting self-regulation in science education: Metacognition as part of a broader perspective on learning. *Research in Science Education, 36*(1-2), 111-139. doi:10.1007/s11165-005-3917-8
- Scotland, J. (2012). Exploring the philosophical underpinnings of research: Relating ontology and epistemology to the methodology and methods of the scientific, interpretive, and critical research paradigms. *English Language Teaching, 5*(9), 9-16. doi:10.5539/elt.v5n9p9
- Scully, P. (2011). Taking care of staff: A comprehensive model of support for paramedics and emergency medical dispatchers. *Traumatology, 17*(4), 35-42. doi:10.1177/1534765611430129
- Seah, C., Mackenzie, L., & Gamble, J. (2011). Transition of graduates of the Master of Occupational Therapy to practice. *Australian Occupational Therapy Journal, 58*(2), 103-110. doi:10.1111/j.1440-1630.2010.00899.x
- Seel, D., & Turner, M. (2016). Industrial paramedic: An emerging speciality? *Journal of Paramedic Practice, 8*(7), 350-355.
- Shenton, A. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. *Education for information, 22*(2), 63-75. doi:10.3233/EFI-2004-22201
- Shin, J., Taylor, M., & Seo, M. (2012). Resources for change: The relationships of organizational inducements and psychological resilience to employees' attitudes and behaviors toward organizational change. *Academy of Management Journal, 55*(3), 727-748. doi:10.5465/amj.2010.0325
- Simpson, P., Thomas, R., Bendall, J., Lord, B., Lord, S., & Close, J. (2017). 'Popping nana back into bed' - a qualitative exploration of paramedic decision making when caring for older people who have fallen. *BMC Health Services Research, 17*(1), 299. doi:10.1186/s12913-017-2243-y
- Smith, E., Archer, F., & Burgess, S. (2012). The development of an updated prehospital search filter for the Cochrane Library: Prehospital Search Filter Version 2.0. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 8*(4), 1-5.
- Smith, E., Jennings, P., McDonald, S., MacPherson, C., O'Brien, T., & Archer, F. (2007). The Cochrane Library as a resource for evidence on out-of-

- hospital health care interventions. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 49(3), 344-350. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2006.09.026
- Smith, S., & Roehrs, C. (2009). High-fidelity simulation: Factors correlated with nursing student satisfaction and self-confidence. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 30(2), 74-78.
- Snooks, H., Evans, A., Wells, B., Peconi, J., Thomas, M., Woollard, M., . . . Hartley-Sharpe, C. (2009). What are the highest priorities for research in emergency prehospital care? *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 26(8), 549-550. doi:10.1136/emj.2008.065862
- Snooks, H., Kearsley, N., Dale, J., Halter, M., Redhead, J., & Foster, J. (2005). Gaps between policy, protocols and practice: a qualitative study of the views and practice of emergency ambulance staff concerning the care of patients with non-urgent needs. *Quality & Safety in Health Care*, 14(4), 251-257. doi:10.1136/qshc.2004.012195
- South Australia Government. (2017). Living in South Australia. Retrieved 2 August, 2017, from <https://www.sa.gov.au/topics/about-sa/about-sa>
- Spinks, K. (2009). Transition from neonatal nurse to advanced neonatal nurse practitioner: A reflective account. *Journal of Neonatal Nursing*, 15(1), 8-13. doi:10.1016/j.jnn.2008.07.007
- Spoelstra, S., & Robbins, L. (2010). A qualitative study of role transition from RN to APN. *International Journal of Nursing Education Scholarship*, 7(1), 1-15. doi:10.2202/1548-923X.2020
- Statistics Canada. (2011). Population by home language, by province and territory (2011 Census). Retrieved 23 April, 2015, from Government of Canada, <http://www.statcan.gc.ca/tables-tableaux/sum-som/l01/cst01/demo61c-eng.htm>
- Suddaby, R. (2006). From the editors: What grounded theory is not. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(4), 633-642. doi:10.5465/AMJ.2006.22083020
- Sullivan-Bentz, M., Humbert, J., Cragg, B., Legault, F., Laflamme, C., Bailey, P., & Doucette, S. (2010). Supporting primary health care nurse practitioners' transition to practice. *Canadian Family Physician*, 56(11), 1176-1182.
- Suter, E., Arndt, J., Arthur, N., Parboosingh, J., Taylor, E., & Deutschlander, S. (2009). Role understanding and effective communication as core competencies for collaborative practice. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 23(1), 41-51. doi:10.1080/13561820802338579

- Swain, A., Hoyle, S., & Long, A. (2010). The changing face of prehospital care in New Zealand: The role of extended care paramedics. *The New Zealand Medical Journal*, *123*(1309), 11-14.
- Tavares, W., Bowles, R., & Donelon, B. (2016). Informing a Canadian paramedic profile: Framing concepts, roles and crosscutting themes. *BMC Health Services Research*, *16*(1), 477-493. doi:10.1186/s12913-016-1739-1
- Thompson, C., Williams, K., Morris, D., Lago, L., Kobel, C., Quinsey, K., . . . Masso, M. (2014). HWA Expanded Scopes of Practice program evaluation: Extending the Role of Paramedics sub-project: Final report. Retrieved 23 April, 2015, from Australian Health Services Research Institute, <http://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1383&context=ahsri>
- Timmermans, S., & Tavory, I. (2012). Theory Construction in Qualitative Research: From Grounded Theory to Abductive Analysis. *Sociological Theory*, *30*(3), 167-186. doi:10.1177/0735275112457914
- Tohira, H., Williams, T. A., Jacobs, I., Bremner, A., & Finn, J. (2013). The impact of new prehospital practitioners on ambulance transportation to the emergency department: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Emergency Medicine Journal*, 88-94. doi:10.1136/emered-2013-202976
- Tracy, S. (2010). Qualitative quality: Eight "big-tent" criteria for excellent qualitative research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, *16*(10), 837-851. doi:10.1177/1077800410383121
- Tuckett, A. (2005). Part II. Rigour in qualitative research: Complexities and solutions. *Nurse Researcher*, *13*(1), 29-42.
- Twining, P., Heller, R., Nussbaum, M., & Tsai, C. (2017). Some guidance on conducting and reporting qualitative studies. *Computers and Education*, *106*, 1-9. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2016.12.002
- Underhill, C. (2006). The effectiveness of mentoring programs in corporate settings: A meta-analytical review of the literature. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, *68*(2), 292-307. doi:10.1016/j.jvb.2005.05.003
- Urquhart, C. (2012). *Grounded theory for qualitative research: A practical guide*. London: SAGE.
- Veronesi, J. (1999). Changing the face of emergency medical services in the 21st century. *Topics in Emergency Medicine*, *21*(1), 58-64.

- Verquer, M., Beehr, T., & Wagner, S. (2003). A meta-analysis of relations between person–organization fit and work attitudes. *Journal of Vocational Behavior, 63*(3), 473-489. doi:10.1016/S0001-8791(02)00036-2
- Wang, E., Quinones, J., Fitch, M., Dooley-Hash, S., Griswold-Theodorson, S., Medzon, R., . . . Clay, L. (2008). Developing technical expertise in emergency medicine—the role of simulation in procedural skill acquisition. *Academic Emergency Medicine, 15*(11), 1046-1057. doi:10.1111/j.1553-2712.2008.00218.x
- Wang, H. (2011). Community Paramedicine Summary of Evidence. Retrieved 27 April, 2015, from http://communityparamedic.ca/site/media/download_gallery/comm%20paramed.pdf
- Wankhade, P. (2012). Different cultures of management and their relationships with organizational performance: Evidence from the UK ambulance service. *Public Money & Management, 32*(5), 381-388. doi:10.1080/09540962.2012.676312
- Wankhade, P., & Brinkman, J. (2014). The negative consequences of culture change management: Evidence from a UK NHS ambulance service. *International Journal of Public Sector Management, 27*(1), 2-25. doi:10.1108/IJPSM-05-2012-0058
- Waring, J. (2005). Beyond blame: Cultural barriers to medical incident reporting. *Social Science & Medicine, 60*(9), 1927-1935. doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2004.08.055
- Webster, J., & Watson, R. (2002). Analyzing the past to prepare for the future: Writing a literature review. *MIS Quarterly, 26*(2), xiii-xxiii.
- Wenger, E. (2011). Communities of practice: A brief introduction. Retrieved 12 May, 2017, from University of Oregon, <https://scholarsbank.uoregon.edu/xmlui/handle/1794/11736>
- West, M., & Rushton, R. (1989). Mismatches in the work-role transitions. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 62*(4), 271-286.
- Westerman, M., Teunissen, P., van der Vleuten, C., Scherpbier, A., Siegert, C. E., van der Lee, N., & Scheele, F. (2010). Understanding the transition from resident to attending physician: A transdisciplinary, qualitative study. *Academic Medicine, 85*(12), 1914-1919. doi:10.1097/ACM.0b013e3181fa2913

- Whetzel, E., & Wagner, L. (2008). Transitioning paramedics into emergency nurses: A unique population of new nurses. *Journal of Emergency Nursing, 34*(2), 154-155. doi:10.1016/j.jen.2008.01.003
- White, R., & Wingrove, G. (2012). Principles for community paramedicine programs. Retrieved 2 February, 2017, from <https://www.ruralhealthweb.org/getattachment/Advocate/Policy-Documents/PrinciplesforCommunityParamedicineSept-2012.pdf.aspx?lang=en-US>
- Williams, B., Brown, T., & Onsmann, A. (2012). From stretcher-bearer to paramedic: The Australian paramedics' move towards professionalisation. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 7*(4), 1-12.
- Williams, R. (2012). Nurses who work in the ambulance service: Ruth Williams concludes a two-part article on urgent care staff who work alongside paramedics by presenting the accounts of five practitioners who have changed career. *Emergency Nurse, 20*(2), 14-17.
- Wingrove, G. (2012). International Roundtable on Community Paramedicine. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 9*(1), 1-3.
- Woollard, M. (2012). The role of the paramedic practitioner in the UK. *Australasian Journal of Paramedicine, 4*(1), 1-9.
- Wright, C. (2016). Community Paramedics. Retrieved 6 August, 2017, from SA Ambulance Service, <https://www.aacb.asn.au/documents/item/4467>
- Wright, D. (2008). Expanding ambulance care for the elderly. An investigation into models of Extended Care Paramedic Programs in Canada and the United Kingdom. Retrieved 5 June, 2017, from The Winston Churchill Memorial Trust of Australia, https://www.churchilltrust.com.au/media/fellows/WRIGHT_Douglas_2007.pdf

Appendices

Appendix A

Research Ethics, Integrity and Safety Modules 1 and 2

Appendix B

Queensland University of Technology University Human Research

Ethics Committee Approval

-----Original Message-----

From: QUT Research Ethics Unit
Sent: Wednesday, 30 September 2015 1:18 PM
To: Michele Clark; David Lim; Scott Devenish; Mr David Long
Cc: Janette Lamb
Subject: Ethics application - approved - 1500000813

Dear Prof Michele Clark and Mr David Long

Project Title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role

Ethics Category: Human - Low Risk
Approval Number: 1500000813
Approved Until: 30/09/2017
(subject to receipt of satisfactory progress reports)

We are pleased to advise that your application has been reviewed and confirmed as meeting the requirements of the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research.

I can therefore confirm that your application is APPROVED.
If you require a formal approval certificate please advise via reply email.

CONDITIONS OF APPROVAL

Please ensure you and all other team members read through and understand all UHREC conditions of approval prior to commencing any data collection:

- > Standard: Please see attached or go to <http://www.orei.qut.edu.au/human/stdconditions.jsp>
- > Specific: None apply

Decisions related to low risk ethical review are subject to ratification at the next available UHREC meeting. You will only be contacted again in relation to this matter if UHREC raises any additional questions or concerns.

Whilst the data collection of your project has received QUT ethical clearance, the decision to commence and authority to commence may be dependent on factors beyond the remit of the QUT ethics review process. For example, your research may need ethics clearance from other organisations or permissions from other organisations to access staff. Therefore the proposed data collection should not commence until you have satisfied these requirements.

Please don't hesitate to contact us if you have any queries.

We wish you all the best with your research.

Kind regards

Janette Lamb / Debbie Smith
on behalf of Chair UHREC
Office of Research Ethics & Integrity
Level 4 | 88 Musk Avenue | Kelvin Grove
p: +61 7 3138 5123 / 3138 4673
e: ethicscontact@qut.edu.au
w: <http://www.orei.qut.edu.au>

Appendix C

QUT Ethics Variation Approval 1 of 2

From: Research Ethics <ethicscontact@qut.edu.au>
Date: 10 December 2015 2:54:55 pm AEST
To: Prof Michele Clark <mj.clark@qut.edu.au>, Mr David Long <d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au>
Cc: Ms Deborah Smith <d3.smith@qut.edu.au>
Subject: Ethics variation - approved - 1500000813

Dear Prof Michele Clark

Approval #: 1500000813
End Date: 30/09/2017
Project Title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role

This email is to advise that your variation has been considered by the Chair, University Human Research Ethics Committee. This HREC is constituted and operates in accordance with the National Health and Medical Research Council's (NHMRC) National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007).

Approval has been provided:

- < For the employer email recruit to request potential participants to make contact with the research team.
- < For the SA Health and NSW Health HRECs will approve the use of work email accounts to disseminate an email requesting participants.
- < For the associated changes to Participant Info-Consent Form (PICF) and recruitment materials.

Documents approved (with above changes):

Low risk application V2 27/11/15
PICF interview V2 27/11/15
Email recruit NSW V1 27/11/15
Email recruit SAA V1 27/11/15
Flyer recruit NSW V1 27/11/15
Flyer recruit SAA V1 27/11/15
Facebook recruit V2 27/11/15

We apologise for the time from your response to approval; we are experiencing some delays in review and processing research ethics applications due factors out of our control.

PLEASE NOTE:
RESEARCH SAFETY -- Ensure any health and safety risks relating to this

variation have been appropriately considered, particularly if your project required a Health and Safety Risk Assessment.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST -- If this variation will introduce any additional perceived or actual conflicts of interest please advise the Research Ethics Unit by return email.

Please don't hesitate to contact us if you have any questions.

Regards

Janette Lamb / Debbie Smith
on behalf of Chair UHREC
Office of Research Ethics & Integrity
Level 4 | 88 Musk Avenue | Kelvin Grove
p: +61 7 3138 5123 / 3138 4673
e: ethicscontact@qut.edu.au
w: <http://www.orei.qut.edu.au>

QUT Ethics Variation Approval

2 of 2

-----Original Message-----

From: QUT Research Ethics Advisory Team

Sent: Tuesday, 16 February 2016 9:25 AM

To: Michele Clark <mj.clark@qut.edu.au>; David Long <d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au>

Cc: Janette Lamb <jd.lamb@qut.edu.au>

Subject: Ethics variation - approved - 1500000813

Dear Prof Michele Clark and Mr David Long

Approval #: 1500000813

End Date: 30/09/2017

Project Title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role

This email is to advise that your variation has been considered by the Chair, University Human Research Ethics Committee. This HREC is constituted and operates in accordance with the National Health and Medical Research Council's (NHMRC) National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007).

Approval has been provided for:

- < The addition of the option to interview participants in their own home if that is their preference.
- < The revised info-consent as per South Australia Health HREC.

Please find attached a FINAL info-consent ready for use.

PLEASE NOTE:

RESEARCH SAFETY -- Ensure any health and safety risks relating to this variation have been appropriately considered, particularly if your project required a Health and Safety Risk Assessment.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST -- If this variation will introduce any additional perceived or actual conflicts of interest please advise the Research Ethics Unit by return email.

Please don't hesitate to contact us if you have any questions.

Regards

Janette Lamb / Debbie Smith

on behalf of Chair UHREC

Office of Research Ethics & Integrity

Level 4 | 88 Musk Avenue | Kelvin Grove

p: +61 7 3138 5123 / 3138 4673

e: ethicscontact@qut.edu.au

w: <http://www.orei.qut.edu.au>

Appendix D

NSW Ambulance Ethics Approval

NSW Ambulance

excellence in care

TRIM File: 15/1055
Document: D16/4582

8 March 2016

Mr David Long
Queensland University of Technology
Ormiston QLD 4160

Via email: d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au

Dear Mr Long,

From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low acuity role.

Thank you for requesting permission to interview NSW Ambulance paramedics as part of the above named study. I am pleased to advise that the Ethics Review Committee has granted ethical approval of this research. Access to staff members through an email of invitation, but not recruitment through direct contact with potential participants, has been authorised at NSW Ambulance. Please liaise with Ms Michelle Sheil, Manager Low Acuity Care, to initiate recruitment of Extended Care Paramedics.

The study is approved for three years. The following conditions apply to this research study. These are additional to the requirement to comply with relevant laws, regulations in conducting this project.

1. By proceeding with this research, you acknowledge, and agree to comply with, *NSW Ambulance Terms and Conditions for Research with External Entities* (enclosed).
2. Proposed amendments to the research protocol or conduct of the research that may affect the ethical acceptability of the study must be submitted to me for review.
3. Proposed amendments to the research protocol or conduct of the research that may affect the ongoing acceptability of the study to NSW Ambulance must be submitted to me.
4. I attach the NSW Ambulance report form for approved projects. Progress reports must be submitted to me annually, and at the completion of the study. The first report for this study will be due in March 2017.
5. I must be notified of any complaints by NSW Ambulance participants.
6. Please note that research findings, reports, conference presentations and manuscripts must be submitted to me for review by the Chief Executive prior to publication.

I wish you every success in your research. Please contact me should you wish to discuss this matter further.

Yours sincerely

Rosemary Carney
Research Governance Officer

End

Cc Professor Michele Clark via email: mj.clark@qut.edu.au
Ms Michelle Shiel via email: mshiel@ambulance.nsw.gov.au

Appendix E

South Australia Department of Health and Ageing Human Research

Ethics Committee Approval

Government of South Australia

SA Health

SA Department for Health and Ageing Human
Research Ethics Committee

Citi Centre Building
Level 8, 11 Hindmarsh Square
Adelaide SA 5000

PO Box 287, Rundle Mall
Adelaide SA 5000
DX 243

Tel 08 8226 6278

Mr David Long
School of Clinical Science
Queensland University of Technology
8 Crestwood Close
ORMISTON QLD 4160

Dear Mr Long

HREC reference number: HREC/15/SAH/173

Project title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low acuity role

RE: HREC LNR Application – Approval

Thank you for responding to the issues raised by the SA Department for Health and Ageing Human Research Ethics Committee (DHA HREC) in relation to the above project. Your response was reviewed by a sub group of the HREC out-of-session.

I am pleased to advise that your application has been granted full ethics approval and appears to meet the requirements of the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research*.

The documents reviewed and approved include:

Document	Version	Date
Letter of Response to the DHA HREC	1.0	02 February 2016
LNR Application Form	1.0	14 December 2015
Australian Participant Information for QUT Research Project	2.0	02 February 2016
Confirmation Seminar Report	1.0	03 Augusts 2015
Interview Guide	1.0	14 December 2015
SAAS Approach Email	1.0	14 December 2015
SAAS Flyer	1.0	14 December 2015

Please note the following conditions of approval:

- The research must be conducted in accordance with the 'National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research.'
- A progress report, at least annually, must be provided to the HREC.
- When the project is completed, a final report must be provided to the HREC.
- The HREC must be notified of any complaints by participants or of adverse

HREC approval is valid for 3 years from the date of this letter.

Should you have any queries about the HREC's consideration of your project please contact the Executive Officer of the HREC, on (08) 8226 6278 or Health.HumanResearchEthicsCommittee@sa.gov.au

You are reminded that this letter constitutes ethical approval only. You must not commence this research project at a SA Health site until separate authorisation from the Chief Executive or delegate of that site has been obtained via the completion of a Site Specific Assessment form.

The HREC wishes you every success in your research.

Yours sincerely

**Catherine Blaikie
CHAIRPERSON
HUMAN RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE**

16/02/2016

Appendix F

Health Research Ethics Board of Alberta (HREBA) – Community Health Committee (CHC) Approval

Health Research Ethics Board of Alberta
Community Health Committee
1500, 10104 - 103 Avenue NW
Edmonton, Alberta, T5J 4A7
Telephone: (780) 423-5727
Fax: (780) 429-3509
Email: communityhealth@hreba.ca

CERTIFICATION OF RESEARCH ETHICS REVIEW

This is to acknowledge that the following study has been reviewed and on behalf of the Health Research Ethics Board of Alberta (HREBA) – Community Health Committee (CHC) has been approved.

Ethics ID: HREBA.CHC-16-0008
Principal Investigator: Michele Clark
Co-Investigator(s): There are no items to display
Student Co-Investigator(s): David Long
Study Title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role.
Sponsor (if applicable): N/A

Effective: May 25, 2016

Expires: April 28, 2017

The following documents have been reviewed and are approved for use:

- AHS_Approachemail_20160320, 1, March 20, 2016
- AHS_ParticipantInfoandConsentForm_20160320, 1, March 20, 2016
- AHS_InterviewGuide_20160320, March 20, 2016
- AHS_transcriberagreement_20161104, April 11, 2016
- AHS_PeerReviewArticulationSeminarReportDLong_20160320, March 20, 2016
- AHS_ResearchProjectProposal_v12_20160320, March 20, 2016

This Committee has been constituted following the *Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans* (TCPS 2) and deliberations of the CHC included all elements of the TCPS 2 and those described in Section 50 of the Health Information Act (HIA).

Members of the CHC who are named as investigators or co-investigators in research studies do not participate in discussion(s) related to, nor vote on, such studies when they are presented to the Committee. It is not our policy to release the names of the Committee membership, however, an outline of its composition can be provided.

Please refer to the accompanying letter for conditions of approval.

Approved on behalf of CHC by,

Date:

Appendix G

SA Ambulance Service Site Specific Assessment – Authorisation

David Long
School of Clinical Sciences
Queensland University of Technology
8 Crestwood Close
Ormiston
Queensland
4160

Telephone: (08) 8274 0339

12 May 2016

Dear David

RE: SITE SPECIFIC ASSESSMENT - AUTHORISATION

Project title: From qualified to specialist paramedic: a qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role

SSA reference: SSA/16 /SAH/142

Site Name: SA Ambulance Service

Thank you for submitting the site-specific assessment (SSA) form for this project which has been reviewed by the SAAS Research Review Committee. I note that your study has been ethically approved by the SA Health Research Ethics Committee, reference HREC/15/SAH/173, I am pleased to advise that your project has been authorised by Jason Killens, CEO of SAAS.

Please note the following conditions of authorisation:

- Authorisation is limited to the site identified in this letter only.
- Project authorisation is granted for the term of your project outlined in Section 9 of the SSA, or until the project is complete (whichever date is earlier). Should you require an extension to this timeframe, please submit an amendment to the SSA with a brief justification.
- The Coordinating Principal Investigator is responsible for notifying SAAS, via the Clinical Audit and Research Manager, of any changes to the status of the project within a timely manner, including discontinuation or withdrawal of the study at the named site, or changes to the scope of the project including the participants, research staff, site resources or other governance matters affecting the site.
- The study must be conducted in accordance with the conditions of ethical approval provided by the lead HREC, and in conjunction with the standards outlined in the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007)*.

- The Coordinating Principal Investigator must ensure regular (at least annual) progress reports are submitted. These progress reports should be submitted directly to the Clinical Audit and Research Manager.
- A copy of this letter should be maintained on file by the Coordinating Principal Investigator as evidence of project authorisation
- If university personnel are involved in this project, the Principal Investigator should notify the university before starting their research to ensure compliance with university requirements including any insurance and indemnification requirements.

Should you have any queries regarding your project authorisation please do contact me.

Yours sincerely

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'M. Thorrowgood', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Melanie Thorrowgood
Clinical Audit & Research Manager
SA Ambulance Service

Appendix H

Alberta Health Services Emergency Medical Services Operational

Approval

From: Ian Blanchard [<mailto:Ian.Blanchard@albertahealthservices.ca>]
Sent: Friday, 3 June 2016 5:39 AM
To: David Long <d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au>
Cc: Gerald Lazarenko <Gerald.Lazarenko@albertahealthservices.ca>
Subject: Research review

Hi David,

We hope all is well.

We just wanted to touch base to let you know that your research proposal entitled: *From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role* has received operational approval from Dr. Ian Phelps the Senior Medical Director for AHS EMS.

In the course of operational approval we have identified some areas that we would like to get your thoughts on (attached feedback/recommendations). Please let us know your thoughts on these and please accept them as a starting point for dialogue that we hope will improve the quality of your study and usefulness for the end users. We also want to make sure that all other approvals are in place prior to data collection. To that end, can you please let us know how the ethics review is going with HREBA.

Once the HREBA review is complete, we would encourage you as quickly as possible to connect with the larger AHS Research portfolio so that we can begin the process of creating a research agreement with AHS. Please email this address: Research.Administration@albertahealthservices.ca and advise them that your HREBA review is complete. Please c/c us using the email addresses on this email so that we can let them know that you have received operational approval by AHS EMS.

If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact us at your convenience.

Thanks David, we look forward to collaborating with you on your research!

Ian (and Dr. Gerald Lazarenko)

Ian Blanchard MSc, EMT-P
Senior Performance Strategist
Co-Chair, Research Committee
Alberta Health Services, Emergency Medical Services

Adjunct Assistant Professor
University of Calgary, Cumming School of Medicine, Department of Community Health Sciences

Cell | 403-669-2551

Appendix I

Alberta Health Services Research Agreement

RESEARCH AGREEMENT

BETWEEN:

AND

<p>David Long PhD Candidate, Queensland University of Technology Brisbane, Australia</p> <p>And</p> <p>Michele Clark Faculty of Health, School - Clinical Sciences Queensland University of Technology Brisbane, Australia</p> <p>(together, the "RESEARCHER")</p>	<p>Alberta Health Services Becky Wong Director, Research Administration Research, Innovation & Analytics 14th Floor - North Tower 10030 107 St NW Edmonton AB T5J 3E4 ("AHS")</p>
<p>If associated with an Research Ethics Board approved study insert REB Study Number: HREBA.CHC-16-0008</p>	

WHEREAS:

1. The RESEARCHER has requested the participation of AHS employees in interview as part of a research study (the "Research Study") regarding: From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role as described in Schedule "A";
2. AHS has considered the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study;
3. The parties wish to enter into an agreement to govern use of information arising from the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study;

THEREFORE, in consideration of the above, the covenants contained herein and other good and valuable consideration, the receipt and sufficiency of which is hereby acknowledged, each of the parties covenants and agrees with the other, as follows:

1. AHS shall allow the RESEARCHER to seek the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study in accordance with Schedule "A";
2. The RESEARCHER may use and disclose the information arising from the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study only for the purposes of the above named Research Study as described in Schedule "A";
3. The RESEARCHER shall not use or further disclose the information arising from the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study except as permitted or required by this Agreement and REB approved ethics submission;

4. The RESEARCHER shall not disclose to AHS personally identifying information regarding or arising from the participation or non-participation of AHS employees in the Research Study, except as required by law; The RESEARCHER shall not include any personally identifying information of AHS employees, patients or other individuals associated with AHS in any publication or presentation;
5. The RESEARCHER shall use appropriate safeguards to keep information arising from the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study secure and shall report to the AHS any unauthorized use or disclosure of which the RESEARCHER becomes aware, or of any breach of this Agreement by the RESEARCHER and cooperate with any AHS investigation of any such breach; and
6. The RESEARCHER shall ensure that any agent, contractor, partner, or any other individual or organization, that will have access to information arising from the participation of AHS employees in the Research Study, agrees to be bound by the same restrictions, terms and conditions that apply to the RESEARCHER pursuant to the Agreement.

By my signature hereunder, I AGREE to be bound by the terms and conditions herein effective as of date of execution.

Researcher (Principal Investigator)

David Long _____

Signature

28.07.16

Date

Academic Supervisor (if applicable)

Michele Clark _____

Signature

28th July 2016

Date

Appendix J

Approach Email to Participants (Example)

Dear Colleagues,

My name is David Long from School of Clinical Sciences at Queensland University of Technology (QUT) Brisbane, Australia and I'm doing a PhD in the process of transition from qualified to specialist paramedic in a low-acuity role.

If you'd like to help me in this study I'm looking for qualified or previously Community Paramedics from Alberta Health Services.

Please view the attached Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form for further details on the study.

Should you wish to participate or have any questions, please contact me via email at d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au

Please note that this study has been approved by the QUT Human Research Ethics Committee (approval number: 1500000813) and the Health Research Ethics Board of Alberta (HREBA) – Community Health Committee (CHC). If you have any complaints or concerns about the ethical conduct of this project, please contact: HREBA – Community Health Committee Suite 1500, 10104 - 103 AVE Edmonton AB, T5J 4A7 Phone: (780) 423-5727 / Toll-free: 1-877-423-5727 Email: communityhealth@hreba.ca

Many thanks for your consideration of this request.

David Long

PhD Candidate + 61 7 3138 0641 d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au

Professor Michele Clark Principal Supervisor +61 7 3138 3519

mj.clark@qut.edu.au

School of Clinical Sciences, Faculty of Health Queensland University of Technology (KG) Brisbane, Australia

Appendix K

Participant Information and Consent Form (Example)

	AUSTRALIAN PARTICIPANT INFORMATION FOR QUT RESEARCH PROJECT – Interview –
From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role.	
QUT Ethics Approval Number: 150000813 SA Health Ethics Approval Number: HREC-15-SAH-173 NSW Ambulance Approval Number: TRIM 15/1055	

RESEARCH TEAM

Principal Researcher:	David Long	PhD Candidate
Associate Researchers:	Prof Michele Clark	Principal Supervisor
	Dr David Lim	Associate Supervisor
	Dr Scott Devenish	Associate Supervisor
School of Clinical Science, Faculty of Health, Queensland University of Technology (QUT)		

DESCRIPTION

This project is being undertaken as part of PhD study for Mr. David Long.

The purpose of this project is to gain an understanding of the process of work role transition from qualified paramedic to Extended Care Paramedic (ECP) or Community Paramedic.

You are invited to participate in this project because you are either a currently qualified or formally qualified Extended Care Paramedic employed in New South Wales or South Australia.

PARTICIPATION

Your participation will involve an audio-recorded interview at an agreed public location that will take approximately one hour of your time. Questions will mainly be about your experience of work role transition. You may be contacted again with your approval if additional items of interest requiring clarification emerge.

Some examples include:

- Please describe the training you underwent as an ECP.
- What on-going support (if any) do you receive as an ECP?
- In what ways is the role of an ECP different from your previous role?

Your participation in this project is entirely voluntary. If you do agree to participate you can withdraw from the project without comment or penalty. If you withdraw within four (4) weeks, on request any identifiable information already obtained from you will be destroyed including any audio recordings. Your decision to participate or not participate will in no way impact upon your current or future relationship with QUT or with any Ambulance Service.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

It is expected that this project will not benefit you directly however an understanding of the process of work role transition may translate to enhancements in paramedic education programs and facilitate the recruitment, selection and retention of paramedics in a low-acuity role.

RISKS

There are minimal risks associated with your participation in this project. These include mild anxiety in discussing a potentially unpleasant experience during your working life and the transition to a specialist role.

Should you experience any discomfort or anxiety, there are a number of services available to assist you.

Both South Australia Ambulance Service and NSW Ambulance Service provide free counselling services to employees. The number in South Australia is **08 8431 9300** and New South Wales is **1300 360 364**. If you travel to Brisbane, QUT provides for limited free psychology, family therapy or counselling services (face-to-face only) for research participants of QUT projects who may experience discomfort or distress as a result of their participation in the research. Should you wish to access this service please call the Clinic Receptionist on **07 3138 0999** (Monday–Friday only 9am–5pm), QUT Psychology and Counselling Clinic, 44 Musk Avenue, Kelvin Grove, and indicate that you are a research participant. Alternatively, Lifeline provides access to online, phone or face-to-face support, call **13 11 14** for 24 hour telephone crisis support.

PRIVACY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

All comments and responses will be treated confidentially unless disclosure is required by law. No individual participant will be identified however due to the relatively small number of people in the specialist groups in which the participants will be drawn from, those that are intimately involved in the research may be able to take an "educated guess" in identifying an individual participant. This is a recognised small risk however the pooling of data will assist in mitigating this risk. Additionally, any contact details such as phone or email will be stored securely from the research data and will only be used for the intent to which it was provided.

This project involves audio recording. It is important to understand that:

- You will not have the opportunity to verify your comments and responses prior to final inclusion.
- The audio recording will be transcribed to text.
- The audio recording and associated transcription will be securely stored at QUT and destroyed five years after last publication arising from the research.
- The audio recording will not be used for any other purpose (e.g. as an instructional aide).
- No other researchers other than the Research Team will have access to the audio recording or transcription.
- It is not possible to participate in the project without being audio recorded or transcribed.
- A thesis, publications and conference paper may be presented using non-identified data.

Please note that non-identifiable data may be used for future research.

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

We would like to ask you to sign a written consent form (enclosed) to confirm your agreement to participate. The consent form will be securely stored at QUT for a period of 15 years and then destroyed.

QUESTIONS / FURTHER INFORMATION ABOUT THE PROJECT

If you have any questions or require further information please contact one of the researchers listed below.

David Long	07 3138 0641	d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au
Michele Clark	07 3138 3519	mi.clark@qut.edu.au
David Lim	07 3138 3347	c113.lim@qut.edu.au
Scott Devenish	07 3138 3581	scott.devenish@qut.edu.au

CONCERNS / COMPLAINTS REGARDING THE CONDUCT OF THE PROJECT

QUT is committed to research integrity and the ethical conduct of research projects. However, if you do have any concerns or complaints about the ethical conduct of the project you may contact the QUT Research Ethics Advisory Team on 07 3138 5123 or email ethicscontact@qut.edu.au. The QUT Research Ethics Advisory Team is not connected with the research project and can facilitate a resolution to your concern in an impartial manner.

Thank you for helping with this research project. Please keep this sheet for your information.

**From qualified to specialist paramedic:
A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role.**

QUT Ethics Approval Number: 1500000813
SA Health Ethics Approval Number: HREC-15-SAH-173
NSW Ambulance Approval Number: TRIM 15/1055

RESEARCH TEAM CONTACTS

David Long	07 3138 0641	d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au
Michele Clark	07 3138 3519	mi.clark@qut.edu.au
David Lim	07 3138 3347	c113.lim@qut.edu.au
Scott Devenish	07 3138 3581	scott.devenish@qut.edu.au

STATEMENT OF CONSENT

By signing below, you are indicating that you:

- Have read and understood the information document regarding this project.
- Have had any questions answered to your satisfaction.
- Understand that if you have any additional questions you can contact the research team.
- Understand that you are free to withdraw up to four (4) weeks after the interview without comment or penalty.
- Understand that you can contact the Research Ethics Advisory Team on 07 3138 5123 or email ethicscontact@qut.edu.au if you have concerns about the ethical conduct of the project.
- Understand that the project will include an audio recording.
- Understand non-identifiable data may be used for future research.
- Agree to participate in the project.

Name _____

Signature _____

Date _____

I agree to be contacted by email at a later point to arrange for another interview:

YES NO

My email address for contact is : _____

Please return this sheet to the investigator.

Appendix L

Participant Interview Guide

Research question:

“How do qualified paramedics transition to a specialist low-acuity role and what factors influence the transition?”

- > Introduce self and thank participant for their time.
- > Reason for research.
- > Reason for audio recording, transcription and confidentiality.
- > Don't have to answer if you don't want to. Can withdraw at any time.

Contextual – To start, I just have some general background questions.

How many years have you worked in Ambulance/EMS and as an ECP/CP?

Please tell me about your background and education prior to becoming an ECP/CP, for example, the training and other courses you have undertaken.

What is your role/what do you do as an ECP/CP?

Antecedents – What lead you to decide to become an ECP/CP?

What impact, do you think, your prior background / education / experience has on your role as an ECP/CP?

Thoughts on you or your colleagues having a nursing background?

What personal characteristics do you think are necessary for a successful ECP/CP?

End Points - At what point did you feel you have successfully completed the transition to ECP/CP (if at all)?

What stages did you go through? What emotions did you feel at each stage?

What factors influenced each stage of the transition ie. made the transition smoother or harder? What was your experience just after the course eg. with other “non-ECPs”, other health workers etc.

Is there anything else about the transition to the ECP/CP role you would like to add?

How long do you intend to continue working/did you work as an ECP/CP?

Supplemental areas (if not already covered)

Training - Please describe the training you underwent as an ECP/CP.

What was good and bad about it? What was challenging? What was of most value and why?

How important were clinical placements?

Support – Did you feel supported in the new role at an individual (peer) and organisational (systems) level?

Describe the first few weeks working as an ECP. Did you have someone to “show you the ropes”?

What on-going support (if any) do you receive as an ECP? (May include personal education initiatives and peer-to-peer mentoring).

Other

To what extent did the realities of the ECP role match the expectations of going into the role?

If you could change one thing about ECP, what would that be?

On a scale of 1-10 how valued/understood is your role by other paramedics and other healthcare professionals?

Appendix M

Transcription Confidentiality Agreement

QUT Queensland University of Technology Brisbane Australia	AGREEMENT TRANSCRIBER FOR QUT RESEARCH PROJECT
From qualified to specialist paramedic: A qualitative study of the process of transition to a low-acuity role.	
QUT Ethics Approval Number 1500000813	
RESEARCH TEAM CONTACTS	
David Long – PhD Candidate School of Clinical Sciences Faculty of Health Phone +61 7 3138 0641 Email d5.long@hdr.qut.edu.au	Professor Michele Clark – Prindpal Supervisor School of Clinical Sciences Faculty of Health Phone +61 7 3138 3519 Email mj.clark@qut.edu.au
THE AGREEMENT	
As this research involves questioning individuals about work role transition, I the Principal Researcher in this project, require you to sign this transcriber confidentiality agreement.	
As the transcriber for this project you must:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Keep all information related to this project secret and confidential.• Not disclose to any person or make known in any manner any part of the project's information.• Keep the project's information in a secure place so as to ensure that unauthorised persons do not have access to it.• To not make copies of any audiotapes or computerized files of the transcribed interview texts, unless specifically requested to do so by Mr. David Long.• To delete all electronic files containing study-related documents from my computer hard drive and any backup devices.	
SIGNATURES	
This Agreement shall be effective when signed and dated by all parties.	
Transcriber	Name Alexander D McAllister
	Signature
	Date 22/04/2016
Witness	Name Gediminas Tinteris
	Signature
	Date 22/04/2016